

Reduced Entries Algebraic Magic and PanMagic Squares of Order 12

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The whole work as pdf files is available at author's sites:
Magic and PanMagic: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16149>
Semi-magic: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16447>
This work is without use of any kind of programming language

Abstract

This work brings *magic*, *panmagic* and *semi-magic* squares of order 12 for the *reduced entries*. By *reduced* or *less entries* we understand that instead of considering 144 entries in a sequential way, we are using *non-sequential* entries in less numbers. These *non-sequential* entries may be *positive* and/or *negative numbers*. In some cases, these may be *decimal* or *fractional* values. It depends on the type of magic square. Initially, the work is written in terms of letters instead of numbers and then are followed by examples. These kind of magic squares sometimes we call as *algebraic* magic squares. The complete work is composed of 57 different types of magic squares of order 12. Out of them 28 are *magic*, 4 are *panmagic* or *pandiagonal* and 25 are *semi-magic* squares. In this work we bring total 32 different ways of writing *magic* and *panmagic* squares of order 12. By *panmagic* we understand that the magic squares are *pandiagonal*. We have divided this work in two parts. This part is composed of *magic* and *panmagic* squares. The second part is with *semi-magic* squares of order 12. In case of *semi-magic* squares some conditions are also explained to change them in magic squares. These are based on four types of magic squares, i.e., *pandiagonal*, *cornered*, *single-digit bordered* and *double-digit bordered* magic squares. This work also include the idea of *magic rectangles*. In each magic square, the *magic rectangles* of same order are equal in width and length. For similar kind of work for the orders 3 to 10 refer Taneja [37, 38]. Previously, the author [31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36] also brought similar kind of work for the orders 3 to 12 for the *dates* and *days* of the year 2025, where the *dates* are few entries and *days* are the sums of magic squares. The work is extension and enlarged version of author's previous works. This is the first part only on *magic* and *panmagic* squares. The second part of this work on *semi-magic* squares is given separately [40].

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1 Introduction

We have divided this work in two parts. This part is composed of **magic** and **panmagic** squares. The second part is with **semi-magic** squares of order 12. In case of **semi-magic** squares some conditions are also explained to bring the as magic squares. These are based on four types of magic squares, i.e., **pandiagonal**, **cornered**, **single-digit bordered** and **double-digit bordered** magic squares. This work also include the idea of **magic rectangles**. In each magic square, the **magic rectangles** of same order are equal in width and length. Below are two table giving the details of algebraic magic squares of orders 3 to 12:

Orders	Magic Squares	Pandiagonal Magic Squares	Semi-Magic Squares	Total
3	1	0	1	2
5	1	1	1	3
7	4	1	3	8
9	10	1	9	20
11	12	–	–	12

Orders	Magic Squares	Pandiagonal Magic Squares	Semi-Magic Squares	Total
4	1	1	0	2
6	2	2	1	5
8	5	1	3	9
10	9	1	10	20
12	28	4	25	57

The table give above brings the revised version of author’s previous work [37, 38] for orders 3 to 12 except order 11. The revised version of order 11 shall be given in another work. The author’s previous works [31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36] based on similar ideas for the orders 3 to 12 brings the **dates** and **days** of the year 2025, where the **dates** are few entries and **days** are the sums of magic squares. These previous works are on reduced entries algebraic magic squares. The web-site by F. Gaspalou [3] brings initial work on magic squares of orders 3, 4 and 5.

This first part brings 32 different type of reduced entries algebraic **magic** and **panmagic** squares. For the second parts on different type of reduced entries algebraic **semi-magic** squares refer the author’s work [40]. All these 57 algebraic **magic**, **panmagic** and **semi-magic** squares are with two numerical examples. In case of **magic** and **panmagic** squares , the examples are for even and odd number

magic sums. In some examples, the decimal entries are also considered. In case of **semi-magic** squares the numerical examples are for **semi-magic** and **magic** squares.

2 Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are six different examples of magic squares of order 12. These are based on sequential numbers from 1 to 144. These can be seen in author's previous works [24, 25, 26, 27, 28].

Example 2.1. *Let's consider a magic square of order 12.*

1	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	98	1	51	72	22	119	78	28	125	140	43	93	870
870	3	50	97	118	71	24	124	77	30	45	92	139	870
870	49	99	2	23	120	70	29	126	76	91	141	44	870
870	131	34	84	87	37	134	57	7	104	113	16	66	870
870	36	83	130	133	86	39	103	56	9	18	65	112	870
870	82	132	35	38	135	85	8	105	55	64	114	17	870
870	67	117	20	5	102	52	47	144	94	73	123	26	870
870	21	68	115	100	53	6	142	95	48	27	74	121	870
870	116	19	69	54	4	101	96	46	143	122	25	75	870
870	88	138	41	32	129	79	14	111	61	58	108	11	870
870	42	89	136	127	80	33	109	62	15	12	59	106	870
	137	40	90	81	31	128	63	13	110	107	10	60	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

It is a pandiagonal magic square of order 12, where the blocks of order 3 equal semi-magic sums semi-magic squares.

Example 2.2. *Let's consider a magic square of order 12*

2	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	7	140	1	142	15	132	9	134	23	124	17	126	870
870	2	141	8	139	10	133	16	131	18	125	24	123	870
870	144	3	138	5	136	11	130	13	128	19	122	21	870
870	137	6	143	4	129	14	135	12	121	22	127	20	870
870	31	116	25	118	39	108	33	110	47	100	41	102	870
870	26	117	32	115	34	109	40	107	42	101	48	99	870
870	120	27	114	29	112	35	106	37	104	43	98	45	870
870	113	30	119	28	105	38	111	36	97	46	103	44	870
870	55	92	49	94	63	84	57	86	71	76	65	78	870
870	50	93	56	91	58	85	64	83	66	77	72	75	870
870	96	51	90	53	88	59	82	61	80	67	74	69	870
	89	54	95	52	81	62	87	60	73	70	79	68	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

It is a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 12, where the blocks of order 4 equal magic sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 4.

Example 2.3. Let's consider a magic square of order 12

3	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										870	
	1	143	142	141	2	6	19	125	124	123	20	24	870
	138	8	136	9	11	133	120	26	118	27	29	115	870
	132	131	15	16	128	13	114	113	33	34	110	31	870
	18	14	129	130	17	127	36	32	111	112	35	109	870
	7	134	10	135	137	12	25	116	28	117	119	30	870
	139	5	3	4	140	144	121	23	21	22	122	126	870
	55	89	88	87	56	60	37	107	106	105	38	42	870
	84	62	82	63	65	79	102	44	100	45	47	97	870
	78	77	69	70	74	67	96	95	51	52	92	49	870
	72	68	75	76	71	73	54	50	93	94	53	91	870
	61	80	64	81	83	66	43	98	46	99	101	48	870
	85	59	57	58	86	90	103	41	39	40	104	108	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

It is a magic square of order 12, where the four blocks of order 6 are magic squares of equal magic sums.

Example 2.4. Let's consider a magic square of order 12

4	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											870
	134	143	3	141	5	1	22	124	20	126	18	133	870
	16	113	108	38	106	40	36	26	120	24	114	129	870
	15	35	48	42	102	104	91	53	93	47	110	130	870
	131	111	45	86	84	57	90	58	60	100	34	14	870
	132	33	46	56	71	76	65	78	89	99	112	13	870
	139	118	51	62	66	77	72	75	83	94	27	6	870
	128	23	101	64	80	67	74	69	81	44	122	17	870
	10	115	96	82	73	70	79	68	63	49	30	135	870
	9	29	95	85	61	88	55	87	59	50	116	136	870
	137	117	98	103	43	41	54	92	52	97	28	8	870
	7	31	37	107	39	105	109	119	25	121	32	138	870
	12	2	142	4	140	144	123	21	125	19	127	11	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

It is a well-known **single-digit bordered** magic square. The inner blocks are magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10.

Example 2.5. Let's consider a magic square of order 12

5	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											870
	66	67	77	80	86	59	54	91	23	122	134	11	870
	79	76	70	65	64	81	41	104	118	27	18	127	870
	74	69	75	72	58	87	97	48	106	39	9	136	870
	71	78	68	73	83	62	44	101	28	117	141	4	870
	55	82	61	60	88	89	98	47	121	24	126	19	870
	90	63	84	85	56	57	100	45	31	114	140	5	870
	103	92	99	43	49	93	51	50	38	107	123	22	870
	42	53	46	102	96	52	95	94	120	25	135	10	870
	26	40	30	36	112	34	110	116	108	113	21	124	870
	119	105	115	109	33	111	35	29	32	37	14	131	870
	1	143	128	137	133	16	130	7	20	13	3	139	870
	144	2	17	8	12	129	15	138	125	132	6	142	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

It is a **cornered** magic squares, where in each case the magic rectangles of orders 2×4 , 2×6 , 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal sums in each case. It contains magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 in the upper left corner.

Example 2.6. Let's consider a magic square of order 12

6	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										870
4	1	143	142	5	139	138	8	9	12	134	135	870
141	144	2	3	140	6	7	137	136	133	11	10	870
37	108	43	41	103	101	100	98	48	46	13	132	870
107	38	102	104	42	44	45	47	97	99	131	14	870
106	39	57	88	71	76	65	78	61	84	130	15	870
40	105	60	85	66	77	72	75	64	81	16	129	870
33	112	87	58	80	67	74	69	83	62	17	128	870
111	34	86	59	73	70	79	68	82	63	127	18	870
110	35	93	95	49	51	56	54	90	92	126	19	870
36	109	52	50	96	94	89	91	55	53	20	125	870
115	114	32	29	25	119	118	28	122	123	21	24	870
30	31	113	116	120	26	27	117	23	22	124	121	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic squares where the magic rectangles of order 2×4 and 2×8 are of equal sums in each case. It contains magic squares of orders 4 and 8.

Based on these six examples we shall give below 32 different types of **algebraic** magic and **panmagic** squares of order 12 for the reduced entries. By **panmagic** we understand as **pandiagonal** magic square.

3 Reduced Entries Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are 32 results with respective examples of reduced entries algebraic magic squares of order 12. To understand well, these are divided in different sub-blocks.

3.1 Reduced Entries Algebraic PanMagic Squares of Order 12

This section brings algebraic **pandiagonal** magic squares or **panmagic** squares of order 12 for the reduced entries. Along with results some examples are also given. Below are given four different ways of constructing algebraic pandiagonal magic squares of order 4. In the forth case, we need one an extra condition to be a pandiagonal.

Result 3.1. *Let's consider following algebraic magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:*

$(7/3)*S-A7-A8-A13-A14-A19-A20$	$A7+A8+A14-A3+A19+A20-(2/3)*S-A23$	$A13+A23+A3-(2/3)*S$	$(7/3)*S-A21-A22-A16-A15-A1-A2$	$A21-A17-A5+A22+A16+A1+A2-(2/3)*S$	$A15+A17+A5-(2/3)*S$	$(7/3)*S-A23-A24-A9-A10-A3-A4$	$A23+A24+A10-A7+A3+A4-A19-(2/3)*S$	$A7-(2/3)*S+A19+A9$	$(7/3)*S-A18-A17-A11-A12-A5-A6$	$A18+A17+A12+A5+A6-A1-(2/3)*S-A21$	$A11+A21+A1-(2/3)*S$
$A7+A8-(8/3)*S+2*A13+A14+A23+A3+A19+A20$	$S/3$	$(10/3)*S-A7-A8-2*A13-A14-A23-A3-A19-A20$	$A21+A22+A16+2*A15+A17+A5+A1+A2-(8/3)*S$	$S/3$	$(10/3)*S-A21-A22-A16-2*A15-A17-A5-A1-A2$	$A23+A24+A10+A7+A3+A4-(8/3)*S+A19+2*A9$	$S/3$	$(10/3)*S-A23-A24-A10-A7-A3-A4-A19-2*A9$	$A18+A17+2*A11+A12+A5+A6+A21+A1-(8/3)*S$	$S/3$	$(10/3)*S-A18-A17-2*A11-A12-A5-A6-A21-A1$
$(4/3)*S-A13-A23-A3$	$A23-A7-A8-A14+A3-A19-A20+(4/3)*S$	$A7+A8-(5/3)*S+A13+A14+A19+A20$	$(4/3)*S-A15-A17-A5$	$(4/3)*S-A21+A17+A5-A22-A16-A1-A2$	$A21+A22+A16+A1+5+A1+A2-(5/3)*S$	$(4/3)*S-A7-A19-A9$	$(4/3)*S-A23-A24-A10+A7-A3-A4+A19$	$A23+A24+A9+A10+A3+A4-(5/3)*S$	$(4/3)*S-A11-A21-A1$	$A21-A18-A17-A12-A5-A6+A1+(4/3)*S$	$A18+A17+A11+A12+A5+A6-(5/3)*S$
$A1+A2-S/3$	$2*S/3-A2$	$2*S/3-A1$	$A3+A4-S/3$	$2*S/3-A4$	$2*S/3-A3$	$A5+A6-S/3$	$2*S/3-A6$	$2*S/3-A5$	$A7+A8-S/3$	$2*S/3-A8$	$2*S/3-A7$
$4*S/3-2*A1-A2$	$S/3$	$2*A1+A2-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*A3-A4$	$S/3$	$2*A3+A4-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*A5-A6$	$S/3$	$2*A5+A6-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*A7-A8$	$S/3$	$2*A7+A8-2*S/3$
$A1$	$A2$	$S-A1-A2$	$A3$	$A4$	$S-A3-A4$	$A5$	$A6$	$S-A5-A6$	$A7$	$A8$	$S-A7-A8$
$A9+A10-S/3$	$2*S/3-A10$	$2*S/3-A9$	$A11+A12-S/3$	$2*S/3-A12$	$2*S/3-A11$	$A13+A14-S/3$	$2*S/3-A14$	$2*S/3-A13$	$A15+A16-S/3$	$2*S/3-A16$	$2*S/3-A15$
$4*S/3-2*A9-A10$	$S/3$	$2*A9+A10-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*A11-A12$	$S/3$	$2*A11+A12-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*A13-A14$	$S/3$	$2*A13+A14-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*A15-A16$	$S/3$	$2*A15+A16-2*S/3$
$A9$	$A10$	$S-A9-A10$	$A11$	$A12$	$S-A11-A12$	$A13$	$A14$	$S-A13-A14$	$A15$	$A16$	$S-A15-A16$
$A17+A18-S/3$	$2*S/3-A18$	$2*S/3-A17$	$A19+A20-S/3$	$2*S/3-A20$	$2*S/3-A19$	$A21+A22-S/3$	$2*S/3-A22$	$2*S/3-A21$	$A23+A24-S/3$	$2*S/3-A24$	$2*S/3-A23$
$4*S/3-2*A17-A18$	$S/3$	$2*A17+A18-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*A19-A20$	$S/3$	$2*A19+A20-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*A21-A22$	$S/3$	$2*A21+A22-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*A23-A24$	$S/3$	$2*A23+A24-2*S/3$
$A17$	$A18$	$S-A17-A18$	$A19$	$A20$	$S-A19-A20$	$A21$	$A22$	$S-A21-A22$	$A23$	$A24$	$S-A23-A24$

Details:

It is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 with 12 **equal sums** magic squares of order 3. The letter M represents the magic sum of order 3. In this case, $R = 4 \times M$ is the sum of the magic square of order 3. Below are two examples.

Example 3.1. Let's consider following two examples:

$A3+A17-A21+A10-A13$	$A4+A6+2*A21-A28-A26-2*A25-2*A10+2*A13+A18+A20-A1$	$A23+A1-A24-2*A21+A28-A9-A27+A8+A25-A7-A11+A12-A6+2*A10-A13+A17+A5$	$A24+A21+A26+A9+A27-A8+A25+A7+A11-A18-A20-A12-A10-A4+S-A3-2*A17-A5-A23$	$A10+A3+A17-A25-A7$	$A22+A24+2*A21-A2-A28-A26+2*A7+A6-2*A10+A4-2*A17$	$A23-A19-A15-A24+A16-A21+A2-A9+A8-A25-2*A7+A20-A6+A10+A13+2*A17+A5$	$A19+A15-A22-A16-A21+A28+A26+A9-A8+2*A25+A7-A20-A13-A4+S-A3-A17-A5-A23$	A3	A4	A5	$S-A3-A4-A5$
A1	$A28+A26+2*A25-A18-A20-A6+A10-A13-A4+S-A3-A17-A21$	$A24+A21-A28+A9+A27-A8-A25+A7+A11-A12+A6-A10+A3-A5-A23$	$A23-A1-A24-A26-A9-A27+A8-A25-A7-A11+A18+A20+A12+A13+A4+A17+A5$	A2	$A28+A26+A25-A7-A6+A10-A4+S-A3+A17-A22-A24-2*A21$	$A19+A15+A24-A16+A21+A9-A8+A7-A20+A6-A13+A3-A17-A5-A23$	$A23-A19-A15+A22+A16+A21-A2-A28-A26-A9+A8-A25+A20-A10+A13+A4+A5$	A6	$S-A3-A4-A6$	$A3-A5+A6$	$A4+A5-A6$
$A24+2*A21-A28+A9+A27-A8-A25+A7+A11-A12+A6-2*A10+A13+(1/2)*S-A17-A5-A23-A1$	$A23-A24-A21-A26-A9-A27+A8-A25-A7-A11+A18+A20+A12+A10+A4-(1/2)*S+A3+2*A17+A5$	$(1/2)*S-A3-A17+A21-A10+A13$	$(1/2)*S+A1-A4-A6-2*A21+A28+A26+2*A25+2*A10-2*A13-A18-A20$	$A19+A15+A24-A16+A21-A2+A9-A8+A25+2*A7-A20+A6-A10-A13+(1/2)*S-2*A17-A5-A23$	$A23-A19-A15+A22+A16+A21-A28-A26-A9+A8-2*A25-A7+A20+A13+A4-(1/2)*S+A3+A17+A5$	$(1/2)*S+A25+A7-A10-A3-A17$	$A2+A28+A26-2*A7-A6+2*A10-A4+(1/2)*S+2*A17-A22-A24-2*A21$	$S/2-A5$	$A3+A4+A5-S/2$	$S/2-A3$	$S/2-A4$
$A23-A24-A21+A28-A9-A27+A8+A25-A7-A11+A12-A6+A10+(1/2)*S-A3+A5$	$A1+A24+A26+A9+A27-A8+A25+A7+A11-A18-A20-A12-A13-A4+(1/2)*S-A17-A5-A23$	$S/2-A1$	$A21-A28-A26-2*A25+A18+A20+A6-A10+A13+A4-(1/2)*S+A3+A17$	$A23-A19-A15-A24+A16-A21-A9+A8-A7+A20-A6+A13+(1/2)*S-A3+A17+A5$	$A19+A15-A22-A16-A21+A2+A28+A26+A9-A8+A25-A20+A10-A13-A4+(1/2)*S-A5-A23$	$S/2-A2$	$A22+A24+2*A21-A28-A26-A25+A7+A6-A10+A4-(1/2)*S+A3-A17$	$S/2-A3+A5-A6$	$S/2-A4-A5+A6$	$S/2-A6$	$A3+A4+A6-S/2$
A7	$A16-A28-A26-A9-2*A25-2*A7+A18+A20+A14+2*A13+2*A17$	A8	$A28+A26+A9-A8+2*A25+A7-A18-A20-A14-2*A13+S-2*A17-A16$	A10	$A22+A24+A16+2*A21-A28-A26-2*A25-A12+A14-2*A10+2*A13$	A11	$S+A10-A22-A24-A16-2*A21+A28+A26+2*A25+A12-A14-2*A13-A11$	A13	A14	A15	$S-A13-A14-A15$
A9	$A28+A26+2*A25+A7-A18-A20-A14-2*A13+S-2*A17-A16$	$A7-A8+A9$	$A16-A28-A26-2*A9+A8-2*A25-2*A7+A18+A20+A14+2*A13+2*A17$	A12	$S+A10-A22-A24-A16-2*A21+A28+A26+2*A25-A14-2*A13$	$A10-A11+A12$	$A22+A24+A16+2*A21-A28-A26-2*A25-2*A12+A14-2*A10+2*A13+A11$	A16	$S-A13-A14-A16$	$A13-A15+A16$	$A14+A15-A16$
$S/2-A8$	$A16-A28-A26-A9+A8-2*A25-A7+A18+A20+A14+2*A13-(1/2)*S+2*A17$	$S/2-A7$	$A28+A26+A9+2*A25+2*A7-A18-A20-A14-2*A13+(1/2)*S-2*A17-A16$	$S/2-A11$	$A22+A24+A16+2*A21-A28-A26-2*A25-A12+A14+2*A13+A11-(1/2)*S-A10$	$S/2-A10$	$(1/2)*S-A22-A24-A16-2*A21+A28+A26+2*A25+A14+2*A13-A14+2*A10-2*A13$	$S/2-A15$	$A13+A14+A15-S/2$	$S/2-A13$	$S/2-A14$
$S/2-A7+A8-A9$	$A28+A26+2*A9-A8+2*A25+2*A7-A18-A20-A14-2*A13+(1/2)*S-2*A17-A16$	$S/2-A9$	$A16-A28-A26-2*A25-A7+A18+A20+A14+2*A13-(1/2)*S+2*A17$	$S/2-A10+A11-A12$	$(1/2)*S-A22-A24-A16-2*A21+A28+A26+2*A25+2*A12-A14+2*A10-2*A13-A11$	$S/2-A12$	$A22+A24+A16+2*A21-A28-A26-2*A25+A14+2*A13-(1/2)*S-A10$	$S/2-A13+A15-A16$	$S/2-A14-A15+A16$	$S/2-A16$	$A13+A14+A16-S/2$
A17	A18	A19	$S-A17-A18-A19$	A21	A22	A23	$S-A21-A22-A23$	A25	A26	A27	$S-A25-A26-A27$
A20	$S-A17-A18-A20$	$A17-A19+A20$	$A18+A19-A20$	A24	$S-A21-A22-A24$	$A21-A23+A24$	$A22+A23-A24$	A28	$S-A25-A26-A28$	$A25-A27+A28$	$A26+A27-A28$
$S/2-A19$	$A17+A18+A19-S/2$	$S/2-A17$	$S/2-A18$	$S/2-A23$	$A21+A22+A23-S/2$	$S/2-A21$	$S/2-A22$	$S/2-A27$	$A25+A26+A27-S/2$	$S/2-A25$	$S/2-A26$
$S/2-A17+A19-A20$	$S/2-A18-A19+A20$	$S/2-A20$	$A17+A18+A20-S/2$	$S/2-A21+A23-A24$	$S/2-A22-A23+A24$	$S/2-A24$	$A21+A22+A24-S/2$	$S/2-A25+A27-A28$	$S/2-A26-A27+A28$	$S/2-A28$	$A25+A26+A28-S/2$

Details:

It is also a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 with 12 **equal sums** magic squares of order 4. The letter M represents the magic sum of order 4. In this case, $R = 3 \times M$ is the sum of the magic square of order 4. The magic squares of order 4 are also **pandiagonals**. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sums of orders should be even numbers. Below are two examples.

Example 3.2. Let's consider following two examples:

$3*m-A29-A21-A15-A8-A3$	$A3-A22+A13+A29+A15+A14-3*m+A1+A2+A27-A9+A28$	$A31+A5-A10-A14+A16-A34+3*m-A27-A1-A7-A13-A20$	$A20-A31+A21-A5+A10-A28+A22-A16+A34+A8+A9-m+A7-A2$	$A35+A4-A19-A3-A6+A22-A32-A29-A8+3*m-A17-A18$	$A2+A3+A6-A35-A4+A28-A22+A32+A14+A29-A9-3*m+A27+A1+A13+A17$	$A31-A10-A28-A14+A11+3*m-A27-A1-A13-A20$	$A18+A19+A20-A31+A10-A11+A8+A9-m-A2$	$A25+A4-A19-A3-A32-A12-A8-A9+3*m+A24-A18-A21$	$A2+A28+A3-A4-A22+A32+A14+A12-3*m+A27+A1+A13$	$3*m-A27-A1-A7-A13-A20$	$A18+A19+A20+A21-A25-A28-A14+A22+A8+A9-m-A24+A7-A2$
$A3+A29+A21+A15-2*m+A8$	$A22-A13-A29-A15-A14+4*m-A1-A2-A27+A9-A28-A3$	$A20-A31-A5+A10+A14-A16+A34-2*m+A27+A1+A7+A13$	$A2-A20+A31-A21+A5-A10+A28-A22+A16-A34-A8-A9+2*m-A7$	$A18+A19+A3+A6-A35-A4-A22+A32+A29+A8-2*m+A17$	$A35+A4-A28+A22-A32-A14-A29+A9+4*m-A27-A1-A13-A17-A2-A3-A6$	$A20-A31+A10+A28+A14-A11-2*m+A27+A1+A13$	$A2-A18-A19-A20+A31-A10+A11-A8-A9+2*m$	$A18+A19+A3+A21-A25-A4+A32+A12+A8+A9-2*m-A24$	$A4-A3+A22-A32-A14-A12-A27-A1+4*m-A13-A2-A28$	$A20+A27+A1+A7+A13-2*m$	$A2-A18-A19-A20-A21+A25+A28+A14-A22-A8-A9+2*m+A24-A7$
$A20-A33-A5-A23+A27+A1+A7$	$A2-A20+A5+A23+A28-A34-A7$	$A25+A3+A6-A22+A29-A9-A35$	$A33-A25-A28+A35-A3-A6+A22-A29+A34+A9+2*m-A27-A1-A2$	$A20-A33-A26-A5+A10+A30+A1$	$A2-A20+A31+A26+A5-A10-A34$	$A19+A3+A6-A35-A4-A22+A32$	$A35+A33+A4-A30-A19-A3-A6+A22-A32+A34+2*m-A1-A2-A31$	A1	A2	A3	$2*m-A1-A2-A3$
$A33+A5+A23+m-A27-A1-A7-A20$	$A20-A5-A23-A28+A34+m+A7-A2$	$A35-A25+A22-A29+A9+m-A3-A6$	$A2-A33+A25+A28+A3+A6-A35-A22+A29-A34-A9-m+A27+A1$	$A33+A26+A5-A10-A30+m-A1-A20$	$A20-A31-A26-A5+A10+A34+m-A2$	$m+A35+A4-A19-A3-A6+A22-A32$	$A2+A19+A31+A3+A6-A35-A33-A4+A30-A22+A32-A34-m+A1$	m-A1	m-A2	m-A3	$A1+A2+A3-m$
$A18+A19-A25-A4+A8+A9-A24$	A4	A5	$A25-A19-A8-A9+2*m+A24-A18-A5$	$A21-A25+A22+A8+A9-A24-A6$	A6	A7	$A25-A22-A8-A9+2*m+A24-A7-A21$	A8	A9	A10	$2*m-A8-A9-A10$
$A25+A4-A19-A8-A9+m+A24-A18$	m-A4	m-A5	$A18+A19+A5-A25+A8+A9-m-A24$	$A25+A6-A22-A8-A9+m+A24-A21$	m-A6	m-A7	$A21-A25+A22+A8+A9-m-A24+A7$	m-A8	m-A9	m-A10	$A8+A9+A10-m$
$A28-A30+A14-A11+A27+A13-A31$	A11	A12	$2*m+A31-A28+A30-A14-A27-A13-A12$	A13	A14	A15	$2*m-A13-A14-A15$	$A33-A30+A14-A16+A34+A13-A31$	A16	A17	$A31-A33+A30-A14-A34+2*m-A13-A17$
$m+A31-A28+A30-A14+A11-A27-A13$	m-A11	m-A12	$A28-A30+A14+A27+A13+A12-m-A31$	m-A13	m-A14	m-A15	$A13+A14+A15-m$	$A31-A33+A30-A14+A16-A34+m-A13$	m-A16	m-A17	$A33-A30+A14+A34-m+A13+A17-A31$
A18	A19	A20	$2*m-A18-A19-A20$	A21	A22	A23	$2*m-A21-A22-A23$	A24	A25	A26	$2*m-A24-A25-A26$
m-A18	m-A19	m-A20	$A18+A19+A20-m$	m-A21	m-A22	m-A23	$A21+A22+A23-m$	m-A24	m-A25	m-A26	$A24+A25+A26-m$
A27	A28	A29	$2*m-A27-A28-A29$	A30	A31	A32	$2*m-A30-A31-A32$	A33	A34	A35	$2*m-A33-A34-A35$
m-A27	m-A28	m-A29	$A27+A28+A29-m$	m-A30	m-A31	m-A32	$A30+A31+A32-m$	m-A33	m-A34	m-A35	$A33+A34+A35-m$

Details:

It is also a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 with 12 **equal sums** magic rectangles of order 2×4 . The letter m represents the width of magic rectangle. In this case, $R_{12 \times 12} = 6m$ is the sum of the magic square of order 12, where m is the width of each magic rectangle. These types of magic squares we call as **striped** magic squares. For more details on **striped** magic squares refer author's work [27, 28]. Below are two examples.

Example 3.3. Let's consider following two examples:

$(R-2*S)/2-A21$	A22	$(R-2*S)/2-A15$	$(R-2*S)/2-A16$	$(R-2*S)/2-A17$	$(R-2*S)/2-A18$	$7*R-A25-A27+A6+A16-A26-A23+A8+A2+A7-A28-A29+A5-A4+2*A21-21*S$	$A25+A27-A6+A15+A26+A18+A23-A8-A2-A7+A28+A29+A19+A20-A5+A4-8*R-2*A21+23*S+A17$	$(R-2*S)/2-A19$	$(R-2*S)/2-A20$	$6*S-2*R+(-2/3)*R-A21+(5/2)*S-A22+A21$	$(7/6)*R-(7/2)*S+A21$
$5*S-A22-(3/2)*R$	A21	A15	A16	A17	A18	$A25+A27-A6-A16+A26+A23-A8-A2-A7+A28+A29-A5+A4-2*A21+20*S-(13/2)*R$	$(17/2)*R-A25-A27+A6-A15-A26-A18-A23+A8+A2+A7-A28-A29-A19-A20+A5-A4+2*A21-24*S-A17$	A19	A20	$(5/2)*S-(2/3)*R-A21$	$(7/6)*R+A22-(7/2)*S$
$(R-2*S)/2-A23$	A23	$(7/2)*R+A2-(21/2)*S-A21-A28+2*A21+A6-A19$	$A25-A1-2*A6+A26+A18-2*A2+2*A28+2*A19-4*A21+50*S+A17-(33/2)*R$	$15*R+A10-A25+A1+2*A6-A9-A26-A18+A8+2*A2+A7-A28-A29+A3-A19-A20+A4+4*A21-46*S-A17$	$A20-2*R-A21+(15/2)*S-A3-A2+A9-A10-A4-A8+A29-A6-A7$	A2	A3	A4	$S-A2-A3-A4$	$(31/3)*R-A14+A6+A2-A28+A29-A19+2*A21-31*S-A17$	$A14-A6-A2+A28-A29+A19-2*A21+30*S+A17-(59/6)*R$
$(R-2*S)/2-A24$	A24	A1	$13*R-A25+A6-A26-A18+A2-A28-A19+3*A21-(77/2)*S-A17$	$A25-A6+A9+A26+A18-A8-A2-A7+A29-A3+A20-A4-3*A21+71*S/2+A17-(23/2)*R-A10$	$A19-A20-(3/2)*R+4*S+A3-A1-A9+A10+A4+A8+A28-A29+A7$	A5	$S-A2-A3-A5$	$A2-A4+A5$	$A3+A4-A5$	A12	$(R-2*S)/2-A12$
$(R-2*S)/2-A25$	A25	$A25-A1-2*A6+A9+A26+A18-A8-2*A2-A7+A28+A29-A3+A19+A20-A4-4*A21+(93/2)*S+A17-15*R-A10$	$2*R+A21-7*S+A3+A2-A9+A10+A4+A8-A29+A6+A7-A20$	$A19-(7/2)*R-A2+11*S+A21+A28-2*A21-A6$	$(33/2)*R-A25+A1+2*A6-A26-A18+2*A2-2*A28-2*A19+4*A21-(99/2)*S-A17$	$S/2-A4$	$A2+A3+A4-S/2$	$S/2-A2$	$S/2-A3$	$A16+A15+A18-2*A2-A3+A19+A20-A5-2*A21+10*S+A17-(19/6)*R-A13$	$(11/3)*R+A13-A16-A15-A18+2*A2+A3-A19-A20+A5+2*A21-11*S-A17$
$(R-2*S)/2-A26$	A26	$(23/2)*R+A10-A25+A6-A9-A26-A18+A8+A2+A7-A29+A3-A20+A4+3*A21-35*S-A17$	$A20+(3/2)*R-(7/2)*S-A3+A1+A9-A10-A4-A8-A28+A29-A7-A19$	$S/2-A1$	$A25-A6+A26+A18-A2+A28+A19-3*A21+39*S+A17-13*R$	$S/2-A2+A4-A5$	$S/2-A3-A4+A5$	$S/2-A5$	$A2+A3+A5-S/2$	A13	$(R-2*S)/2-A13$
$3*(2*S-R)/2+A23+A24+A25+A26+A27+A28+A29$	$2*(R-2*S)-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29$	A6	A7	A8	$S-A6-A7-A8$	$A19-(7/2)*R+(21/2)*S-A21+A28$	$A20+(3/2)*R-4*S-A10-A28+A29-A19$	A9	$2*R+A21-(11/2)*S-A9+A10-A29-A20$	$A25-A12-A6+A26-A2+2*A28+A19-2*A21+17*S+A17-(17/3)*R$	$(37/6)*R-A25+A12+A6-A26+A2-2*A28-A19+2*A21-18*S-A17$
$(R-2*S)/2-A27$	A27	$A25-2*A6+A26+A18-2*A2-A7+A28+A29-A3+A19+A20-A5-4*A21+46*S+A17-15*R$	$A6+15*R-A25-A26-A18+2*A2-A28-A29+A3-A19-A20+A5+4*A21-A17-45*S$	$A25-A6+A26+A18-A8-2*A2-A7+A28+A29-A3+A19+A20-A5-4*A21+46*S+A17-15*R$	$2*A7+A8+15*R-A25+2*A6-A26-A18+2*A2-A28-A29+A3-A19-A20+A5+4*A21-46*S-A17$	A10	$2*R+A21-(11/2)*S-A29-A20$	$A19-(7/2)*R+(21/2)*S-A21-A9+A10+A28$	$A20+(3/2)*R-4*S+A9-2*A10-A28+A29-A19$	A14	$(R-2*S)/2-A14$
$(R-2*S)/2-A28$	A28	$S/2-A8$	$A6+A7+A8-S/2$	$S/2-A6$	$S/2-A7$	$S/2-A9$	$A20-2*R-A21+6*S+A9-A10+A29$	$(7/2)*R-10*S+A21-A28-A19$	$A19-A20-(3/2)*R+(9/2)*S+A10+A28-A29$	$21*S-(13/2)*R-A6-A16-A8-A7-A21$	$7*R+A6+A16+A8+A7+A21-22*S$
$(R-2*S)/2-A29$	A29	$A6+A8+15*R-A25-A26-A18+2*A2+A7-A28-A29-A19-A20+A3+A5+4*A21-A17-(91/2)*S$	$A25-2*A6+A26+A18-A8-2*A2-2*A7+A28+A29-A3+A19+A20-A5-4*A21+(93/2)*S+A17-15*R$	$15*R-A25+2*A6-A26-A18+2*A2+A7-A28-A29+A3-A19-A20+A5+4*A21-(91/2)*S-A17$	$A25+A26+A18-2*A2+A28+A29+A19+A20-A3-A5-4*A21+(91/2)*S+A17-A6-15*R$	$(7/2)*R-10*S+A21+A9-A10-A28-A19$	$A19-A20-(3/2)*R+(9/2)*S-A9+2*A10+A28-A29$	$S/2-A10$	$A20-2*R-A21+6*S+A29$	$7*R-A25+A6-A15-A26-A18+A8+2*A2+A7-A28-A29+A3-A19-A20+A5+3*A21-21*S-A17$	$A25-A6+A15+A26+A18-A8-2*A2-A7+A28+A29-A3+A19+A20-A5-3*A21+20*S+A17-(13/2)*R$
$(7/6)*R+A22-(7/2)*S$	$(5/3)*R-(9/2)*S-A21$	$A14-A29+(29/2)*S+A17-(29/6)*R$	$A25-A12-A6+A26+A18-A2+A28+A19-2*A21+(57/2)*S+A17-(19/2)*R$	$(17/3)*R+A13-A16-A18+A23+2*A2+A3-A19-A20+A5+2*A21-(35/2)*S-A17$	$(3/2)*R-(9/2)*S+A21-A13+A24+A16-A21$	$A12-A26+A19+(5/2)*S-(5/6)*R$	$(21/2)*R-A25-A14+A6+A2-A28+A29-A19+A20+2*A21-(63/2)*S-A17$	$(1/2)*R-A21-(1/2)*S-A5-A2+A4-A24$	$(9/2)*S-A3-A23-A4-A2-R-A21$	A21	$12*S-(23/6)*R-A22$
$(7/2)*S-(7/6)*R+A21$	$(17/2)*S-(8/3)*R-A22$	$(16/3)*R-A14+A29-(31/2)*S-A17$	$10*R-A25+A12+A6-A26-A18+A2-A28-A19+2*A21-(59/2)*S-A17$	$A16+A18-A23-2*A2-A3+A19+A20-A5-2*A21+(33/2)*S+A17-(31/6)*R-A13$	$A13-A24-A16+A21-R+(7/2)*S-A21$	$A26-A19-2*(-2/3)*R-A21+(5/2)*S-2*A21+(3/2)*S-A12$	$A25+A14-A6-A2+A28-A29+A19-A20-2*A21+(61/2)*S+A17-10*R$	$A2+A5-A4+A24+A21-(1/2)*S$	$(3/2)*R-(11/2)*S+A2+A21+A3+A23+A4$	$R-2*S-2*(-2/3)*R-A21+(5/2)*S+A22-A21-A21$	$(R-2*S)/2-A21$

Details:

It is a *double-digit bordered* magic square of order 12 embedded with four equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 4. It is almost a *pandiagonal* magic square, except at two *cross-pandiagonals*. In order to bring it as a *pandiagonal* we must have a condition, i.e., $R = 3 \times S$, where the letters S, L and R are magic sums of orders 4, 8 and 12. Also $L = 2 \times S$. The magic squares of order 4 and 8 are *pandiagonal*. See the examples below.

Example 3.4. Let's consider following two examples:

	mgc	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240		pan	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	
240	-18	50	-11	-12	-13	-14	-334	537	-16	-17	75	13	240	180	-1	32	5	4	3	2	-66	171	1	0	-2	31	180	
240	40	48	41	42	43	44	364	-507	46	47	17	15	240	180	-2	31	25	26	27	28	96	-141	29	30	-1	32	180	
240	-21	51	-131	679	-618	160	12	13	14	51	-311	341	240	180	-3	33	-8	99	-68	37	12	13	14	21	11	19	180	
240	-22	52	11	-469	498	50	15	50	13	12	34	-4	240	180	-4	34	11	-42	71	20	15	20	13	12	22	8	180	
240	-23	53	663	-115	176	-634	31	-6	33	32	219	-189	240	180	-5	35	98	-7	38	-69	16	9	18	17	58	-28	180	
240	-24	54	-453	-5	34	514	32	33	30	-5	36	-6	240	180	-6	36	-41	10	19	72	17	18	15	10	23	7	180	
240	288	-258	16	17	18	39	159	-21	22	-70	320	-290	240	180	162	-132	16	17	18	9	36	12	19	-7	91	-61	180	
240	-25	55	647	-590	645	-612	23	-71	160	-22	37	-7	240	180	-7	37	97	-70	95	-62	20	-8	37	11	24	6	180	
-180	-26	56	27	6	29	28	23	115	-114	66	189	-159	240	180	-8	38	12	21	14	13	11	37	-6	18	-18	48	180	
240	-27	57	-600	657	-602	635	-115	67	22	116	-404	434	240	180	-9	39	-65	92	-67	100	-7	19	10	38	-91	121	180	
660	15	-53	168	423	-202	13	51	-322	-38	27	48	110	240	180	32	-1	12	81	0	37	15	6	-18	-13	31	-2	180	
	83	75	-138	-393	232	17	-21	352	68	3	-20	-18	240		31	-2	18	-51	30	-7	15	24	48	43	32	-1	180	
31a	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	31b	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180

The magic sums of first example are $R_{12 \times 12} := 240$ and $SR_{4 \times 4} := 90$, and the second example are $R_{12 \times 12} := 180$ and $M_{4 \times 4} := 60$. The second example is a **pandiagonal** magic squares. It satisfies the condition $R = 3 \times S$, i.e. $180 = 3 \times 60$. In both the examples the magic squares of order 4 and 8 are **pandiagonal**.

3.2 Double-Digit Bordered Magic Squares

Below are four examples of reduced entries magic squares of order 12.

Result 3.5. *Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:*

$(R-T)/2-A50$	A52	$(R-T)/2-A43$	$(R-T)/2-A44$	$(R-T)/2-A45$	$(R-T)/2-A46$	$3*(T-R)/2+A43$ $+A44+A45+A46+A47$ $+A48+A49$	$(R-T)/2-A47$	$(R-T)/2-A48$	$(R-T)/2-A49$	$3*T-2*R+A42-$ $A52+A50$	$(R-T)/2-A42$
A51	A50	A43	A44	A45	A46	$2*(R-T)-A43-A44-A45-$ $A46-A47 -A48-A49$	A47	A48	A49	A42	$2*T-R-A51-A50-$ $A42$
$(R-T)/2-A53$	A53	A19	a35	$T-M-A16-A17-$ $A18$	A16	A17	A18	$A19-A20+2*M$ $+A24-T$	$T-M-A24-$ $2*A19$	A35	$(R-T)/2-A35$
$(R-T)/2-A54$	A54	$2*A14+A25+A15+$ $2*A19-T+M-A20$	$T-M-2*A19-A14$	$A16+A17+A18-$ $(T-M)/2$	$(T-M)/2-A16$	$(T-M)/2-A17$	$(T-M)/2-A18$	$T-M-A24-A14-$ $A25-A19+A20$	$2*M-T+A19$ $+A24-A15$	A36	$(R-T)/2-A36$
$(R-T)/2-A55$	A55	$T-M-A8-A9-A10$	$A8+A9+A10-(T-$ $M)/2$	A1	$A4+M-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	$A11+A12+A13-(T-$ $M)/2$	$T-M-A11-A12-$ $A13$	A37	$(R-T)/2-A37$
$(R-T)/2-A56$	A56	A8	$(T-M)/2-A8$	A6	A4	A5	$M-A4-A5-A6$	$(T-M)/2-A11$	A11	A38	$(R-T)/2-A38$
$3*(T-R)/2+A53+$ $A54+A55+A56+$ $A57+A58+A59$	$2*(R-T)-A53-A54-$ $A55-A56-A57 -$ $A58-A59$	A9	$(T-M)/2-A9$	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$M-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	$(T-M)/2-A12$	A12	$2*(R-T)-A35-A36 -$ $A37-A38-A39 -$ $A40-A41$	$3*(T-R)/2+A35$ $+A36+A37+A38+$ $A39+A40+A41$
$(R-T)/2-A57$	A57	A10	$(T-M)/2-A10$	$M-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-$ $A6$	A2	$(T-M)/2-A13$	A13	A39	$(R-T)/2-A39$
$(R-T)/2-A58$	A58	$T-2*A14-A15+A20-$ $3*A19-A24-A25$	$A24+3*A19+A25-$ $A20+A14-T+M$	$A21+A22+A23-$ $(T-M)/2$	$(T-M)/2-A21$	$(T-M)/2-A22$	$(T-M)/2-A23$	A14	A15	A40	$(R-T)/2-A40$
$(R-T)/2-A59$	A59	A24	$M-A25-A24-A19$	$T-M-A21-A22-$ $A23$	A21	A22	A23	A25	A19	A41	$(R-T)/2-A41$
$2*T-R-A42-A34-$ $A51$	$R-T-A42-A50-A34$	A27	A28	A29	A30	$2*(R-T)-A27-A28-A29-$ $A30-A31-A32-A33$	A31	A32	A33	A34	$T-R+2*A42$ $+A50+A34+A51$
$(T-R)/2+A42$ $+A50+A34$	$3*T-2*R+A42$ $+A34-A52$	$(R-T)/2-A27$	$(R-T)/2-A28$	$(R-T)/2-A29$	$(R-T)/2-A30$	$3*(T-R)/2+A27 +A28$ $+A29+A30$ $+A31+A32+A33$	$(R-T)/2-A31$	$(R-T)/2-A32$	$(R-T)/2-A33$	$R-T-2*A42+A52-$ $A50-A34$	$(R-T)/2-A34$

Details:

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 12 embedded with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 8. The internal magic square is of order 4. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×8 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, T and R represents the magic squares of orders 4, 8 and 12. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums T and R should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Example 3.5. Let's consider following two examples:

1	mgc												200	1	mgc												221
	-35	62	-28	-29	-30	-31	317	-32	-33	-34	100	-27	200		-25	62	-18	-19	-20	-21	287	-22	-23	-24	61	-17	221
	61	60	53	54	55	56	-292	57	58	59	52	-73	200		61	60	53	54	55	56	-252	57	58	59	52	-92	221
	-38	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	63	-32	45	-20	200		-28	63	29	30	-21	26	27	28	64	-32	45	-10	221
	-39	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	68	46	-21	200		-29	64	76	-22	51	4	3	2	-32	69	46	-11	221
	-40	65	3	27	11	77	-11	13	36	-6	47	-22	200		-30	65	3	27	11	78	-11	13	36	-6	47	-12	221
	-41	66	18	12	16	14	15	45	9	21	48	-23	200		-31	66	18	12	16	14	15	46	9	21	48	-13	221
	387	-362	19	11	9	8	53	20	8	22	-236	261	200		357	-322	19	11	9	8	54	20	8	22	-196	231	221
	-42	67	20	10	54	-9	33	12	7	23	49	-24	200		-32	67	20	10	55	-9	33	12	7	23	49	-14	221
	-43	68	-49	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-25	200		-33	68	-48	90	66	-1	-2	-3	24	25	50	-15	221
	-44	69	34	-8	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-26	200		-34	69	34	-7	-36	31	32	33	35	29	51	-16	221
	-57	-106	37	38	39	40	-180	41	42	43	44	219	200		-76	-86	37	38	39	40	-140	41	42	43	44	199	221
	131	84	-12	-13	-14	-15	205	-16	-17	-18	-96	-19	200		121	45	-2	-3	-4	-5	175	-6	-7	-8	-76	-9	221
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 90$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 150$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 91$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 151$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 221$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. To avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums (T, R) and (M,T) are **even** numbers for **first example** and **odd** numbers for **second example**. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 35 \times 140$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{8 \times 8} = 35 \times 140$$

Result 3.6. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with **reduced entries**:

$(R-2*S)/2-A38$	A40	$(R-2*S)/2-A31$	$(R-2*S)/2-A32$	$(R-2*S)/2-A33$	$(R-2*S)/2-A34$	$3*(2*S-R)/2+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37$	$(R-2*S)/2-A35$	$(R-2*S)/2-A36$	$(R-2*S)/2-A37$	$3*2*S-2*R+A30-A40+A38$	$(R-2*S)/2-A30$
A39	A38	A31	A32	A33	A34	$2*(R-2*S)-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37$	A35	A36	A37	A30	$2*2*S-R-A39-A38-A30$
$(R-2*S)/2-A41$	A41	$A2-A10+A6$	$A3+A5-A11-A13+A7+A9-A1$	$A4+A13+A1-A9+A8-A5-A12$	$S-A2+A10-A6-A3+A11-A7+A12-A4-A8$	A2	A3	A4	$S-A2-A3-A4$	A23	$(R-2*S)/2-A23$
$(R-2*S)/2-A42$	A42	A1	$S-A2+A10-A6-A3-A5+A11+A13-A7-A9$	$A2-A10+A6+A12-A4-A13+A9-A8+A5$	$A3-A11+A7-A12+A4-A1+A8$	A5	$S-A2-A3-A5$	$A2-A4+A5$	$A3+A4-A5$	A24	$(R-2*S)/2-A24$
$(R-2*S)/2-A43$	A43	$S/2+A12-A4-A13-A1+A9-A8+A5$	$A2-A10+A6+A3-A11+A7-A12+A4+A8-S/2$	$S/2-A2+A10-A6$	$S/2+A1-A3-A5+A11+A13-A7-A9$	$S/2-A4$	$A2+A3+A4-S/2$	$S/2-A2$	$S/2-A3$	A25	$(R-2*S)/2-A25$
$(R-2*S)/2-A44$	A44	$S/2-A2+A10-A6-A12+A4+A13-A9+A8-A5$	$S/2+A1-A3+A11-A7+A12-A4-A8$	$S/2-A1$	$A2-A10+A6+A3+A5-A11-A13+A7+A9-S/2$	$S/2-A2+A4-A5$	$S/2-A3-A4+A5$	$S/2-A5$	$A2+A3+A5-S/2$	A26	$(R-2*S)/2-A26$
$3*(2*S-R)/2+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47$	$2*(R-2*S)-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47$	A6	A7	A8	$S-A6-A7-A8$	A10	A11	A12	$S-A10-A11-A12$	$2*(R-2*S)-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29$	$3*(2*S-R)/2+A23+A24+A25+A26+A27+A28+A29$
$(R-2*S)/2-A45$	A45	A9	$S-A6-A7-A9$	$A6-A8+A9$	$A7+A8-A9$	A13	$S-A10-A11-A13$	$A10-A12+A13$	$A11+A12-A13$	A27	$(R-2*S)/2-A27$
$(R-2*S)/2-A46$	A46	$S/2-A8$	$A6+A7+A8-S/2$	$S/2-A6$	$S/2-A7$	$S/2-A12$	$A10+A11+A12-S/2$	$S/2-A10$	$S/2-A11$	A28	$(R-2*S)/2-A28$
$(R-2*S)/2-A47$	A47	$S/2-A6+A8-A9$	$S/2-A7-A8+A9$	$S/2-A9$	$A6+A7+A9-S/2$	$S/2-A10+A12-A13$	$S/2-A11-A12+A13$	$S/2-A13$	$A10+A11+A13-S/2$	A29	$(R-2*S)/2-A29$
$2*2*S-R-A30-A22-A39$	$R-2*S-A30-A38-A22$	A15	A16	A17	A18	$2*(R-2*S)-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19-A20-A21$	A19	A20	A21	A22	$2*S-R+2*A30+A38+A22+A39$
$(2*S-R)/2+A30+A38+A22$	$3*2*S-2*R+A30+A22-A40$	$(R-2*S)/2-A15$	$(R-2*S)/2-A16$	$(R-2*S)/2-A17$	$(R-2*S)/2-A18$	$3*(2*S-R)/2+A15+A16+A17+A18+A19+A20+A21$	$(R-2*S)/2-A19$	$(R-2*S)/2-A20$	$(R-2*S)/2-A21$	$R-2*S-2*A30+A40-A38-A22$	$(R-2*S)/2-A22$

Details:

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 12 embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8. The magic square of order 8 is composed with four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. The letters S, T and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 4, 8 and 12 respectively, where $T = 2 \times S$. In this case, the magic sum of order 12 is always an even number. To get magic sum as odd numbers, some of the entries may be decimal numbers. See the examples below.

Example 3.6. Let's consider following two examples:

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											210	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT											261
7	50	14	13	12	11	143	10	9	8	-82	15	210	32.5	50.0	39.5	38.5	37.5	36.5	66.5	35.5	34.5	33.5	-184.0	40.5	261
49	48	41	42	43	44	-88	45	46	47	40	-147	210	49.0	48	41	42	43	44	14	45	46	47	40	-198.0	261
4	51	8	9	10	23	12	13	14	11	33	22	210	29.5	51	8	9	10	23	12	13	14	11	33	47.5	261
3	52	11	22	9	8	15	10	13	12	34	21	210	28.5	52	11	22	9	8	15	10	13	12	34	46.5	261
2	53	15	2	17	16	11	14	13	12	35	20	210	27.5	53	15	2	17	16	11	14	13	12	35	45.5	261
1	54	16	17	14	3	12	13	10	15	36	19	210	26.5	54	16	17	14	3	12	13	10	15	36	44.5	261
213	-158	16	17	18	-1	20	21	22	-13	-32	87	210	136.5	-56	16	17	18	-1	20	21	22	-13	70	10.5	261
0	55	19	-2	17	16	23	-14	21	20	37	18	210	25.5	55	19	-2	17	16	23	-14	21	20	37	43.5	261
-1	56	7	26	9	8	3	38	5	4	38	17	210	24.5	56	7	26	9	8	3	38	5	4	38	42.5	261
-2	57	8	9	6	27	4	5	2	39	39	16	210	23.5	57	8	9	6	27	4	5	2	39	39	41.5	261
-131	-10	25	26	27	28	24	29	30	31	32	99	210	-182.0	41	25	26	27	28	126	29	30	31	32	48.0	261
65	-98	30	29	28	27	31	26	25	24	0	23	210	39.5	-200.0	55.5	54.5	53.5	52.5	-45.5	51.5	50.5	49.5	51.0	48.5	261
21a	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	21b	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261

The magic sums of above two magic squares are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 50$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 100$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 210$$

Second Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 50$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 100$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 261$$

The magic rectangles sum is given by

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 55 \times 220$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 80.5 \times 322$$

Remark 1. There are many entries with decimal numbers. It is due to the fact that the magic sum of order 8 is always an *even number* and the magic sum of order 12 is considered as *odd number*.

Result 3.7. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with *reduced entries*:

$(R-4^*m)/2-A36$	A38	$(R-4^*m)/2-A29$	$(R-4^*m)/2-A30$	$(R-4^*m)/2-A31$	$(R-4^*m)/2-A32$	$3*(4^*m-R)/2 + A29+A30+A31 + A32+A33+A34 + A35$	$(R-4^*m)/2-A33$	$(R-4^*m)/2-A34$	$(R-4^*m)/2-A35$	$3^*4^*m-2^*R+A28-A38+A36$	$(R-4^*m)/2-A28$
A37	A36	A29	A30	A31	A32	$2*(R-4^*m)-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35$	A33	A34	A35	A28	$8^*m-R-A37-A36-A28$
$(R-4^*m)/2-A39$	A39	$A1-A3-A5-A6-A8+A7$	$A6+A8-2^*m+A11+A1-A3-A5$	2^*m	$2^*m+2^*A3+2^*A5-A7-A11-2^*A1$	$A5+2^*A3-A7-A11+A10-A9$	$2^*m-A9-A5-A10$	$A9-2^*A3+A7+A11$	A9	A21	$(R-4^*m)/2-A21$
$(R-4^*m)/2-A40$	A40	$m+A3+A5+A6+A8-A7-A1$	$3^*m+A3+A5-A6-A8-A11-A1$	$(-m)$	$A7-m+A11+2^*A1-2^*A3-2^*A5$	$m+A9-A10+A11-A5-2^*A3+A7$	$A9+A5+A10-m$	$m-A9+2^*A3-A7-A11$	$m-A9$	A22	$(R-4^*m)/2-A22$
$(R-4^*m)/2-A41$	A41	$2^*A3+2^*A5-A7-A11-A1$	A1	$A6+A8+A11-A3-A5$	$2^*m+A7-A3-A5-A6-A8$	$A5+2^*A3-A7-A11$	A5	$2^*m+A7+A11-A10-2^*A3-2^*A5$	A10	A23	$(R-4^*m)/2-A23$
$(R-4^*m)/2-A42$	A42	$A1+m-2^*A3-2^*A5+A7+A11$	$m-A1$	$m+A3+A5-A6-A8-A11$	$A3+A5+A6+A8-A7-m$	$m+A7+A11-A5-2^*A3$	$m-A5$	$2^*A3+2^*A5-A7-A11+A10-m$	$m-A10$	A24	$(R-4^*m)/2-A24$
$3*(4^*m-R)/2 + A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45$	$2*(R-4^*m)-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45$	$A3+A2-A7-A11+A4$	$2^*m-A3-A2-A4$	$A7+A11-A3$	A3	$2^*m-A6-A8-A11$	$A6+A8-A7$	A7	A11	$2*(R-4^*m)-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27$	$3*(4^*m-R)/2 + A21+A22+A23+A24+A25+A26+A27$
$(R-4^*m)/2-A43$	A43	$m+A7+A11-A4-A3-A2$	$A3+A2+A4-m$	$m+A3-A7-A11$	$m-A3$	$A6+A8+A11-m$	$m+A7-A6-A8$	$m-A7$	$m-A11$	A25	$(R-4^*m)/2-A25$
$(R-4^*m)/2-A44$	A44	$A2+2^*A3-A7-A11$	A2	$2^*m+A7+A11-2^*A2-A4-2^*A3$	A4	$A6+A11-A7$	A6	A8	$2^*m+A7-2^*A6-A8-A11$	A26	$(R-4^*m)/2-A26$
$(R-4^*m)/2-A45$	A45	$m+A7+A11-A2-2^*A3$	$m-A2$	$2^*A3-A7-A11+2^*A2+A4-m$	$m-A4$	$m+A7-A11-A6$	$m-A6$	$m-A8$	$2^*A6+A8+A11-A7-m$	A27	$(R-4^*m)/2-A27$
$8^*m-R-A28-A20-A37$	$R-4^*m-A28-A36-A20$	A13	A14	A15	A16	$2*(R-4^*m)-A13-A14-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19$	A17	A18	A19	A20	$4^*m-R+2^*A28+A36+A20+A37$
$(4^*m-R)/2 + A28+A36+A20$	$3^*4^*m-2^*R+A28+A20-A38$	$(R-4^*m)/2-A13$	$(R-4^*m)/2-A14$	$(R-4^*m)/2-A15$	$(R-4^*m)/2-A16$	$3*(4^*m-R)/2 + A13+A14+A15+A16+A17+A18+A19$	$(R-4^*m)/2-A17$	$(R-4^*m)/2-A18$	$(R-4^*m)/2-A19$	$R-4^*m-2^*A28+A38-A36-A20$	$(R-4^*m)/2-A20$

Details:

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 12 embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square off order 8. The magic square of order 8 is composed with equal sum **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . The letters T and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 8 and 12 respectively. The letter m represents the width of each magic rectangle of order 2×4 . In this case where $T = 4m$. In this case, the magic sum of order 12 is always an even number. To get magic sum as odd numbers, some of the entries may be decimal numbers. See the examples below.

Example 3.7. Let's consider following two examples:

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												200	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												231
13	49	20	19	18	17	121	16	15	14	-123	21	200	18.5	49.0	25.5	24.5	23.5	22.5	104.5	21.5	20.5	19.5	-125.0	26.5	231		
48	47	40	41	42	43	-61	44	45	46	39	-174	200	48.0	47	40	41	42	43	-39	44	45	46	39	-165.0	231		
10	50	-34	-2	40	36	4	-14	31	19	32	28	200	15.5	50	-34	-12	50	46	4	-4	31	19	32	33.5	231		
9	51	54	22	-20	-16	16	34	-11	1	33	27	200	14.5	51	59	37	-25	-21	21	29	-6	6	33	32.5	231		
8	52	7	11	27	-5	3	15	2	20	34	26	200	13.5	52	7	11	27	5	3	15	12	20	34	31.5	231		
7	53	13	9	-7	25	17	5	18	0	35	25	200	12.5	53	18	14	-2	20	22	10	13	5	35	30.5	231		
191	-131	1	1	25	13	-15	17	17	21	-5	65	200	174.5	-109	1	11	25	13	-5	17	17	21	17	48.5	231		
6	54	19	19	-5	7	35	3	3	-1	36	24	200	11.5	54	24	14	0	12	30	8	8	4	36	29.5	231		
5	55	0	12	14	14	20	16	18	-14	37	23	200	10.5	55	0	12	24	14	20	16	18	-4	37	28.5	231		
4	56	20	8	6	6	0	4	2	34	38	22	200	9.5	56	25	13	1	11	5	9	7	29	38	27.5	231		
-158	3	24	25	26	27	51	28	29	30	31	84	200	-149.0	14	24	25	26	27	73	28	29	30	31	73.0	231		
57	-139	36	35	34	33	9	32	31	30	13	29	200	51.5	-141.0	41.5	40.5	39.5	38.5	-7.5	37.5	36.5	35.5	24.0	34.5	231		
22a	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	22b	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231		

The magic sums of above two magic squares are as follows:

First Example

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 80$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 200$$

Second Example

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 100$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 231$$

The magic rectangles sum is given by

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 20 \times 40$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 60 \times 240$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 25 \times 50$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 65.5 \times 262$$

Remark 2. There are many entries with decimal numbers. It is due to the fact that the magic sum of order 8 is always an *even number* and the magic sum of order 12 is considered as *odd number*.

3.3 Cornered Magic Squares

Below are few examples of reduced entries **cornered algebraic** magic squares of order 12.

Result 3.8. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with *reduced entries*:

A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	S-M-A10	A10	a18	T-S-A18	L-T-A30	A30	A46	R-L-A46
A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	S-M-A11	A11	a19	T-S-A19	L-T-A31	A31	A47	R-L-A47
A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	M-S+A10+A11+A12	2*(S-M)-A10-A11-A12	A20	T-S-A20	L-T-A32	A32	A48	R-L-A48
M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6	A2	S-M-A12	A12	3*(T-S)-A18-A19-A20-A21-A22	2*(S-T)+A18+A19+A20+A21+A22	L-T-A33	A33	A49	R-L-A49
2*S-3*M+A1-A8+3*A4-A11+A10	S-M-A8	3*M-2*S-A1+2*A8-3*A4+A11-A10+A9	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	(5*M-3*S)/2	A21	T-S-A21	3*(T-L)+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36	4*(L-T)-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36	5*(R-L)-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54	4*(L-R)+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54
2*M-S-A1+A8-3*A4+A11-A10	A8	3*S-4*M+A1-2*A8+3*A4-A11+A10-A9	A9	(5*M-3*S)/2	(S-M)/2	A22	T-S-A22	L-T-A34	A34	A50	R-L-A50
A14	2*A11-T-5*S-A1+2*A9+2*A8+2*A12+A14-3*A4+A18-A19+8*M	A15	4*T+2*S-2*A14+A1-2*A11-2*A9-2*A8-2*A12+3*A4-A18+A19-8*M-A15-A16-A17	A16	A17	(T-S)/2	(7*S-5*T)/2	L-T-A35	A35	A51	R-L-A51
T-S-A14	2*T+4*S+A1-2*A11-2*A9-2*A8-2*A12-A14+3*A4-A18+A19-8*M	T-S-A15	2*A14-3*S-3*T-A1+2*A11+2*A9+2*A8+2*A12-3*A4+A18-A19+8*M+A15+A16+A17	T-S-A16	T-S-A17	(7*S-5*T)/2	(T-S)/2	L-T-A36	A36	A52	R-L-A52
2*L+6*T-6*S-2*A20-A16-2*A15-2*A11-2*A9-A17-2*A8-A22-2*A12-A21-2*A14+3*A4-2*A18+A1-A24+A30-A31-3*M	L-T-A24	L-T-A25	L-T-A26	L-T-A27	6*S-4*L-4*T+2*A20+A29+A27+A16+2*A15+2*A11+2*A9+A17+2*A8+A25+A28+A22+A26-A1+2*A12+A21+2*A14-3*A4+2*A18+2*A24-A30+A31+3*M	L-T-A28	L-T-A29	(L-T)/2	(9*T-7*L)/2	A53	R-L-A53
6*S-L-7*T+2*A20+A16+2*A15+2*A11+2*A9+A17+2*A8+A22+2*A12+A21+2*A14-3*A4+2*A18-A1+A24-A30+A31+3*M	A24	A25	A26	A27	5*L+3*T-6*S-2*A20-A29-A27-A16-2*A15-2*A11-2*A9-A17-2*A8-A25-A28-A22-A26+A1-2*A12-A21-2*A14+3*A4-2*A18-2*A24+A30-A31-3*M	A28	A29	(9*T-7*L)/2	(L-T)/2	A54	R-L-A54
A38	A38-R-A25+A26+2*S+A16-A17-A22+A21+A33-A32-A47+A46	A39	A40	6*R-5*L-2*A38+A25-A26-2*S-A16+A17+A22-A21-A33+A32+A47-A46-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	(R-L)/2	(11*L-9*R)/2
R-L-A38	2*R-L-A38+A25-A26-2*S-A16+A17+A22-A21-A33+A32+A47-A46	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	4*L-5*R+2*A38-A25+A26+2*S+A16-A17-A22+A21+A33-A32-A47+A46+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	(11*L-9*R)/2	(R-L)/2

Details:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 12, where the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 are in the left upper corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 , 2×6 , 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal width and length for each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums S, T, L and R should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Example 3.8. Let's consider following two examples:

2	mgc												200	2	mgc												221
	21	47	-21	23	0	30	38	-18	-20	50	66	-16	200		21	48	-21	23	0	30	38	-18	-30	50	66	14	221
	26	24	25	-5	-1	31	39	-19	-21	51	67	-17	200		26	24	25	-4	-1	31	39	-19	-31	51	67	13	221
	19	18	3	30	63	-33	40	-20	-22	52	68	-18	200		19	18	4	30	63	-33	40	-20	-32	52	68	12	221
	4	-19	63	22	-2	32	-140	160	-23	53	69	-19	200		5	-19	63	22	-2	32	-140	160	-33	53	69	11	221
	54	2	3	1	15	25	41	-21	281	-251	-380	430	200		53	2	4	1	15	26	41	-21	311	-291	-230	310	221
	-24	28	27	29	25	15	42	-22	-24	54	70	-20	200		-23	28	26	29	26	15	42	-22	-34	54	70	10	221
	34	120	35	-202	36	37	10	50	-25	55	71	-21	200		34	122	35	-204	36	37	10	51	-35	55	71	9	221
	-14	-100	-15	222	-16	-17	50	10	-26	56	72	-22	200		-14	-102	-15	224	-16	-17	51	10	-36	56	72	8	221
	-432	-14	-15	-16	-17	651	-18	-19	15	15	73	-23	200		-453	-24	-25	-26	-27	692	-28	-29	10	51	73	7	221
	462	44	45	46	47	-621	48	49	15	15	74	-24	200		473	44	45	46	47	-672	48	49	51	10	74	6	221
	58	57	59	60	-299	61	62	63	64	65	25	-75	200		58	38	59	60	-130	61	62	63	64	65	40	-219	221
	-8	-7	-9	-10	349	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-75	25	200		22	42	21	20	210	19	18	17	16	15	-219	40	221
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 70$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 100$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 120$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 150$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 71$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 101$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 121$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 141$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 221$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. To avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums (T, R) and (M,T) are **even** numbers for **first example** and **odd** numbers for **second example**. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 20 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 30 \times 120$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 50 \times 250$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 20 \times 60$$

$$MR_{8 \times 8} = 20 \times 80$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 80 \times 400$$

Result 3.9. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

$A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}-A_4-A_7-A_{11}-A_{15}$	A4	A7	A11	A15	$S-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}$	T-S-A29	A29	L-T-A41	A41	A57	R-L-A57
$S-A_{12}-A_5-A_8-A_{16}-A_{19}$	A5	A8	A12	A16	A19	T-S-A30	A30	L-T-A42	A42	A58	R-L-A58
$A_4+A_7+A_{11}+A_{15}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{12}-A_2-A_3+A_5+A_8+A_{12}+A_{16}$	$S-A_4-A_5-A_{12}+A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}-A_{17}-A_7-A_8-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{13}-A_9-A_{11}+A_1+A_2+A_3$	A9	A13	A17	A20	T-S-A31	A31	L-T-A43	A43	A59	R-L-A59
A1	$S+A_{16}+A_{13}+A_6-A_{19}+A_3-A_{11}-A_{18}-A_{14}-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{20}$	$A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}+A_{20}-A_{16}-A_{13}-A_6+A_{19}-A_3$	A14	A18	A21	T-S-A32	A32	L-T-A44	A44	A60	R-L-A60
A2	A6	$S+A_{16}+A_{13}-A_9+A_6-A_{19}+A_3-A_{10}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{20}-A_7-A_8$	$A_5+A_{14}+A_{10}+2*A_{21}+A_{22}+3*A_{23}+2*A_{20}-A_4+A_8-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{13}+2*A_9-2*A_6+2*A_{19}-A_{11}-A_2-A_3-S$	$S-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-2*A_{23}+A_4+A_7+A_{11}+A_{15}-A_5-A_9-A_{14}$	A22	T-S-A33	A33	L-T-A45	A45	A61	R-L-A61
A3	$A_{12}+A_{18}+A_{14}+A_{21}+A_{20}+A_{17}+A_7+A_8+A_{15}+A_9-2*A_6+A_{19}+A_{11}-A_2-2*A_3-S$	A10	$2*S+A_4-A_8+A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_9+2*A_6-2*A_{19}+A_2+A_3-A_{12}-A_5-2*A_{14}-A_{10}-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-3*A_{23}-2*A_{20}$	$A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{21}+A_{22}+2*A_{23}-A_4-A_7-A_{11}+A_5+A_9+A_{14}-2*A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}-A_{18}$	A23	$2*S-2*T+A_{29}+A_{30}+A_{31}+A_{32}+A_{33}$	$3*T-3*S-A_{29}-A_{30}-A_{31}-A_{32}-A_{33}$	L-T-A46	A46	A62	R-L-A62
T-S-A25	$A_{30}-A_{29}-2*A_9+A_{13}-A_{25}+2*S-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-3*A_{23}-A_{18}-2*A_{19}-3*A_{20}-A_{14}+A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_{10}+A_2+A_4+A_{11}-A_5+2*A_6-A_8+A_3$	T-S-A26	T-S-A27	T-S-A28	$2*A_{25}+A_{28}+A_{27}+A_{26}-A_{30}+A_{29}+2*A_9-A_{13}-T-S+2*A_{21}+A_{22}+3*A_{23}+A_{18}+2*A_{19}+3*A_{20}+A_{14}-A_{15}-A_{16}+2*A_{10}-A_2-A_4-A_{11}+A_5-2*A_6+A_8-A_3$	(T-S)/2	$(7*S-5*T)/2$	L-T-A47	A47	A63	R-L-A63
A25	$A_{29}-A_{30}+2*A_9-A_{13}+T+A_{25}-A_{11}-3*S+2*A_{21}+A_{22}+3*A_{23}+A_{18}+2*A_{19}+3*A_{20}+A_{14}-A_{15}-A_{16}+2*A_{10}-A_2-A_4+A_5-2*A_6+A_8-A_3$	A26	A27	A28	$A_{30}-A_{29}-A_{28}-A_{27}-A_{26}-2*A_9+A_{13}+2*T-2*A_{25}-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-3*A_{23}-A_{18}-2*A_{19}-3*A_{20}-A_{14}+A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_{10}+A_2+A_4+A_{11}-A_5+2*A_6-A_8+A_3$	$(7*S-5*T)/2$	$(T-S)/2$	$3*T-3*L+A_{41}+A_{42}+A_4+3+A_{44}+A_{45}+A_{46}+A_{47}$	$4*L-4*T-A_{41}-A_{42}-A_{43}-A_{44}-A_{45}-A_{46}-A_{47}$	A64	R-L-A64
L-T-A35	$A_{32}+T-A_{31}+2*S-A_{21}-2*A_{22}-2*A_{23}-A_{26}+A_{18}-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{14}+2*A_{15}+A_{16}+A_{17}-A_{41}+A_4+A_{42}-A_{35}+A_{27}+A_{11}+A_7-A_5-A_9-2*T$	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	$A_9+2*T-A_{32}+T+A_{36}+A_{31}-2*S+A_{21}+2*A_{22}+2*A_{23}+A_{26}-A_{18}+A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{14}-2*A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}+A_{38}+A_{39}+A_{40}+A_{37}+A_{41}-A_{44}-A_{42}+2*A_{35}-2*L-A_{27}-A_{11}-A_7+A_5$	(L-T)/2	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	A65	R-L-A65
A35	$A_9+2*T-A_{32}-2*T+A_{31}-2*S+A_{21}+2*A_{22}+2*A_{23}+A_{26}-A_{18}+A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{14}-2*A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}+A_{41}-A_4-A_{42}+A_{35}+L-A_{27}-A_{11}-A_7+A_5$	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	$A_{32}-2*T-A_{36}-A_{31}+2*S-A_{21}-2*A_{22}-2*A_{23}-A_{26}+A_{18}-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{14}+2*A_{15}+A_{16}+A_{17}-A_{38}-A_{39}-A_{40}-A_{37}-A_{41}+A_4+A_{42}-2*A_{35}+3*L+A_{27}+A_{11}+A_7-A_5-A_9-2*T$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	(L-T)/2	$5*(R-L)-A_{57}-A_{58}-A_{59}-A_{60}-A_{61}-A_{62}-A_{63}-A_{64}-A_{65}$	$4*(L-R)+A_{57}+A_{58}+A_{59}+A_{60}+A_{61}+A_{62}+A_{63}+A_{64}+A_{65}$
$A_{49}-A_{37}+A_{36}-2*A_6+A_8-A_3-A_2-A_4-A_{11}+A_5-A_{15}-A_{16}+2*A_{10}+2*A_{19}+3*A_{20}+A_{14}+A_{22}+3*A_{23}+A_{18}+2*A_{21}+2*A_9-A_{13}+2*A_{28}+A_{27}+A_{26}+A_{32}+2*A_{25}+2*A_{29}+A_{31}+2*A_{33}+S-5*T-A_{44}+A_{58}+A_{43}+R-A_{57}$	A49	A50	A51	A52	A53	A54	A55	A56	$A_{37}-A_{36}+2*A_6-A_8+A_3+A_2+A_4+A_{11}-A_5+A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_{10}-2*A_{19}-3*A_{20}-A_{14}-A_{22}-3*A_{23}-A_{18}-2*A_{21}-2*A_9+A_{13}-2*A_{28}-A_{27}-A_{26}-A_{32}-2*A_{25}-2*A_{29}-A_{31}-2*A_{33}-S+5*T+A_{44}-A_{58}-A_{43}+4*R+A_{57}-A_{56}-A_{53}-A_{54}-A_{55}-A_{50}-A_{51}-A_{52}-5*L-2*A_{49}$	(R-L)/2	$(11*L-9*R)/2$
$A_{37}-A_{36}+2*A_6-A_8+A_3+A_2+A_4+A_{11}-A_5+A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_{10}-2*A_{19}-3*A_{20}-A_{14}-A_{22}-3*A_{23}-A_{18}-2*A_{21}-2*A_9+A_{13}-2*A_{28}-A_{27}-A_{26}-A_{32}-2*A_{25}-2*A_{29}-A_{31}-2*A_{33}-S+5*T+A_{44}-A_{58}-A_{43}+A_{57}-L-A_{49}$	R-L-A49	R-L-A50	R-L-A51	R-L-A52	R-L-A53	R-L-A54	R-L-A55	R-L-A56	$A_{56}+A_{53}+A_{54}+A_{55}+A_{50}+A_{51}+A_{52}+4*L+2*A_{49}-A_{37}+A_{36}-2*A_6+A_8-A_3-A_2-A_4-A_{11}+A_5-A_{15}-A_{16}+2*A_{10}+2*A_{19}+3*A_{20}+A_{14}+A_{22}+3*A_{23}+A_{18}+2*A_{21}+2*A_9-A_{13}+2*A_{28}+A_{27}+A_{26}+A_{32}+2*A_{25}+2*A_{29}+A_{31}+2*A_{33}+S-5*T-A_{44}+A_{58}+A_{43}-3*R-A_{57}$	$(11*L-9*R)/2$	(R-L)/2

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with magic square of order 6 at the upper-left corner. The blocks of orders 8 and 10 is also **cornered** magic squares of orders 8 and 10. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 , 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums in pairs (S,T), (T, L) and (L, R) should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd**. See below two examples.

Example 3.9. Let's consider following two examples:

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											260
78	14	17	21	25	-75	51	39	-21	51	67	-7	260
-30	15	18	22	26	29	50	40	-22	52	68	-8	260
-4	-15	19	23	27	30	49	41	-23	53	69	-9	260
11	-91	77	24	28	31	48	42	-24	54	70	-10	260
12	16	-71	180	-89	32	47	43	-25	55	71	-11	260
13	141	20	-190	63	33	25	65	-26	56	72	-12	260
55	-212	54	53	52	268	45	-145	-27	57	73	-13	260
35	302	36	37	38	-178	-145	45	288	-258	74	-14	260
-15	-147	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	372	15	65	75	-15	260
45	177	46	47	48	49	50	-342	65	15	-339	399	260
352	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	-552	30	-70	260
-292	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	612	-70	30	260
19a	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT											275
78	14	17	21	25	-70	51	39	-21	51	67	3	275
-25	15	18	22	26	29	50	40	-22	52	68	2	275
-4	-10	19	23	27	30	49	41	-23	53	69	1	275
11	-86	77	24	28	31	48	42	-24	54	70	0	275
12	16	-66	175	-84	32	47	43	-25	55	71	-1	275
13	136	20	-180	63	33	25	65	-26	56	72	-2	275
55	-202	54	53	52	258	45	-140	-27	57	73	-3	275
35	292	36	37	38	-168	-140	45	288	-258	74	-4	275
-15	-142	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	367	15	70	75	-5	275
45	172	46	47	48	49	50	-337	70	15	-289	359	275
347	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	-497	35	-110	275
-277	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	567	-110	35	275
19b	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275

The magic sums of above two magic squares are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 80$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 170$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 200$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 260$$

Second Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 85$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 175$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 205$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 275$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. To avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums, the pairs (S,T), (T, L) and (L, R) are considered as **even** numbers for **first example** and **odd** numbers for **second example**. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 90 \times 270$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 30 \times 120$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 60 \times 300$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 90 \times 270$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 30 \times 120$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 70 \times 350.$$

Result 3.10. *Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:*

$2^*M/3-A6$	$A6+A7-M/3$	$2^*M/3-A7$	$2^*M/3-A2$	$A2+A3-M/3$	$2^*M/3-A3$	$T-2^*M-A15$	$A15$	$L-T-A27$	$A27$	$A43$	$R-L-A43$
$A6+A8-M/3$	$M+A1-A6-A7-A8$	$M/3+A7-A1$	$A2+A4-M/3$	$5^*M/3-A3-A2-A4-A5$	$A3+A5-M/3$	$T-2^*M-A16$	$A16$	$L-T-A28$	$A28$	$A44$	$R-L-A44$
$2^*M/3-A8$	$M/3+A8-A1$	$A1$	$2^*M/3-A4$	$A4+A5-M/3$	$2^*M/3-A5$	$T-2^*M-A17$	$A17$	$L-T-A29$	$A29$	$A45$	$R-L-A45$
$A2$	$M-A2-A3$	$A3$	$A6$	$M-A6-A7$	$A7$	$T-2^*M-A18$	$A18$	$L-T-A30$	$A30$	$A46$	$R-L-A46$
$M-A2-A4$	$A2+A3+A4+A5-M$	$M-A3-A5$	$M-A6-A8$	$A6+A7+A8-A1-M/3$	$M/3-A7+A1$	$T-2^*M-A19$	$A19$	$L-T-A31$	$A31$	$A47$	$R-L-A47$
$A4$	$M-A4-A5$	$A5$	$A8$	$M/3-A8+A1$	$2^*M/3-A1$	$4^*M-2^*T+A15+A16+A17+A18+A19$	$3^*T-6^*M-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19$	$L-T-A32$	$A32$	$A48$	$R-L-A48$
$2^*T-10^*M/3-A10+A15-A16-2^*A6-A7-A8$	$T-2^*M-A10$	$T-2^*M-A11$	$T-2^*M-A12$	$T-2^*M-A13$	$16^*M/3-3^*T+2^*A10-A15+A16+2^*A6+A7+A8+A11+A12+A13$	$(T-2^*M)/2$	$(14^*M-5^*T)/2$	$L-T-A33$	$A33$	$A49$	$R-L-A49$
$A10-A15-T+4^*M/3+A16+2^*A6+A7+A8$	$A10$	$A11$	$A12$	$A13$	$4^*T-22^*M/3-2^*A10+A15-A16-2^*A6-A7-A8-A11-A12-A13$	$(14^*M-5^*T)/2$	$(T-2^*M)/2$	$3^*(T-L)+A27+A28+A29+A30+A31+A32+A33$	$4^*(L-T)-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33$	$A50$	$R-L-A50$
$2^*L-T+A27-A28+A17-(10/3)^*M-A18-A7+2^*A1-A8-A12-A21+A11$	$L-T-A21$	$L-T-A22$	$L-T-A23$	$L-T-A24$	$L-T-A25$	$L-T-A26$	$3^*T-4^*L-A27+A28-A17+(10/3)^*M+A18+A7-2^*A1+A8+A12+2^*A21-A11+A22+A23+A24+A25+A26$	$(L-T)/2$	$(9^*T-7^*L)/2$	$A51$	$R-L-A51$
$A28-A17+(10/3)^*M+A18+A7-2^*A1+A8+A12+A21-A11-A27-L$	$A21$	$A22$	$A23$	$A24$	$A25$	$A26$	$5^*L-4^*T+A27-A28+A17-(10/3)^*M-A18-A7+2^*A1-A8-A12-2^*A21+A11-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	$(9^*T-7^*L)/2$	$(L-T)/2$	$5^*(R-L)-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51$	$4^*(L-R)+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51$
$A11+R-7^*T+A8+2^*A6+A7+(28/3)^*M+A17+A35+2^*A16+A12+2^*A13+A22-A23+A29-A30+2^*A10+2^*A19+A18+A44-A43$	$A35$	$A36$	$A37$	$A38$	$A39$	$A40$	$A41$	$A42$	$4^*R+7^*T-A8-2^*A6-A7-(28/3)^*M-A17-A11-A42-A41-A40-A39-A38-A37-A36-2^*A35-2^*A16-A12-2^*A13-A22+A23-A29+A30-2^*A10-2^*A19-A18-A44+A43-5^*L$	$(R-L)/2$	$(11^*L-9^*R)/2$
$A43-L-A11+7^*T-A8-2^*A6-A7-(28/3)^*M-A17-A35-2^*A16-A12-2^*A13-A22+A23-A29+A30-2^*A10-2^*A19-A18-A44$	$R-L-A35$	$R-L-A36$	$R-L-A37$	$R-L-A38$	$R-L-A39$	$R-L-A40$	$R-L-A41$	$R-L-A42$	$A8+2^*A6+A7+(28/3)^*M+A17+A11+A42+A41+A40+A39+A38+A37+A36+2^*A35+2^*A16+A12+2^*A13+A22-A23+A29-A30+2^*A10+2^*A19+A18+A44-A43+4^*L-3^*R-7^*T$	$(11^*L-9^*R)/2$	$(R-L)/2$

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with magic square of order 6 at the upper-left corner. This magic square of order 6 is composed of four equal sums magic squares of order 3. The blocks of orders 8 and 10 are also **cornered** magic squares. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 , 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums in pairs (S,T), (T, L) and (L, R) should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd**. See below two examples.

Example 3.10. Let's consider following two examples:

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												300	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												321
44	3	43	48	-5	47	5	25	3	37	53	-3	300	33	17	31	41	1	39	10	39	-19	63	95	-29	321		
4	50	36	-4	96	-2	4	26	2	38	54	-4	300	19	23	39	3	71	7	8	41	-21	65	97	-31	321		
42	37	11	46	-1	45	3	27	1	39	55	-5	300	29	41	11	37	9	35	6	43	-23	67	99	-33	321		
12	65	13	16	57	17	2	28	0	40	56	-6	300	13	53	15	21	37	23	4	45	-25	69	101	-35	321		
64	-36	62	56	10	24	1	29	-1	41	57	-7	300	51	-17	47	35	31	15	2	47	-27	71	103	-37	321		
14	61	15	18	23	49	75	-45	-2	42	58	-8	300	17	45	19	25	13	43	117	-68	-29	73	105	-39	321		
32	10	9	8	7	24	15	105	-3	43	59	-9	300	31	20	18	16	14	48	24.5	39.5	-31	75	107	-41	321		
-2	20	21	22	23	6	105	15	160	-120	60	-10	300	18	29	31	33	35	1	39.5	24.5	351	-307	109	-43	321		
-57	9	8	7	6	5	4	178	20	70	61	-11	300	-54	-7	-9	-11	-13	-15	-17	302	22	57	111	-45	321		
97	31	32	33	34	35	36	-138	70	20	-263	313	300	98	51	53	55	57	59	61	-258	57	22	-597	663	321		
75	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	-213	25	25	300	223	79	81	83	85	87	89	91	93	-581	33	-42	321		
-25	5	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	263	25	25	300	-157	-13	-15	-17	-19	-21	-23	-25	-27	647	-42	33	321		
28a	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	28b	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321			

The magic sums of above two magic squares are as follows:

First Example

$M_{3 \times 3} = 90$
 $S_{6 \times 6} = 180$
 $T_{8 \times 8} = 210$
 $L_{10 \times 10} = 250$
 $R_{12 \times 12} = 300$

Second Example

$S_{3 \times 3} = 81$
 $S_{6 \times 6} = 162$
 $T_{8 \times 8} = 211$
 $L_{10 \times 10} = 255$
 $R_{12 \times 12} = 3215$

The magic rectangles sums are given by

First Example

$MR_{2 \times 6} = 30 \times 90$
 $MR_{2 \times 8} = 40 \times 160$
 $MR_{2 \times 10} = 50 \times 250$

Second Example

$MR_{2 \times 6} = 49 \times 147$
 $MR_{2 \times 8} = 44 \times 176$
 $MR_{2 \times 10} = 66 \times 330$

Remark 3. There are four entries with decimal numbers. It is due to the fact that the magic sum of orders 6 is and 8 are different, i.e., the pair (162, 211) is neither even or odd.

Result 3.11. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

$2^*M-2^*A4-2^*A7-A12+A3+A6$	$3^*A4+3^*A7-A15-A2+A12-A3-A6-2^*M$	$A2+A14-A16-4^*A4-4^*A7+A3+A6-A1+4^*M+A15$	$A16+3^*A4-3^*M+3^*A7-A3-A6+A1-A14$	A3	$2^*M-A9-A4-A7-A5-A3$	$A5+A8-A16+A3+A6-A1+A9$	$A16+A4+A7-A3-A6+A1-A8-M$	L-2*M-A25	A25	A41	R-L-A41
A2	$A4+A7-A15-M$	A1	$2^*M-A4-A7+A15-A1-A2$	A5	$M-A9-A4-A7$	$A16+2^*A4-2^*M+2^*A7+A1-A10$	$A9-A4-A7+2^*M-A16-A1+A10-A5$	L-2*M-A26	A26	A42	R-L-A42
$2^*A4+2^*A7-A13-M-A14+A16-A3-A6+A1-A2$	$4^*M-3^*A4-3^*A7-A12+A3+A6-A13-A1$	$2^*A4+2^*A7+A12-A3-A6+A13+A15-2^*M$	$A2+A13+A14-A16-A4-A7+A3+A6-A15$	$2^*A4-M-A8+A16+A7-A3-A6+A1-A5$	$A3-A4+2^*M-A16-2^*A7-A1+A10$	$A9+A7-A3$	$A8+A3+A6-A10+A5-A9-A4$	L-2*M-A27	A27	A43	R-L-A43
$A12+A13+A14-A16-A1$	$A1-A4-A7+A13+2^*A15+A2$	$2^*A4+2^*A7-A12-A13-A14-M+A16-2^*A15-A2$	$2^*M-A4-A7-A13$	$2^*M-2^*A4+A8-A16-A7+A6-A1$	$A16+3^*A4-4^*M+4^*A7+A1+2^*A9+A5-A10$	$3^*M-A8-3^*A7-A6-2^*A9+A10-A5-2^*A4$	A4	L-2*M-A28	A28	A44	R-L-A44
A6	$A9+M-A11-A6$	$A11-A8-A9$	A8	A12	$A15+M-A17-A12$	$A17-A14-A15$	A14	L-2*M-A29	A29	A45	R-L-A45
A11	A9	A10	$M-A9-A10-A11$	A17	A15	A16	$M-A15-A16-A17$	L-2*M-A30	A30	A46	R-L-A46
$A7+A8-A11$	$A6+A7-A10$	$M-A6-A7-A9$	$A9+A10+A11-A7-A8$	$A13+A14-A17$	$A12+A13-A16$	$M-A12-A13-A15$	$A15+A16+A17-A13-A14$	L-2*M-A31	A31	A47	R-L-A47
$M-A6-A7-A8$	$A10-A7-2^*A9+A11$	$A6+A7+A8+2^*A9-A10-A11$	A7	$M-A12-A13-A14$	$A16-A13-2^*A15+A17$	$A12+A13+A14+2^*A15-A16-A17$	A13	$6^*M-3^*L+A25+A26+A27+A28+A29+A30+A31$	$4^*L-8^*M-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31$	A48	R-L-A48
L-2*M-A19	$3^*A4+A26-A19+A12+3^*A7-A6-A3-2^*M-A15-A25$	L-2*M-A20	L-2*M-A21	L-2*M-A22	L-2*M-A23	L-2*M-A24	$6^*M-2^*L+2^*A19+A15+A25-3^*A4-A26-A12-3^*A7+A6+A3+A20+A21+A22+A23+A24$	$(L-2^*M)/2$	$(9^*2^*M-7^*L)/2$	A49	R-L-A49
A19	$A15+A25-3^*A4-A26+A19+L-A12-3^*A7+A6+A3$	A20	A21	A22	A23	A24	$3^*L-8^*M-2^*A19-A15-A25+3^*A4+A26+A12+3^*A7-A6-A3-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24$	$(9^*2^*M-7^*L)/2$	$(L-2^*M)/2$	$5^*(R-L)-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49$	$4^*(L-R)+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49$
A33	$3^*M-R+A21+A28-A27-A20+A33+A41-A42$	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	$6^*R-5^*L-3^*M-2^*A33-A41+A42-A21-A28+A27+A20-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	$(R-L)/2$	$(11^*L-9^*R)/2$
R-L-A33	$2^*R-L-A21-A28+A27-3^*M+A20-A33-A41+A42$	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	$4^*L-5^*R+3^*M+2^*A33+A41-A42+A21+A28-A27-A20+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40$	$(11^*L-9^*R)/2$	$(R-L)/2$

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 at the upper-left corner containing four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4. The block of order 10 is also a **cornered** magic square of order 10. The magic rectangles of orders 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 4, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums in pairs (L, R) and (T, L) should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd**.

Example 3.11. Let's consider following two examples:

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												200	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												221
5	-11	49	-13	13	-18	44	-9	25	35	51	29	200	9	-15	57	-19	13	-14	44	-11	23	35	51	48	221		
12	-24	11	31	15	-20	19	16	24	36	52	28	200	12	-26	11	35	15	-18	15	20	22	36	52	47	221		
-19	0	43	6	-10	8	23	9	23	37	53	27	200	-21	8	39	6	-12	12	23	9	21	37	53	46	221		
32	65	-73	6	12	60	-56	14	22	38	54	26	200	32	65	-75	10	16	52	-50	14	20	38	54	45	221		
16	12	-16	18	22	6	-22	24	21	39	55	25	200	16	14	-16	18	22	8	-22	24	19	39	55	44	221		
21	19	20	-30	27	25	26	-48	20	40	56	24	200	21	19	20	-28	27	25	26	-46	18	40	56	43	221		
14	13	-22	25	20	19	-40	31	19	41	57	23	200	14	13	-20	25	20	19	-38	31	17	41	57	42	221		
-21	-14	48	17	-39	-20	66	23	86	-26	58	22	200	-19	-14	48	17	-37	-20	66	23	92	-34	58	41	221		
31	-27	30	29	28	27	26	96	30	-150	59	21	200	29	-31	28	27	26	25	24	104	29	-139	59	40	221		
29	87	30	31	32	33	34	-36	-150	30	-95	175	200	29	89	30	31	32	33	34	-46	-139	29	0	99	221		
43	-66	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	94	40	-240	200	43	-81	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	204	49.5	-323.5	221		
37	146	36	35	34	33	32	31	30	-14	-240	40	200	56	180	55	54	53	52	51	50	49	-105	-323.5	49.5	221		
17a	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	17b	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 30$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 120$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 32$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 122$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 221$$

Remark 4. The magic sum of order 8 is always even numbers as it is sum of four equal sums magic squares of order 4. In this case to get odd number magic sum of order 12, we wrote the pair (L,R)=(122,221). This gives us few decimal entries.

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 60 \times 240$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 80 \times 400$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 58 \times 232$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 99 \times 495$$

Result 3.12. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

$A1-A3-A5-A6-A8+A7$	$A6+A8-2*m+A11+A1-A3-A5$	$2*m$	$2*m+2*A3+2*A5-A7-A11-2*A1$	$A5+2*A3-A7-A11+A10-A9$	$2*m-A9-A5-A10$	$A9-2*A3+A7+A11$	$A9$	$L-4*m-A19$	$A19$	$A35$	$R-L-A35$
$m+A3+A5+A6+A8-A7-A1$	$3*m+A3+A5-A6-A8-A11-A1$	$(-m)$	$A7-m+A11+2*A1-2*A3-2*A5$	$m+A9-A10+A11-A5-2*A3+A7$	$A9+A5+A10-m$	$m-A9+2*A3-A7-A11$	$m-A9$	$L-4*m-A20$	$A20$	$A36$	$R-L-A36$
$2*A3+2*A5-A7-A11-A1$	$A1$	$A6+A8+A11-A3-A5$	$2*m+A7-A3-A5-A6-A8$	$A5+2*A3-A7-A11$	$A5$	$2*m+A7+A11-A10-2*A3-2*A5$	$A10$	$L-4*m-A21$	$A21$	$A37$	$R-L-A37$
$A1+m-2*A3-2*A5+A7+A11$	$m-A1$	$m+A3+A5-A6-A8-A11$	$A3+A5+A6+A8-A7-m$	$m+A7+A11-A5-2*A3$	$m-A5$	$2*A3+2*A5-A7-A11+A10-m$	$m-A10$	$L-4*m-A22$	$A22$	$A38$	$R-L-A38$
$A3+A2-A7-A11+A4$	$2*m-A3-A2-A4$	$A7+A11-A3$	$A3$	$2*m-A6-A8-A11$	$A6+A8-A7$	$A7$	$A11$	$L-4*m-A23$	$A23$	$A39$	$R-L-A39$
$m+A7+A11-A4-A3-A2$	$A3+A2+A4-m$	$m+A3-A7-A11$	$m-A3$	$A6+A8+A11-m$	$m+A7-A6-A8$	$m-A7$	$m-A11$	$L-4*m-A24$	$A24$	$A40$	$R-L-A40$
$A2+2*A3-A7-A11$	$A2$	$2*m+A7+A11-2*A2-A4-2*A3$	$A4$	$A6+A11-A7$	$A6$	$A8$	$2*m+A7-2*A6-A8-A11$	$L-4*m-A25$	$A25$	$A41$	$R-L-A41$
$m+A7+A11-A2-2*A3$	$m-A2$	$2*A3-A7-A11+2*A2+A4-m$	$m-A4$	$m+A7-A11-A6$	$m-A6$	$m-A8$	$2*A6+A8+A11-A7-m$	$12*m-3*L+A19+A20+A21+A22+A23+A24+A25$	$4*L-16*m-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25$	$A42$	$R-L-A42$
$L-4*m-A13$	$7*m-A19+A11-A13+A20-2*A4-2*A6-2*A8+3*A7-4*A3-2*A5-2*A10-2*A2$	$L-4*m-A14$	$L-4*m-A15$	$L-4*m-A16$	$L-4*m-A17$	$L-4*m-A18$	$m-2*L+2*A13+A19-A11-A20+2*A4+2*A6+2*A8-3*A7+4*A3+2*A5+2*A10+2*A2+A14+A15+A16+A17+A18$	$(L-4*m)/2$	$(9*4*m-7*L)/2$	$A43$	$R-L-A43$
$A13$	$A19-A11+A13-A20+2*A4+2*A6+2*A8-3*A7+4*A3+2*A5+2*A10+2*A2-11*m+L$	$A14$	$A15$	$A16$	$A17$	$A18$	$3*L-5*m-2*A13-A19+A11+A20-2*A4-2*A6-2*A8+3*A7-4*A3-2*A5-2*A10-2*A2-A14-A15-A16-A17-A18$	$(9*4*m-7*L)/2$	$(L-4*m)/2$	$5*(R-L)-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43$	$4*(L-R)+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43$
$A27$	$6*m-R+A35-A36-A21+A22+A15-A14+A27$	$A28$	$A29$	$A30$	$A31$	$A32$	$A33$	$A34$	$6*R-5*L-2*A27-6*m-A35+A36+A21-A22-A15+A14-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34$	$(R-L)/2$	$(11*L-9*R)/2$
$R-L-A27$	$2*R-L-6*m-A35+A36+A21-A22-A15+A14-A27$	$R-L-A28$	$R-L-A29$	$R-L-A30$	$R-L-A31$	$R-L-A32$	$R-L-A33$	$R-L-A34$	$4*L-5*R+2*A27+6*m+A35-A36-A21+A22+A15-A14+A28+A29+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34$	$(11*L-9*R)/2$	$(R-L)/2$

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 at the upper-left corner containing four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 . The block of order 10 is also a **cornered** magic square of order 10. The magic rectangles of orders 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters T, L and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 8, 10 and 12 respectively. The letter m represents the width of magic rectangles appearing in magic squares of order 8. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums in pairs (L, R) and (T,L) should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd**. See below two examples.

Example 3.12. Let's consider following two examples:

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												250
-54	-14	72	68	14	-12	41	29	-33	39	55	45	250	
90	50	-36	-32	22	48	-5	7	-34	40	56	44	250	
17	21	37	-3	13	25	4	30	-35	41	57	43	250	
19	15	-1	39	23	11	32	6	-36	42	58	42	250	
11	3	35	23	-13	27	27	31	-37	43	59	41	250	
25	33	1	13	49	9	9	5	-38	44	60	40	250	
10	22	16	24	30	26	28	-12	-39	45	61	39	250	
26	14	20	12	6	10	8	48	276	-270	62	38	250	
-27	-70	-28	-29	-30	-31	-32	271	3	123	63	37	250	
33	76	34	35	36	37	38	-265	123	3	-31	131	250	
47	14	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	82	50	-300	250	
53	86	52	51	50	49	48	47	46	18	-300	50	250	
18a	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												275
-54	-12	70	66	14	-14	41	29	-29	39	55	70	275	
89	47	-35	-31	21	49	-6	6	-30	40	56	69	275	
17	21	37	-5	13	25	2	30	-31	41	57	68	275	
18	14	-2	40	22	10	33	5	-32	42	58	67	275	
11	1	35	23	-15	27	27	31	-33	43	59	66	275	
24	34	0	12	50	8	8	4	-34	44	60	65	275	
10	22	14	24	30	26	28	-14	-35	45	61	64	275	
25	13	21	11	5	9	7	49	264	-254	62	63	275	
-23	-77	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	270	5	105	63	62	275	
33	87	34	35	36	37	38	-260	105	5	94	31	275	
47	-17	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	238	62.5	-412.5	275	
78	142	77	76	75	74	73	72	71	-113	-412.5	62.5	275	
18b	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	

The magic sums of above two magic squares are as follows:

First Example

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 144$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 150$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 250$$

Second Example

$$M_{8 \times 8} = 140$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 150$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 275$$

Remark 5. The magic sum of order 8 is always even numbers as it is composed of eight equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 . In this case to get *odd number* magic sum of order 12, we wrote the pair $(L,R)=(150,275)$. This gives us few decimal entries.

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 36 \times 72$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 6 \times 24$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 100 \times 500$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 35 \times 70$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 10 \times 40$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 125 \times 625.$$

Result 3.13. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with *reduced entries*:

A7-A23+A15	A1	S-A7+A23-A15-A1-A2-A3	A2	A3	A7	A8	S-A7-A8-A9-A10	A9	A10	A38	R-2*S-A38
A21-A28+A13-A1+A6	A4	A7-A23+A15+A1+A2+A3-A4-A5-A21+A28-A13	A5	S-A7+A23-A15-A2-A3-A6	A14-A8+A13	A11	A7+A8+A9+A10-A11-A12-A13	A12	S-A7-A9-A10-A14	A39	R-2*S-A39
A1+A2+A3-A4-A21+A28-A13	S-A7+A23-A15-A1-A2-A3+A5-A6	A21-A28+A13	A21-A28+A13-A1-A2+A4+A6	A7-A23+A15+A1+A2-A5-A21+A28-A13	A8+A9+A10-A11-A13	S-A7-A8-A9-A10+A12-A14	A13	A13-A8-A9+A11+A14	A7+A8+A9-A12-A13	A40	R-2*S-A40
A21-A28+A13-A2+A4	A7-A23+A15-A5+A6	A1+A2-A21+A28-A13	S-A7+A23-A15-A4-A6-A21+A28-A13	A21-A28+A13-A1+A5	A13-A9+A11	A7-A12+A14	A8+A9-A13	S-A7-A11-A13-A14	A13-A8+A12	A41	R-2*S-A41
S-A7+A23-A15-A3-A6-A21+A28-A13	A2+A3-A4	A21-A28+A13-A1-A2+A4+A5	A7-A23+A15+A1-A5	A6	S-A7-A10-A13-A14	A9+A10-A11	A13-A8-A9+A11+A12	A7+A8-A12	A14	A42	R-2*S-A42
A15	A16	S-A15-A16-A17-A18	A17	A18	A23	A24	S-A23-A24-A25+A3-A18-A10	A25	A18+A10-A3	A43	R-2*S-A43
A22-A16+A21	A19	A15+A16+A17+A18-A19-A20-A21	A20	S-A15-A17-A18-A22	A22+A14-A6-A24+A28	A26	A23+A24+A25-A3+A18+A10-A26-A27-A28	A27	S-A23-A25+A3-A18-A10-A22-A14+A6	A44	R-2*S-A44
A16+A17+A18-A19-A21	S-A15-A16-A17-A18+A20-A22	A21	A21-A16-A17+A19+A22	A15+A16+A17-A20-A21	A24+A25-A3+A18+A10-A26-A28	S-A23-A24-A25+A3-A18-A10+A27-A22-A14+A6	A28	A28-A24-A25+A26+A22+A14-A6	A23+A24+A25-A27-A28	A45	R-2*S-A45
A21-A17+A19	A15-A20+A22	A16+A17-A21	S-A15-A19-A21-A22	A21-A16+A20	A28-A25+A26	A23-A27+A22+A14-A6	A24+A25-A28	S-A23-A26-A28-A22-A14+A6	A28-A24+A27	A46	R-2*S-A46
S-A15-A18-A21-A22	A17+A18-A19	A21-A16-A17+A19+A20	A15+A16-A20	A22	S-A23+A3-A18-A10-A28-A22-A14+A6	A25-A3+A18+A10-A26	A28-A24-A25+A26+A27	A23+A24-A27	A22+A14-A6	5*(R-2*S)-A38 - A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46	4*(2*S-R)+A38 +A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46
A39-A38-2*S+A30-A21+A28-A6-A13+R	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	4*R-8*S-A39+A38-2*A30+A21-A28+A6+A13-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37	(R-2*S)/2	(11*2*S-9*R)/2
A38-A30+A21-A28+A6+A13-A39	R-2*S-A30	R-2*S-A31	R-2*S-A32	R-2*S-A33	R-2*S-A34	R-2*S-A35	R-2*S-A36	R-2*S-A37	6*S-3*R+A39-A38+2*A30-A21+A28-A6-A13+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37	(11*2*S-9*R)/2	(R-2*S)/2

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with pandiagonal magic square of order 10 at the upperr-left corner. It is composed of 4 equal sum pandiagonal magic squares of order 5. The magic rectangles of orders 2×10 are of equal width and length The letters S, L and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 5, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums in pair (L, R) should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd**. See below two examples.

Example 3.13. Let's consider following two examples:

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											250	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT											261	
7	11	34	13	15	23	25	-24	27	29	85	5	250	7	11	55	13	15	23	25	-3	27	29	85	-26	261	
31	17	-11	19	24	47	31	5	33	-36	87	3	250	31	17	-11	19	45	47	31	5	33	-15	87	-28	261	
1	32	21	35	-9	15	-28	35	51	7	89	1	250	1	53	21	35	-9	15	-7	35	51	7	89	-30	261	
25	9	3	14	29	39	27	17	-46	43	91	-1	250	25	9	3	35	29	39	27	17	-25	43	91	-32	261	
16	11	33	-1	21	-44	25	47	15	37	93	-3	250	37	11	33	-1	21	-23	25	47	15	37	93	-34	261	
39	41	-88	43	45	55	57	-150	59	59	95	-5	250	39	41	-67	43	45	55	57	-129	59	59	95	-36	261	
63	47	21	49	-100	77	61	41	63	-162	97	-7	250	63	47	21	49	-79	77	61	41	63	-141	97	-38	261	
31	-92	51	67	23	49	-156	65	79	43	99	-9	250	31	-71	51	67	23	49	-135	65	79	43	99	-40	261	
55	43	33	-110	59	67	61	51	-170	71	101	-11	250	55	43	33	-89	59	67	61	51	-149	71	101	-42	261	
-108	41	63	31	53	-168	57	73	49	69	-387	477	250	-87	41	63	31	53	-147	57	73	49	69	-542	601	261	
119	69	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	-277	45	-245	250	88	69	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	-401	29.5	-63.5	261	
-29	21	19	17	15	13	11	9	7	367	-245	45	250	-29	-10	-12	-14	-16	-18	-20	-22	-24	460	-63.5	29.5	261	
20a	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	20b	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261

The magic sums of above two magic squares are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 80$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 160$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 250$$

Second Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 101$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 202$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 261$$

Remark 6. The magic sum of order 10 is always an even number as it is a composed of four equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 5. In this case to get **odd number** magic sum of order 12, we wrote the pair $(L,R)=(202,261)$. This gives us few decimal entries.

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 90 \times 450$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 59 \times 295.$$

3.4 Cornered With Double-Digit Bordered

Below are few examples of **cornered algebraic** magic squares of order 12, where there is **double-digit bordered** magic squares at upper-left.

Result 3.14. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with *reduced entries*:

$2*(L-S)/2-A51-A37-A44$	$2*A44+A51+A50+A37-A38-2*A31+(5*S-3*L)/2-A30$	A32	A33	A34	A35	$3*(L-S)/2-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36$	A36	$A38+2*A31-A37+A30-A44-A50$	A37	A61	R-L-A61
A30	A31	$(L-S)/2-A32$	$(L-S)/2-A33$	$(L-S)/2-A34$	$(L-S)/2-A35$	$A32+A33+A34+A35+A36-2*(L-S)/2$	$(L-S)/2-A36$	$(3*S-L)/2-A30-A31-A38$	A38	A62	R-L-A62
$3*(L-S)/2-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29$	$A25+A26+A27+A28+A29-2*(L-S)/2$	$A19+A20+A21+A22+A23-A4-A7-A11-A15$	A4	A7	A11	A15	S-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23	$(L-S)/2-A45$	A45	A63	R-L-A63
A25	$(L-S)/2-A25$	S-A12-A5-A8-A16-A19	A5	A8	A12	A16	A19	$(L-S)/2-A46$	A46	A64	R-L-A64
A26	$(L-S)/2-A26$	$A4+A7+A11+A15-A20-A21-A22-A23-A1-A2-A3+A5+A8+A12+A16$	$S-A4-A5-A12+A21+A22+A23-A17-A7-A8-A15-A16-A13-A9-A11+A1+A2+A3$	A9	A13	A17	A20	$S-L+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49$	$3*(L-S)/2-(A45+A46+A47+A48+A49)$	A65	R-L-A65
A27	$(L-S)/2-A27$	A1	$S+A16+A13+A6-A19+A3-A1-A18-A14-2*A21-A22-A23-A20$	$A21+A22+A23+A20-A16-A13-A6+A19-A3$	A14	A18	A21	$(L-S)/2-A47$	A47	A66	R-L-A66
A28	$(L-S)/2-A28$	A2	$S+A16+A13-A9+A6-A19+A3-A10-A21-A22-A23-A20-A7-A8$	$A5+A14+A10+2*A21+A22+3*A23+2*A20-A4+A8-A15-A16-A13+2*A9-2*A6+2*A19-A11-A2-A3-S$	$S-A19-A20-A21-A22-2*A23+A4+A7+A11+A15-A5-A9-A14$	A22	A22	$(L-S)/2-A48$	A48	A67	R-L-A67
A29	$(L-S)/2-A29$	A3	$A12+A18+A14+A21+A20+A17+A7+A8+A15+A9-2*A6+A19+A11-A2-2*A3-S$	A10	$2*S+A4-A8+A15+A16-2*A9+2*A6-2*A19+A2+A3-A12-A5-2*A14-A10-2*A21-A22-3*A23-2*A20$	$A19+A20+A21+A22+2*A23-A4-A7-A11+A5+A9+A14-2*A15-A16-A17-A18$	A23	$(L-S)/2-A49$	A49	A68	R-L-A68
$(5*S-3*L)/2+A51+A37-A30$	$(3*L-5*S)/2-A37+A30+A31-A44+A38$	$(L-S)/2-A39$	$A39+A40+A41+A42+A43-2*(L-S)/2$	$(L-S)/2-A40$	$(L-S)/2-A41$	$(L-S)/2-A42$	$(L-S)/2-A43$	A44+A37-A31	$(3*S-L)/2-A37-A38-A51$	A69	R-L-A69
A44	$(3*S-L)/2-A44-A51-A50$	A39	$3*(L-S)/2-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43$	A40	A41	A42	A43	A50	A51	$5*(R-L)-A61-A62-A63-A64-A65-A66-A67-A68-A69$	$4*(L-R)+A61+A62+A63+A64+A65+A66+A67+A68+A69$
$A32+A5+A25-S-A11+2*A9+A8-A16-A13+3*A23+2*A10+A22+A18+A14+3*A20-A38+A62+R-A61-A2-2*T-A15-A4-2*A6+2*A21-A3+2*A19-A45+A53$	A53	A54	A55	A56	A57	A58	A59	A60	$S+A11-2*A9-A8+A16+A13-3*A23-2*A10-A22-A18-A14-3*A20-A54-A59-A60-A55-A56-A57-A58+A38-A62+4*R+A61+A2+2*T+A15-5*L+A4+2*A6-2*A21+A3-2*A19+A45-2*A53-A32-A5-A25$	$(R-L)/2$	$(11*L-9*R)/2$
$S+A11-2*A9-A8+A16+A13-3*A23-2*A10-A22-A18-A14-3*A20+A38-A62+A61+A2+2*T+A15-L+A4+2*A6-2*A21+A3-2*A19+A45-A53-A32-A5-A25$	R-L-A53	R-L-A54	R-L-A55	R-L-A56	R-L-A57	R-L-A58	R-L-A59	R-L-A60	$A32+A5+A25-S-A11+2*A9+A8-A16-A13+3*A23+2*A10+A22+A18+A14+3*A20+A54+A59+A60+A55+A56+A57+A58-A38+A62-3*R-A61-A2-2*T-A15+4*L-A4-2*A6+2*A21-A3+2*A19-A45+2*A53$	$(11*L-9*R)/2$	$(R-L)/2$

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper-left corner. This magic square of order 10 is having magic squares of order 6 in the middle. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 , and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 6, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums in pairs (S, L) and (L, R) should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd**. See below two examples.

Example 3.14. Let's consider following two examples:

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												280
-72	91	42	43	44	45	-85	46	9	47	71	-1	280	
40	41	3	2	1	0	130	-1	-54	48	72	-2	280	
-50	95	78	14	17	21	25	-35	-10	55	73	-3	280	
35	10	10	15	18	22	26	29	-11	56	74	-4	280	
36	9	-4	25	19	23	27	30	195	-150	75	-5	280	
37	8	11	-51	77	24	28	31	-12	57	76	-6	280	
38	7	12	16	-31	140	-49	32	-13	58	77	-7	280	
39	6	13	101	20	-110	63	33	-14	59	78	-8	280	
53	43	-4	165	-5	-6	-7	-8	60	-81	79	-9	280	
54	-100	49	-120	50	51	52	53	60	61	-325	395	280	
400	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	-582	35	-105	280	
-330	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	652	-105	35	280	
32a	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												285
-72	96	42	43	44	45	-85	46	9	47	71	-1	285	
40	41	3	2	1	0	130	-1	-49	48	72	-2	285	
-50	95	78	14	17	21	25	-30	-10	55	73	-3	285	
35	10	15	15	18	22	26	29	-11	56	74	-4	285	
36	9	-4	30	19	23	27	30	195	-150	75	-5	285	
37	8	11	-46	77	24	28	31	-12	57	76	-6	285	
38	7	12	16	-26	135	-44	32	-13	58	77	-7	285	
39	6	13	96	20	-100	63	33	-14	59	78	-8	285	
58	38	-4	165	-5	-6	-7	-8	60	-76	79	-9	285	
54	-95	49	-120	50	51	52	53	60	61	-325	395	285	
390	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	-572	35	-100	285	
-320	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	642	-100	35	285	
32b	285	285	285	285	285	285	285	285	285	285	285	285	

The magic sums of above two magic squares are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 120$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 210$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 280$$

Second Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 125$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 215$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 285$$

The magic sums of magic rectangles are given by

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 45 \times 135$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 70 \times 350$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 45 \times 135$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 70 \times 350.$$

Result 3.15. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

$T-2*M-A36-A22-A29$	$2*A29+A36+A35+A22-A23-2*A16-3*T/2+5*M-A15$	A17	A18	A19	A20	$3*T/2-3*M-A17-A18-A19-A20-A21$	A21	$A23+2*A16-A22+A15-A29-A35$	A22	A46	L-T-A46
A15	A16	$(T-2*M)/2-A17$	$(T-2*M)/2-A18$	$(T-2*M)/2-A19$	$(T-2*M)/2-A20$	$A17+A18+A19+A20+A21-T+2*M$	$(T-2*M)/2-A21$	$3*M-T/2-A15-A16-A23$	A23	A47	L-T-A47
$3*T/2-3*M-A10-A11-A12-A13-A14$	$A10+A11+A12+A13+A14-T+2*M$	$2*M/3-A6$	$A6+A7-M/3$	$2*M/3-A7$	$2*M/3-A2$	$A2+A3-M/3$	$2*M/3-A3$	$(T-2*M)/2-A30$	A30	A48	L-T-A48
A10	$(T-2*M)/2-A10$	$A6+A8-M/3$	$M+A1-A6-A7-A8$	$M/3+A7-A1$	$A2+A4-M/3$	$5*M/3-A3-A2-A4-A5$	$A3+A5-M/3$	$(T-2*M)/2-A31$	A31	A49	L-T-A49
A11	$(T-2*M)/2-A11$	$2*M/3-A8$	$M/3+A8-A1$	A1	$2*M/3-A4$	$A4+A5-M/3$	$2*M/3-A5$	$2*M-T+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34$	$3*T/2-3*M-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34$	A50	L-T-A50
A12	$(T-2*M)/2-A12$	A2	$M-A2-A3$	A3	A6	$M-A6-A7$	A7	$(T-2*M)/2-A32$	A32	A51	L-T-A51
A13	$(T-2*M)/2-A13$	$M-A2-A4$	$A2+A3+A4+A5-M$	$M-A3-A5$	$M-A6-A8$	$A6+A7+A8-A1-M/3$	$M/3-A7+A1$	$(T-2*M)/2-A33$	A33	A52	L-T-A52
A14	$(T-2*M)/2-A14$	A4	$M-A4-A5$	A5	A8	$M/3-A8+A1$	$2*M/3-A1$	$(T-2*M)/2-A34$	A34	A53	L-T-A53
$5*M-3*T/2+A36+A22-A15$	$3*T/2-5*M-A22+A15+A16-A29+A23$	$(T-2*M)/2-A24$	$A24+A25+A26+A27+A28-T+2*M$	$(T-2*M)/2-A25$	$(T-2*M)/2-A26$	$(T-2*M)/2-A27$	$(T-2*M)/2-A28$	$A29+A22-A16$	$3*M-T/2-A22-A23-A36$	A54	L-T-A54
A29	$3*M-T/2-A29-A36-A35$	A24	$3*T/2-3*M-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28$	A25	A26	A27	A28	A35	A36	$5*(L-T)-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54$	$4*(T-L)+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54$
$A25-A8-2*A6-A7+(11/3)*M+L+A38-(5/2)*T+A26+A27+2*A24-A31+A28+A30+A47-A46$	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	$A8+2*A6+A7-(11/3)*M+4*L-A42-A41-A40-A39-2*A38-(5/2)*T-A25-A26-A27-2*A24+A31-A28-A30-A47+A46-A45-A44-A43$	$(L-T)/2$	$(11*T-9*L)/2$
$(3/2)*T-A25+A8+2*A6+A7-(11/3)*M-A38-A26-A27-2*A24+A31-A28-A30-A47+A46$	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	L-T-A41	L-T-A42	L-T-A43	L-T-A44	L-T-A45	$(11/3)*M-3*L+A42+A41+A40+A39+2*A38+(3/2)*T+A25+A26+A27+2*A24-A31+A28+A30+A47-A46+A45+A44+A43-A8-2*A6-A7$	$(11*T-9*L)/2$	$(L-T)/2$

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper-left corner. The magic square of order 10 contains magic square of order 6 in the middle. This magic square of order 6 is again formed by four equal sums magic squares of order 3. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, L and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 3, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums in pairs (S,L) and (L, R) should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd**. See below two examples.

Example 3.15. Let's consider following two examples:

	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											220
	-91	196	27	28	29	30	-106	31	-6	32	56	-6	220
	25	26	-14	-15	-16	-17	119	-18	47	33	57	-7	220
	-71	84	32	9	31	36	1	35	-27	40	58	-8	220
	20	-7	10	32	30	2	66	4	-28	41	59	-9	220
	21	-8	30	31	11	34	5	33	184	-171	60	-10	220
	22	-9	12	47	13	16	39	17	-29	42	61	-11	220
	23	-10	46	-18	44	38	16	18	-30	43	62	-12	220
	24	-11	14	43	15	18	17	37	-31	44	63	-13	220
	158	-92	-21	154	-22	-23	-24	-25	45	20	64	-14	220
	39	1	34	-141	35	36	37	38	45	46	-290	340	220
	254	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	-416	25	-55	220
	-204	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	466	-55	25	220
27a	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220

	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT											275
	-91	196	27	28	29	30	-106	31	-6	32	56	49	275
	25	26	-14	-15	-16	-17	119	-18	47	33	57	48	275
	-71	84	32	9	31	36	1	35	-27	40	58	47	275
	20	-7	10	32	30	2	66	4	-28	41	59	46	275
	21	-8	30	31	11	34	5	33	184	-171	60	45	275
	22	-9	12	47	13	16	39	17	-29	42	61	44	275
	23	-10	46	-18	44	38	16	18	-30	43	62	43	275
	24	-11	14	43	15	18	17	37	-31	44	63	42	275
	158	-92	-21	154	-22	-23	-24	-25	45	20	64	41	275
	39	1	34	-141	35	36	37	38	45	46	-15	120	275
	309	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	-196	52.5	-302.5	275
	-204	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	50	301	-302.5	52.5	275
27b	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275

The magic sums of above two magic squares are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 72$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 144$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 170$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 220$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} = 72$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 144$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 170$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 275$$

The magic rectangles sums are given by

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 13 \times 39$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 50 \times 250$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 13 \times 39$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 105 \times 525.$$

Remark 7. There are four entries with decimal numbers. It is due to the fact that the magic sum of order 10 is always an **even number** and the magic sum of order 12 is considered as **odd number**.

Result 3.16. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with **reduced entries**:

$2*(T-S)/2-A35-A20-A41$	$2*A41+A35+A34+A20-A21-2*A28+T-5*(T-S)/2-A27$	A15	A16	A17	A18	$3*(T-S)/2-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19$	A19	$A21+2*A28-A20+A27-A41-A34$	A20	A50	R-T-A50
A27	A28	$(T-S)/2-A15$	$(T-S)/2-A16$	$(T-S)/2-A17$	$(T-S)/2-A18$	$A15+A16+A17+A18+A19-T+S$	$(T-S)/2-A19$	$T-A27-A28-3*(T-S)/2-A21$	A21	A51	R-T-A51
$3*(T-S)/2-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	$A22+A23+A24+A25+A26-2*(T-S)/2$	A1	$A4+M-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	S-M-A10	A10	$(T-S)/2-A29$	A29	A52	R-T-A52
A22	$(T-S)/2-A22$	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	$A10+A11+A12-S+M$	$2*(S-M)-A10-A11-A12$	$(T-S)/2-A30$	A30	A53	R-T-A53
A23	$(T-S)/2-A23$	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	M-A1-A2-A4	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	S-M-A11	A11	$A29+A30+A31+A32+A33-T+S$	$3*(T-S)/2-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33$	$5*(R-T)-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57-A58$	$4*(T-R)+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54+A55+A56+A57+A58$
A24	$(T-S)/2-A24$	M-A1-A2-A3	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	S-M-A12	A12	$(T-S)/2-A31$	A31	A54	R-T-A54
A25	$(T-S)/2-A25$	S-M-A8	$2*S-A8-A1-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-M$	$2*A8+A1+A9+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12+M-2*S$	S-M-A9	$(S-M)/2$	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A32$	A32	A55	R-T-A55
A26	$(T-S)/2-A26$	A8	$A8+A1+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12-S$	$3*S-2*A8-A1-A9-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-2*M$	A9	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	$(S-M)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A33$	A33	A56	R-T-A56
$T-5*(T-S)/2+A35+A20-A27$	$5*(T-S)/2-T-A20+A27+A28-A41+A21$	$(T-S)/2-A36$	$A36+A37+A38+A39+A40-2*(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A37$	$(T-S)/2-A38$	$(T-S)/2-A39$	$(T-S)/2-A40$	$A41+A20-A28$	$T-A20-A21-3*(T-S)/2-A35$	A57	R-T-A57
A41	$T-3*(T-S)/2-A41-A35-A34$	A36	$3*(T-S)/2-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	A37	A38	A39	A40	A34	A35	A58	R-T-A58
$(11*S-5*T)/2-2*A12-4*M+A38+A39+A40+2*A36+A37-3*A4-2*A10+R-A30+A29-A1-A50+A51-2*A8-2*A9+A42$	A42	A43	A44	$2*A12-(11*S+5*T)/2+4*M-A38-A39-A40-2*A36-A37+3*A4+2*A10+4*R+A30-A29+A50-A51+2*A8+2*A9-A48-A49+A1-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-2*A42$	A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	$(R-T)/2$	$(11*T-9*R)/2$
$(3*T-11*S)/2+2*A12+4*M-A38-A39-A40-2*A36-A37+3*A4+2*A10+A30-A29+A1+A50-A51+2*A8+2*A9-A42$	R-T-A42	R-T-A43	R-T-A44	$(11*S+3*T)/2-2*A12-4*M+A38+A39+A40+2*A36+A37-3*A4-2*A10-3*R-A30+A29-A50+A51-2*A8-2*A9+A48+A49-A1+A47+A46+A45+A44+A43+2*A42$	R-T-A45	R-T-A46	R-T-A47	R-T-A48	R-T-A49	$(11*T-9*R)/2$	$(R-T)/2$

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper left corner embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 6 containing magic square of order 4. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 , 2×6 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums S, L and R should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Example 3.16. Let's consider following two examples:

4	mgc												200	4	mgc												251			
		-86	127	25	26	27	28	-75	29	19	30	60	-10	200			-66	108	25	26	27	28	-45	29	19	30	60	10	251	
		37	38	-5	-6	-7	-8	95	-9	-16	31	61	-11	200			37	38	5	4	3	2	75	1	-15	31	61	9	251	
		-110	130	11	67	-11	13	10	20	-19	39	62	-12	200			-80	110	11	68	-11	13	20	20	-9	39	62	8	251	
		32	-12	16	14	15	35	33	-3	-20	40	63	-13	200			32	-2	16	14	15	36	23	17	-10	40	63	7	251	
		33	-13	9	8	43	20	9	21	165	-145	-326	376	200			33	-3	9	8	44	20	19	21	145	-115	-226	296	251	
		34	-14	44	-9	33	12	8	22	-21	41	64	-14	200			34	-4	45	-9	33	12	18	22	-11	41	64	6	251	
		35	-15	12	-14	51	11	15	35	-22	42	65	-15	200			35	-5	22	7	30	21	20	21	-12	42	65	5	251	
		36	-16	18	44	-21	19	35	15	-23	43	66	-16	200			36	-6	18	33	10	19	21	20	-13	43	66	4	251	
		88	-25	-26	200	-27	-28	-29	-30	43	-16	67	-17	200			69	-6	-16	180	-17	-18	-19	-20	43	-15	67	3	251	
		51	-50	46	-180	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	-18	200			51	-49	46	-150	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	2	251	
		237	52	53	54	-431	55	56	57	58	59	25	-75	200			267	52	53	54	-361	55	56	57	58	59	35	-134	251	
		-187	-2	-3	-4	481	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-75	25	200			-197	18	17	16	431	15	14	13	12	11	-134	35	251	
		200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200			251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 80$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 110$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 150$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 81$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 121$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 181$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 251$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. To avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums (L,R), (S,L) and (M,S) are **even** numbers for **first example** and **odd** numbers for **second example**. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 20 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 50 \times 250$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 40 \times 80$$

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 30 \times 90$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 70 \times 350$$

Result 3.17. *Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:*

$2*(T-S)/2-A42-A28-A35$	$2*A35+A42+A41+A28-A29-2*A22+(5*S-3*T)/2-A21$	A23	A24	A25	A26	$3*(T-S)/2-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27$	A27	$A29+2*A22-A28+A21-A35-A41$	A28	A53	R-T-A53
A21	A22	$(T-S)/2-A23$	$(T-S)/2-A24$	$(T-S)/2-A25$	$(T-S)/2-A26$	$A23+A24+A25+A26+A27-2*(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A27$	$(3*S-T)/2-A21-A22-A29$	A29	A54	R-T-A54
$3*(T-S)/2-A16-A17-A18-A19-A20$	$A16+A17+A18+A19+A20-2*(T-S)/2$	$4*S-6*M+A12$	$S-M+2*A14+2*A13-4*A12$	$2*A12+9*M-6*S-A14-A13$	S-M-A14	S-M-A13	A12	$(T-S)/2-A36$	A36	A55	R-T-A55
A16	$(T-S)/2-A16$	$4*M-3*S+A9+A10+A11$	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	$4*S-5*M-A9-A10-A11$	$(T-S)/2-A37$	A37	A56	R-T-A56
A17	$(T-S)/2-A17$	S-M-A9	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A9	$S-T+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40$	$3*(T-S)/2-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	$5*(R-T)-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57-A58-A59-A60-A61$	$4*(T-R)+A53+A54+A55+A56+A57+A58+A59+A60+A61$
A18	$(T-S)/2-A18$	S-M-A10	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	A10	$(T-S)/2-A38$	A38	A57	R-T-A57
A19	$(T-S)/2-A19$	S--M-A11	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6	A2	A11	$(T-S)/2-A39$	A39	A58	R-T-A58
A20	$(T-S)/2-A20$	$5*M-3*S-A12$	$4*A12-2*A14-2*A13$	$7*(T-2*(T-S)/2)+A14+A13-2*A12-10*M$	A14	A13	$5*M-A12-3*S$	$(T-S)/2-A40$	A40	A59	R-T-A59
$(5*S-3*T)/2+A42+A28-A21$	$(3*T-5*S)/2-A28+A21+A22-A35+A29$	$(T-S)/2-A30$	$A30+A31+A32+A33+A34-2*(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A31$	$(T-S)/2-A32$	$(T-S)/2-A33$	$(T-S)/2-A34$	A35+A28-A22	$(3*S-T)/2-A28-A29-A42$	A60	R-T-A60
A35	$(3*S-T)/2-A35-A42-A41$	A30	$3*(T-S)/2-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34$	A31	A32	A33	A34	A41	A42	A61	R-T-A61
A45	$(5*T-15*S)/2+2*A12-A32-A13+10*A7-A14-A36+A37-3*A4-A31-A34-A33-2*A30+A53-A54-A9-R-A1+A45$	A46	A47	$15*(S-T)/2+A32-A52-2*A12+A13+A14+A36-A37+3*A4-A49-A48-A47-A46-A50+A31+A34+A33+6*R-2*A45-A53-A51+A54+2*A30+A9-10*M+A1$	A48	A49	A50	A51	A52	$(R-T)/2$	$(11*T-9*R)/2$
R-T-A45	$2*R+(15*S-7*T)/2-2*A12+A32+A13-10*A7+A14+A36-A37+3*A4+A31+A34+A33+2*A30-A53+A54+A9+A1-A45$	R-T-A46	R-T-A47	$(13*T-15*S)/2+A52+2*A12-A32-A13-A14-A36+A37-3*A4+A49+A48+A47+A46+A50-A31-A34-A33-5*R+2*A45+A53+A51-A54-2*A30-A9+10*M-A1$	R-T-A48	R-T-A49	R-T-A50	R-T-A51	R-T-A52	$(11*T-9*R)/2$	$(R-T)/2$

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper left corner. The inner part is a **single-digit** magic square of order 6 embedded with magic square of order 4. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, L and R represents magic sums for the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the of magic sums M, S, L and R should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Example 3.17. Let's consider following two examples:

5	mgc												200	5	mgc												231		
		-157	153	55	57	59	61	-175	63	-11	65	115	-85	200			-157	134	55	57	59	61	-175	63	-11	65	115	-35	231
		51	53	-15	-17	-19	-21	215	-23	-121	67	117	-87	200			51	53	-15	-17	-19	-21	215	-23	-140	67	117	-37	231
		-105	145	93	52	-96	3	5	33	-41	81	119	-89	200			-105	145	17	33	18	-16	-14	33	-41	81	119	-39	231
		41	-1	17	11	35	-11	15	23	-43	83	121	-91	200			41	-1	74	11	35	-11	15	-53	-43	83	121	-41	231
		43	-3	13	21	17	19	-7	27	345	-305	-957	987	200			43	-3	-6	21	17	19	-7	27	345	-305	-707	787	231
		45	-5	11	7	5	9	29	29	-45	85	123	-93	200			45	-5	-8	7	5	9	29	29	-45	85	123	-43	231
		47	-7	9	11	-7	33	13	31	-47	87	125	-95	200			47	-7	-10	11	-7	33	13	31	-47	87	125	-45	231
		49	-9	-53	-12	136	37	35	-53	-49	89	127	-97	200			49	-9	4	-12	3	37	35	4	-49	89	127	-47	231
		77	57	-29	285	-31	-33	-35	-37	91	-175	129	-99	200			58	76	-29	285	-31	-33	-35	-37	91	-194	129	-49	231
		79	-213	69	-245	71	73	75	77	91	93	131	-101	200			79	-232	69	-245	71	73	75	77	91	93	131	-51	231
		99	-380	101	103	-318	105	107	109	111	113	15	35	200			99	-316	101	103	-132	105	107	109	111	113	40	-209	231
		-69	410	-71	-73	348	-75	-77	-79	-81	-83	35	15	200			-19	396	-21	-23	212	-25	-27	-29	-31	-33	-209	40	231
		200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200			231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 50$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 90$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 170$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 50$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 71$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 151$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 231$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. To avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums (T, R) and (M,T) are **even** numbers for **first example** and **odd** numbers for **second example**. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 40 \times 120$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 30 \times 150$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 40 \times 120$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 80 \times 400$$

Result 3.18. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

A18	A19	$2*(T-S)/2-A15-A16-A17$	A15	A16	A17	$2*S-T+A18-A19+A23$	$2*(T-S)/2-A23-2*A18$	L-T-A28	A28	A49	R-L-A49
$2*A13+A24+A14+2*A18-2*(T-S)/2-A19$	$2*(T-S)/2-2*A18-A13$	$A15+A16+A17-(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A15$	$(T-S)/2-A16$	$(T-S)/2-A17$	$2*(T-S)/2-A23-A13-A24-A18+A19$	$2*S-T+A18+A23-A14$	L-T-A29	A29	A50	R-L-A50
$2*(T-S)/2-A7-A8-A9$	$A7+A8+A9-(T-S)/2$	A1	$A4+S-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	$A10+A11+A12-(T-S)/2$	$2*(T-S)/2-A10-A11-A12$	$A28+A29+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+3*T-3*L$	$4*L-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-4*T$	A51	R-L-A51
A7	$(T-S)/2-A7$	A6	A4	A5	S-A4-A5-A6	$(T-S)/2-A10$	A10	L-T-A30	A30	A52	R-L-A52
A8	$(T-S)/2-A8$	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	S-A1-A2-A4	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	$(T-S)/2-A11$	A11	L-T-A31	A31	$5*(R-L)-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57$	$4*(L-R)+A49+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54+A55+A56+A57$
A9	$(T-S)/2-A9$	S-A1-A2-A3	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	$(T-S)/2-A12$	A12	L-T-A32	A32	A53	R-L-A53
$T-2*A13-A14+A19-3*A18-A23-A24$	$A23+3*A18+A24-A19+A13-2*(T-S)/2$	$A20+A21+A22-(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A20$	$(T-S)/2-A21$	$(T-S)/2-A22$	A13	A14	L-T-A33	A33	A54	R-L-A54
A23	$T-A23-A18-2*(T-S)/2-A24$	$2*(T-S)/2-A20-A21-A22$	A20	A21	A22	A24	A18	L-T-A34	A34	A55	R-L-A55
L-T-A35	$T-A1+A29-A28+A11+A21+A22+2*A20-6*(T-S)/2-A35+2*A10+12-3*A4$	$T+A1-A29+A28-A11-A21-A22-2*A20+6*(T-S)/2+2*A35-2*A10-A12-2*L+3*A4+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40$	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	$(L-T)/2$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	A56	R-L-A56
A35	$A1-A29+A28-A11-A21-A22-2*A20+6*(T-S)/2+A35-2*T-2*A10-A12+L+3*A4$	$3*L-2*T-A1+A29-A28+A11+A21+A22+2*A20-6*(T-S)/2-2*A35+2*A10+A12-3*A4-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	$(L-T)/2$	A57	R-L-A57
$7*L-2*A28-A32+R+2*A11-8*T-2*A35+2*A21-A38-A39-A40-2*A36-A37-3*A4+2*A10-4*(T-S)/2-A31+2*A20-A34-A33-2*A30-A1-A49+A50+A41$	A41	A42	A43	$2*A28-12*L+A32+4*R-2*A11+8*T+2*A35-2*A21+A38+A39+A40+2*A36+A37+3*A4-2*A10+4*(T-S)/2+A31-2*A20+A34+A33+2*A30+A49-A50-A47-A48+A1-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42-2*A41$	A44	A45	A46	A47	A48	$(R-L)/2$	$(11*L-9*R)/2$
$2*A28-8*L+A32-2*A11+8*T+2*A35-2*A21+A38+A39+A40+2*A36+A37+3*A4-2*A10+4*(T-S)/2+A31-2*A20+A34+A33+2*A30+A49-A50+A1-A41$	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	$11*L-2*A28-A32-3*R+2*A11-8*T-2*A35+2*A21-A38-A39-A40-2*A36-A37-3*A4+2*A10-4*(T-S)/2-A31+2*A20-A34-A33-2*A30-A49+A50+A47+A48-A1+A46+A45+A44+A43+A42+2*A41$	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	R-L-A47	R-L-A48	$(11*L-9*R)/2$	$(R-L)/2$

Details:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 8 at the upper left corner embedded with a magic square of order 4. The four magic rectangles of orders 2×4 are of equal width and length. Also the magic rectangles of orders 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. It also contains a magic square of order 10. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 4, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums T, L and R should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Example 3.18. Let's consider following two examples:

3	mgc												200	3	mgc												201			
		38	39	-28	35	36	37	22	-39	-18	48	69	-39	200			38	39	-48	35	36	37	53	-59	-8	48	69	-39	201	
		101	-29	68	5	4	3	-39	27	-19	49	70	-40	200			121	-49	78	-5	-6	-7	-59	58	-9	49	70	-40	201	
		-4	44	21	37	-21	23	53	-13	267	-237	71	-41	200			-24	54	21	48	-21	23	63	-33	237	-197	71	-41	201	
		27	13	26	24	25	-15	10	30	-20	50	72	-42	200			27	3	26	24	25	-4	0	30	-10	50	72	-42	201	
		28	12	19	18	-7	30	9	31	-21	51	-507	537	200			28	2	19	18	4	30	-1	31	-11	51	-507	537	201	
		29	11	-6	-19	63	22	8	32	-22	52	73	-43	200			29	1	5	-19	63	22	-2	32	-12	52	73	-43	201	
		-122	115	83	0	-1	-2	33	34	-23	53	74	-44	200			-131	135	93	-10	-11	-12	33	34	-13	53	74	-44	201	
		43	-65	-43	40	41	42	44	38	-24	54	75	-45	200			43	-54	-63	40	41	42	44	38	-14	54	75	-45	201	
		-25	39	246	-26	-27	-28	-29	-30	15	35	76	-46	200			-15	90	175	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	20	-9	76	-46	201	
		55	-9	-216	56	57	58	59	60	35	15	77	-47	200			55	-50	-135	56	57	58	59	60	-9	20	77	-47	201	
		-499	61	62	63	133	64	65	66	67	68	15	35	200			-379	61	62	63	13	64	65	66	67	68	15	36	201	
		529	-31	-32	-33	-103	-34	-35	-36	-37	-38	35	15	200			409	-31	-32	-33	17	-34	-35	-36	-37	-38	36	15	201	
		200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200			201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 60$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 140$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 170$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 71$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 131$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 171$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 201$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. To avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums (T, R) and (M,T) are **even** numbers for **first example** and **odd** numbers for **second example**. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 40 \times 80$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 30 \times 120$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 30 \times 150$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{8 \times 8} = 40 \times 160$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 30 \times 150$$

3.5 Cornered with Single-Digit Bordered

Result 3.19. *Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:*

4^*S-6^*M+A12	$S+2^*A13+2^*A14-4^*A12-M$	$2^*A12+9^*M-6^*S-A13-A14$	S-A13-M	S-A14-M	A12	T-S-A16	A16	L-T-A25	A25	A46	R-L-A46
$4^*M-3^*S+A9+A10+A11$	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	$4^*S-A9-A10-A11-5^*M$	$T-S-A16-A1-A13-A9-A14+2^*A12-7^*S-3^*A4+10^*M$	$A16+A1+A13+A9+A14-2^*A12+7^*S+3^*A4-10^*M$	$3^*T-3^*L+A25+A26+A27+A28+A29+A30+A31$	$4^*L-4^*T-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31$	A47	R-L-A47
S-A9-M	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A9	$2^*A16+A18+A19+A1-2^*T+9^*S+A13+A9+A14-2^*A12+3^*A4-10^*M+A17$	$3^*T-10^*S-A18-A19-2^*A16-A1-A13-A9-A14+2^*A12-3^*A4+10^*M-A17$	L-T-A26	A26	A48	R-L-A48
S-A10-M	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	A10	T-S-A17	A17	L-T-A27	A27	A49	R-L-A49
S-A11-M	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2^*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2^*A4-A5-A6	A2	A11	T-S-A18	A18	L-T-A28	A28	$5^*(R-L)-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54$	$4^*(L-R)+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54$
$5^*M-A12-3^*S$	$4^*A12-2^*A13-2^*A14$	$7^*S+A13+A14-2^*A12-10^*M$	A13	A14	$5^*M-A12-3^*S$	T-S-A19	A19	L-T-A29	A29	A50	R-L-A50
$T-S+A13+A9+A14-2^*A12+2^*A1+7^*S+6^*A4-11^*M$	$8^*S+A13+A9+A14-2^*A12+2^*A1+6^*A4-11^*M$	$A21+A20+A22-T-2^*A13-2^*A9-2^*A14+4^*A12-4^*A1-14^*S-12^*A4+22^*M$	T-S-A20	T-S-A21	T-S-A22	(T-S)/2	$(7^*S-5^*T)/2$	L-T-A30	A30	A51	R-L-A51
$11^*M-A13-A9-A14+2^*A12-2^*A1-7^*S-6^*A4$	$T-9^*S-A13-A9-A14+2^*A12-2^*A1-6^*A4+11^*M$	$2^*T+13^*S+2^*A13+2^*A9+2^*A14-4^*A12+4^*A1+12^*A4-22^*M-A21-A20-A22$	A20	A21	A22	$(7^*S-5^*T)/2$	(T-S)/2	L-T-A31	A31	A52	R-L-A52
L-T-A32	$4^*L+2^*A17+A19+A18+2^*A16+12^*M-9^*A4+2^*A12-3^*A1-S-A13-A9-2^*A14-A11+A21+2^*A20+A22-A32-10^*T-2^*A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31$	$2^*A32+12^*T+2^*A25+A26+A27+A28+A29+A30+A31-6^*L+A37+A36+A35+A34+A33-2^*A17-A19-A18-2^*A16-12^*M+9^*A4-2^*A12+3^*A1+S+A13+A9+2^*A14+A11-A21-2^*A20-A22$	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	(L-T)/2	$(9^*T-7^*L)/2$	A53	R-L-A53
A32	$A32+9^*T+2^*A25+A26+A27+A28+A29+A30+A31-3^*L-2^*A17-A19-A18-2^*A16-12^*M+9^*A4-2^*A12+3^*A1+S+A13+A9+2^*A14+A11-A21-2^*A20-A22$	$2^*A17+A19+A18+2^*A16+12^*M-9^*A4+2^*A12-3^*A1-S-A13-A9-2^*A14-A11+A21+2^*A20+A22-2^*A32-13^*T-2^*A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31+7^*L-A37-A36-A35-A34-A33$	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	$(9^*T-7^*L)/2$	(L-T)/2	A54	R-L-A54
$7^*L-A28-2^*A27-3^*S+2^*A16+2^*A12-2^*A32+2^*A17-A13-A11+12^*M-2^*A14-A35+2^*A21-13^*T+R-A36-A37-9^*A4-2^*A25-A31+2^*A18+2^*A20-A34-2^*A33-A30-A29-A46+A47-A9-3^*A1+A38$	A38	A39	A40	$A28+2^*A27+3^*S-12^*L-2^*A16-2^*A12+2^*A32-2^*A17+A13+A11-12^*M+2^*A14+A35-2^*A21+13^*T+4^*R+A36+A37+9^*A4+2^*A25+A31-2^*A18-2^*A20+A34+2^*A33+A30+A29+A46-A47+A9-A44-A45+3^*A1-A43-A42-A41-A40-A39-2^*A38$	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	(R-L)/2	$(11^*L-9^*R)/2$
$A28+2^*A27+3^*S-8^*L-2^*A16-2^*A12+2^*A32-2^*A17+A13+A11-12^*M+2^*A14-A35+2^*A21-13^*T-3^*R-A36-A37-9^*A4-2^*A25-A31+2^*A18+2^*A20-A34-2^*A33-A30-A29-A46+A47-A9+A44+A45-3^*A1+A43+A42+A41+A40+A39+2^*A38$	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	$11^*L-A28-2^*A27-3^*S+2^*A16+2^*A12-2^*A32+2^*A17-A13-A11+12^*M-2^*A14-A35+2^*A21-13^*T-3^*R-A36-A37-9^*A4-2^*A25-A31+2^*A18+2^*A20-A34-2^*A33-A30-A29-A46+A47-A9+A44+A45-3^*A1+A43+A42+A41+A40+A39+2^*A38$	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	$(11^*L-9^*R)/2$	(R-L)/2

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 6 at the upper left corner again embedded with magic square of order 4. Magic square of orders 8 and 10 are also parts of **cornered** magic square. This block of order 6 is a **reduced entries semi-magic** square, but the way it is constructed lead us to a magic square of order 12. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 , 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents magic sums for the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the of magic sums S, T, L and R should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Example 3.19. Let's consider following two examples:

6	mgc												200	6	mgc												331			
		37	52	-6	1	-1	37	-35	45	-33	63	105	-65	200			41	53	-12	2	0	37	-5	45	-33	63	105	35	331	
		59	15	61	-15	19	-19	-190	200	393	-363	107	-67	200			56	15	61	-15	19	-15	-167	207	393	-363	107	33	331	
		9	25	21	23	11	31	372	-362	-35	65	109	-69	200			10	25	21	23	11	31	319	-279	-35	65	109	31	331	
		7	11	9	27	33	33	-37	47	-37	67	111	-71	200			8	11	9	27	33	33	-7	47	-37	67	111	29	331	
		5	29	-11	45	17	35	-39	49	-39	69	-817	857	200			6	29	-11	45	17	35	-9	49	-39	69	-317	457	331	
		3	-12	46	39	41	3	-41	51	-41	71	113	-73	200			0	-12	53	39	41	0	-11	51	-41	71	113	27	331	
		163	273	-271	-43	-45	-47	5	95	-43	73	115	-75	200			200	281	-316	-13	-15	-17	20	21	-43	73	115	25	331	
		-153	-263	281	53	55	57	95	5	-45	75	117	-77	200			-160	-241	356	53	55	57	21	20	-45	75	117	23	331	
		-47	-288	720	-49	-51	-53	-55	-57	15	25	119	-79	200			-47	-475	907	-49	-51	-53	-55	-57	15	56	119	21	331	
		77	318	-690	79	81	83	85	87	25	15	121	-81	200			77	505	-877	79	81	83	85	87	56	15	121	19	331	
		-724	89	91	93	156	95	97	99	101	103	20	-20	200			-782	89	91	93	714	95	97	99	101	103	70	-439	331	
		764	-49	-51	-53	-116	-55	-57	-59	-61	-63	-20	20	200			922	51	49	47	-574	45	43	41	39	37	-439	70	331	
		200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200			331	331	331	331	331	331	331	331	331	331	331	331	331	331

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 80$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 120$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 130$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 160$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 80$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 121$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 161$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 191$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 331$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. To avoid decimal entries, the magic sums S, T, L and R are **even** numbers for **first example** and **odd** numbers for **second example**. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 10 \times 30$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 30 \times 120$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 40 \times 200$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 40 \times 120$$

$$MR_{8 \times 8} = 30 \times 120$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 140 \times 700$$

Result 3.20. *Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:*

T-S-A17	$2*T+3*S+A19-A14-A20$	T-S-A14	$A18+2*A17-7*T+2*S+A16+A15+2*A14+A21+A22+A24+2*A20+A23$	T-S-A15	T-S-A16	T-S-A18	T-A21-A22-A24-A20-A23-A17-A19	A32	L-T-A32	A48	R-L-A48
T-S-A20	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	S-M-A10	A10	A20	A33	L-T-A33	A49	R-L-A49
T-S-A21	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	$A10+A11+A12-S+M$	$2*S-2*M-A10-A11-A12$	A21	A34	L-T-A34	A50	R-L-A50
T-S-A22	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	S-M-A11	A11	A22	A35	L-T-A35	A51	R-L-A51
T-S-A23	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	S-M-A12	A12	A23	$4*L-4*T-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38$	$3*(T-L)+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38$	$5*(R-L)-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55-A56$	$4*(L-R)+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54+A55+A56$
T-S-A24	S-M-A8	$2*S-A8-A1-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-M$	$2*A8+A1+A9+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12+M-2*S$	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	A24	A36	L-T-A36	A52	R-L-A52
T-S-A19	A8	$A8+A1+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12-S$	$3*S-2*A8-A1-A9-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-2*M$	A9	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	(S-M)/2	A19	A37	L-T-A37	A53	R-L-A53
$A17+A19+7*S+A21+A22+A24+A20+A23-6*T$	$A14+A20-T-A19-4*S$	A14	$8*T-A18-2*A17-3*S-A16-A15-2*A14-A21-A22-A24-2*A20-A23$	A15	A16	A18	A17	A38	L-T-A38	A54	R-L-A54
$5*S-2*A12-4*M+A21-3*A4-2*A10+A33-2*T-A1+A26-2*A8-2*A9-A32+L+A14$	A26	A27	A28	$3*L-2*T+2*A12-5*S+4*M-A21+3*A4+2*A10-A33+A1-2*A26+2*A8+2*A9+A32-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A14$	A29	A30	A31	(L-T)/2	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	A55	R-L-A55
$T+2*A12-5*S+4*M-A21+3*A4+2*A10-A33+A1-A26+2*A8+2*A9+A32-A14$	L-T-A26	L-T-A27	L-T-A28	$T-2*L-2*A12+5*S-4*M+A21-3*A4-2*A10+A33-A1+2*A26-2*A8-2*A9-A32+A27+A28+A29+A30+A31+A14$	L-T-A29	L-T-A30	L-T-A31	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	(L-T)/2	A56	R-L-A56
A40	$A40-A15-R+2*T+A27-A28-5*M+3*S-A23-A35+A34-A49+A48$	A41	A42	$6*R-5*L-2*A40+A15-2*T-A27+A28+5*M-3*S+A23+A35-A34+A49-A48-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47$	A43	A44	A45	A46	A47	(R-L)/2	$(11*L-9*R)/2$
R-L-A40	$2*R-L-A40+A15-2*T-A27+A28+5*M-3*S+A23+A35-A34+A49-A48$	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	$4*L-5*R+2*A40-A15+2*T+A27-A28-5*M+3*S-A23-A35+A34-A49+A48+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47$	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	R-L-A47	$(11*L-9*R)/2$	(R-L)/2

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 8 at the upper left corner again embedded with cornered magic square of order 6. Magic square of order 10 is also a part of **cornered** magic square. This block of order 8 is a **reduced entries semi-magic** square, but the way it is constructed lead us to a magic square of order 12. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 , 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents magic sums for the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums T, L and R should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Example 3.20. Let's consider following two examples:

7	mgc												200	7	mgc												251
	-29	507	-20	117	-23	-26	-32	-364	104	-64	152	-122	200		-28	509	-19	110	-22	-25	-31	-363	104	-64	152	-72	251
	-38	11	63	-11	17	-18	38	68	107	-67	155	-125	200		-37	11	63	-11	17	-18	38	68	107	-67	155	-75	251
	-41	26	20	23	11	103	-83	71	110	-70	158	-128	200		-40	26	20	23	11	103	-83	71	110	-70	158	-78	251
	-44	5	2	35	38	-21	41	74	113	-73	161	-131	200		-43	5	2	35	38	-21	41	74	113	-73	161	-81	251
	-47	38	-5	33	14	-24	44	77	-631	671	-1326	1356	200		-46	38	-5	33	14	-24	44	77	-631	671	-1076	1156	251
	-50	-12	-144	211	-15	10	50	80	116	-76	164	-134	200		-49	-12	-144	211	-15	10	50	80	116	-76	164	-84	251
	-35	32	164	-191	35	50	10	65	119	-79	167	-137	200		-34	32	164	-191	35	50	10	65	119	-79	167	-87	251
	414	-477	50	-87	53	56	62	59	122	-82	170	-140	200		408	-478	50	-79	53	56	62	59	122	-82	170	-90	251
	-69	86	89	92	-332	95	98	101	20	-10	173	-143	200		-70	86	89	92	-331	95	98	101	20	-9	173	-93	251
	109	-46	-49	-52	372	-55	-58	-61	-10	20	176	-146	200		110	-46	-49	-52	371	-55	-58	-61	-9	20	176	-96	251
	128	-51	131	134	-907	137	140	143	146	149	15	35	200		128	-100	131	134	-608	137	140	143	146	149	40	-189	251
	-98	81	-101	-104	937	-107	-110	-113	-116	-119	35	15	200		-48	180	-51	-54	688	-57	-60	-63	-66	-69	-189	40	251
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 80$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 100$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 130$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 170$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 80$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 100$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 131$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 171$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 251$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. To avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums (T,L) and (L,R) are **even** numbers for **first example** and **odd** numbers for **second example**. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 20 \times 40$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 40 \times 160$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 30 \times 150$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 20 \times 40$$

$$MR_{8 \times 8} = 40 \times 160$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 80 \times 400$$

Result 3.21. *Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:*

T-S-A25	$2^*T+3^*S+A16-2^*A13-A22-2^*A12-2^*A8-5^*M-3^*A4-A17-2^*A14$	T-S-A22	$A26+2^*A25+2^*A13-7^*T+2^*S+A24+A23+2^*A22+2^*A12+2^*A8+5^*M+3^*A4+A18+A19+A21+2^*A17+2^*A14+A20$	T-S-A23	T-S-A24	T-S-A26	T-A18-A19-A21-A17-A20-A25-A16	L-T-A29	A29	A50	R-L-A50
T-S-A17	S-M-A14	S-A12-M	$2^*A11-3^*A4-A12-A8+A9+M$	$3^*A4-3^*S+2^*A12+A13+2^*A8+A9-A10+2^*A14+2^*M$	S-A13-M	S-A8-A9-A10-A11-A14	A17	L-T-A30	A30	A51	R-L-A51
T-S-A18	S-M-A9	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	A9	A18	$A29+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+3^*T-3^*L$	$4^*L-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-4^*T$	A52	R-L-A52
T-S-A19	S-M-A10	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A10	A19	L-T-A31	A31	A53	R-L-A53
T-S-A20	S-M-A11	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	A11	A20	L-T-A32	A32	$5^*(R-L)-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57-A58$	$4^*(L-R)+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54+A55+A56+A57+A58$
T-S-A21	S-M-A8	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2^*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2^*A4-A5-A6	A2	A8	A21	L-T-A33	A33	A54	R-L-A54
T-S-A16	$A8-4^*S+A9+A10+A11+A14+5^*M$	A12	$S-2^*A11+3^*A4+A12+A8-A9-2^*M$	$4^*S+A11-3^*A4-2^*A12-A13-2^*A8-A10-2^*A14-3^*M$	A13	A14	A16	L-T-A34	A34	A55	R-L-A55
$A25+A16+7^*S+A18+A19+A21+A17+A20-6^*T$	$A22+2^*A12+2^*A8+5^*M+3^*A4+A17+2^*A14-T-A16+2^*A13-4^*S$	A22	$8^*T-A26-2^*A25-2^*A13-3^*S-A24-A23-2^*A22-2^*A12-2^*A8-5^*M-3^*A4-A18-A19-A21-2^*A17-2^*A14-A20$	A23	A24	A26	A25	L-T-A35	A35	A56	R-L-A56
L-T-A36	$A30-A29-A18-A36+T-A12-A22+2^*A11+A9-S-A8-6^*A4+2^*M-A1-A10$	$A29-A30+A18+A38+A37+A40+2^*A36+T+A12+A22-2^*A11+A39-A9-2^*L+S+A8+6^*A4-2^*M+A1+A10+A41$	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	L-T-A41	(L-T)/2	$(9^*T-7^*L)/2$	A57	R-L-A57
A36	$A29-A30+A18+A36-2^*T+A12+A22-2^*A11-A9+L+S+A8+6^*A4-2^*M+A1+A10$	$A30-A29-A18-A38-A37-A40-2^*A36-2^*T-A12-A22+2^*A11-A39+A9+3^*L-S-A8-6^*A4+2^*M-A1-A10-A41$	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	$(9^*T-7^*L)/2$	(L-T)/2	A58	R-L-A58
$7^*L-8^*T-S-A12-A32+A13+2^*A11+2^*M-A35+A23-A38-A39-A40-2^*A36-2^*A37-6^*A4-A10+R-2^*A31-A18+A20-A34-A33-A22-A41-2^*A29-A50+A51+A9-A1+A42$	A42	A43	A44	$8^*T-12^*L+S+A12+A32-A13-2^*A11-2^*M+A35-A23+A38+A39+A40+2^*A36+2^*A37+6^*A4+A10+4^*R+2^*A31+A18-A20+A34+A33+A22+A41+2^*A29+A50-A51-A9-A48-A49+A1-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-2^*A42$	A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	(R-L)/2	$(11^*L-9^*R)/2$
$8^*T-8^*L+S+A12+A32-A13-2^*A11-2^*M+A35-A23+A38+A39+A40+2^*A36+2^*A37+6^*A4+A10+2^*A31+A18-A20+A34+A33-A22-A41-2^*A29-A50+A51+A9+A48+A49-A1+A47+A46+A45+A44+A43+2^*A42$	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	$11^*L-8^*T-S-A12-A32+A13+2^*A11+2^*M-A35+A23-A38-A39-A40-2^*A36-2^*A37-6^*A4-A10-3^*R-2^*A31-A18+A20-A34-A33-A22-A41-2^*A29-A50+A51+A9+A48+A49-A1+A47+A46+A45+A44+A43+2^*A42$	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	R-L-A47	R-L-A48	R-L-A49	$(11^*L-9^*R)/2$	(R-L)/2

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 8 at the upper left corner. Magic square of order 10 is also a part of **cornered** magic square. This block of order 8 is a **reduced entries semi-magic** square, but the way it is constructed lead us to a magic square of order 12. The magic rectangles of orders 2×8 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents magic sums for the magic squares of orders 4, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums T, L and R should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Example 3.21. Let's consider following two examples:

8	mgc												200	8	mgc												271			
		-15	-109	-12	455	-13	-14	-16	-146	-9	49	70	-40	200			-14	-107	-11	448	-12	-13	-15	-145	-9	49	70	30	271	
		-7	6	8	19	112	7	-52	37	-10	50	71	-41	200			-6	6	8	19	112	7	-52	37	-10	50	71	29	271	
		-8	11	21	37	-21	23	29	38	244	-204	72	-42	200			-7	11	21	37	-21	23	29	38	244	-204	72	28	271	
		-9	10	26	24	25	-15	30	39	-11	51	73	-43	200			-8	10	26	24	25	-15	30	39	-11	51	73	27	271	
		-10	9	19	18	-7	30	31	40	-12	52	-516	546	200			-9	9	19	18	-7	30	31	40	-12	52	-166	266	271	
		-11	12	-6	-19	63	22	28	41	-13	53	74	-44	200			-10	12	-6	-19	63	22	28	41	-13	53	74	26	271	
		-6	52	32	21	-72	33	34	36	-14	54	75	-45	200			-5	52	32	21	-72	33	34	36	-14	54	75	25	271	
		196	139	42	-425	43	44	46	45	-15	55	76	-46	200			190	138	42	-417	43	44	46	45	-15	55	76	24	271	
		-16	-149	420	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	20	-10	77	-47	200			-16	-148	419	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	20	-9	77	23	271	
		56	189	-380	57	58	59	60	61	-10	20	78	-48	200			56	188	-379	57	58	59	60	61	-9	20	78	22	271	
		-545	62	63	64	171	65	66	67	68	69	15	35	200			-475	62	63	64	451	65	66	67	68	69	50	-279	271	
		575	-32	-33	-34	-141	-35	-36	-37	-38	-39	35	15	200			575	38	37	36	-351	35	34	33	32	31	-279	50	271	
		200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200			271	271	271	271	271	271	271	271	271	271	271	271	271	271

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 60$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 100$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 130$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 170$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 60$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 100$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 131$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 171$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 271$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. To avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums (T, L) and (L,R) are **even** numbers for **first example** and **odd** numbers for **second example**. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 8} = 40 \times 160$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 30 \times 150$$

Second Example

$$MR_{8 \times 8} = 40 \times 160$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 100 \times 500$$

Result 3.22. *Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:*

$10^*T+A43-9^*L$	$27^*L-2^*A43-28^*T-A42-A41-A40-A38-A37-A36-A34-A35-A32-A33-A29-A30-A31-A28-A39$	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	$A34+A35+A43+A32+A33+A29+A30+A31+A28+18^*T-17^*L$	A52	R-L-A52
A28-T	A18	A19	$2^*(T-S)/2-A15-A16-A17$	A15	A16	A17	$2^*S-T+A18-A19+A23$	$T-S-A23-2^*A18$	L-A28	A53	R-L-A53
A29	$2^*A13+A24+A14+2^*A18-2^*(T-S)/2-A19$	$T-S-2^*A18-A13$	$A15+A16+A17-(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A15$	$(T-S)/2-A16$	$(T-S)/2-A17$	$T-S-A23-A13-A24-A18+A19$	$2^*S-T+A18+A23-A14$	L-T-A29	A54	R-L-A54
A30	$2^*(T-S)/2-A7-A8-A9$	$A7+A8+A9-(T-S)/2$	A1	$A4+S-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	$A10+A11+A12-(T-S)/2$	$T-S-A10-A11-A12$	L-T-A30	A55	R-L-A55
A31	A7	$(T-S)/2-A7$	A6	A4	A5	S-A4-A5-A6	$(T-S)/2-A10$	A10	L-T-A31	$5^*(R-L)-A52-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57-A58-A59-A60$	$4^*(L-R)+A52+A53+A54+A55+A56+A57+A58+A59+A60$
A32	A8	$(T-S)/2-A8$	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	S-A1-A2-A4	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	$(T-S)/2-A11$	A11	L-T-A32	A56	R-L-A56
A33	A9	$(T-S)/2-A9$	S-A1-A2-A3	$A5-A2-2^*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2^*A4-A5-A6$	A2	$(T-S)/2-A12$	A12	L-T-A33	A57	R-L-A57
A34	$T-2^*A13-A14+A19-3^*A18-A23-A24$	$A23+3^*A18+A24-A19+A13-2^*(T-S)/2$	$A20+A21+A22-(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A20$	$(T-S)/2-A21$	$(T-S)/2-A22$	A13	A14	L-T-A34	A58	R-L-A58
A35	A23	S-A23-A18-A24	$T-S-A20-A21-A22$	A20	A21	A22	A24	A18	L-T-A35	A59	R-L-A59
$10^*L-9^*T-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A43$	$27^*T+2^*A43+A42+A41+A40+A38+A37+A36+A34+A35+A32+A33+A29+A30+A31+A28-26^*L+A39$	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	L-T-A41	L-T-A42	10^*L-11^*T-A43	A60	R-L-A60
A44	$A12+A11-T+A21+A36-3^*A4+2^*A10+3^*S+2^*A20-R+A22+A29+A52-A53-A1+A44$	A45	A46	$T-5^*L+6^*R-3^*S-A45-A49-A48-A47-A46-A50-A51+A1-2^*A44-A22-A52+A53-2^*A20-2^*A10-A21-A12-A11+3^*A4-A29-A36$	A47	A48	A49	A50	A51	$(R-L)/2$	$(11^*L-9^*R)/2$
R-L-A44	$2^*R-L-A12-A11+T-A21-A36+3^*A4-2^*A10-3^*S-2^*A20-A22-A29-A52+A53+A1-A44$	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	$4^*L-T-5^*R+3^*S+A45+A49+A48+A47+A46+A50+A51-A1+2^*A44+A22+A52-A53+2^*A20+2^*A10+A21+A12+A11-3^*A4+A29+A36$	R-L-A47	R-L-A48	R-L-A49	R-L-A50	R-L-A51	$(11^*L-9^*R)/2$	$(R-L)/2$

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper left corner containing **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 8. It contains in the middle a magic square of order 4. This block of order 10 is a **reduced entries semi-magic** square, but the way it is constructed lead us to a magic square of order 12. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters S, T, L and R represents magic sums for the magic squares of orders 4, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums (S,T) and (L,R) should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Example 3.22. Let's consider following two examples:

9	mgc												200	9	mgc												321
	69	-1053	85	87	89	91	93	95	97	517	117	-87	200		-210	-216	85	87	89	91	93	95	97	-10	117	3	321
	-81	49	51	-55	43	45	47	47	-77	101	119	-89	200		-81	49	51	-55	43	45	47	47	-77	132	119	1	321
	71	147	-57	95	-3	-5	-7	-77	57	-51	121	-91	200		71	147	-57	95	-3	-5	-7	-77	57	-20	121	-1	321
	73	-7	47	15	51	-15	19	65	-25	-53	123	-93	200		73	-7	47	15	51	-15	19	65	-25	-22	123	-3	321
	75	27	13	25	21	23	1	7	33	-55	-975	1005	200		75	27	13	25	21	23	1	7	33	-24	-525	645	321
	77	29	11	11	9	17	33	5	35	-57	125	-95	200		77	29	11	11	9	17	33	5	35	-26	125	-5	321
	79	31	9	19	-11	45	17	3	37	-59	127	-97	200		79	31	9	19	-11	45	17	3	37	-28	127	-7	321
	81	-185	175	125	-13	-15	-17	39	41	-61	129	-99	200		81	-185	175	125	-13	-15	-17	39	41	-30	129	-9	321
	83	59	-99	-85	53	55	57	61	49	-63	131	-101	200		83	59	-99	-85	53	55	57	61	49	-32	131	-11	321
	-357	1073	-65	-67	-69	-71	-73	-75	-77	-49	133	-103	200		-47	267	-34	-36	-38	-40	-42	-44	-46	261	133	-13	321
	101	393	103	105	-1107	107	109	111	113	115	15	35	200		101	272	103	105	-536	107	109	111	113	115	60	-339	321
	-71	-363	-73	-75	1137	-77	-79	-81	-83	-85	35	15	200		19	-152	17	15	656	13	11	9	7	5	-339	60	321
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 70$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 150$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 170$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 70$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 150$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 201$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 321$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. To avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums (L, R) are **even** numbers for **first example** and **odd** numbers for **second example**. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 40 \times 80$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 30 \times 150$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 40 \times 80$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 120 \times 600$$

Result 3.23. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

10*T-9*L	27*L-28*T-A36-A35-A34-A32-A31-A30-A28-A29-A26-A27-A23-A24-A25-A22-A33	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	18*T-17*L+A28+A29+A26+A27+A23+A24+A25+A22	A46	R-L-A46
A22-T	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	S-M-A10	A10	T-S-A17	A17	L-A22	A47	R-L-A47
A23	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A10+A11+A12-S+M	2*S-2*M-A10-A11-A12	T-4*S-A17+A1+2*M+2*A9+2*A8+3*A4	A17-A1-2*M+3*S-2*A9-2*A8-3*A4	L-T-A23	A48	R-L-A48
A24	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	S-M-A11	A11	2*A17+A19+A20-A1-2*M+5*S-2*T-2*A9-2*A8-3*A4+A18	3*T-6*S-A19-A20-2*A17+A1+2*M+2*A9+2*A8+3*A4-A18	L-T-A24	A49	R-L-A49
A25	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6	A2	S-M-A12	A12	T-S-A18	A18	L-T-A25	5*(R-L)-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54	4*(L-R)+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54
A26	S-M-A8	2*S-A8-A1-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-M	2*A8+A1+A9+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12+M-2*S	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	(5*M-3*S)/2	T-S-A19	A19	L-T-A26	A50	R-L-A50
A27	A8	A8+A1+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12-S	3*S-2*A8-A1-A9-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-2*M	A9	(5*M-3*S)/2	(S-M)/2	T-S-A20	A20	L-T-A27	A51	R-L-A51
A28	T+2*S-3*M-2*A9-2*A8	2*A10+2*A12-M+2*S-2*A9-2*A8	A16-4*S+4*M-T+4*A9+4*A8+A15+A14-2*A12-2*A10	T-S-A14	T-S-A15	T-S-A16	(T-S)/2	(7*S-5*T)/2	L-T-A28	A52	R-L-A52
a43	2*A9+2*A8-3*S+3*M	2*A9+2*A8+M+T-3*S-2*A10-2*A12	2*T+3*S-A15-A14-4*M-4*A9-4*A8+2*A12+2*A10-A16	A14	A15	A16	(7*S-5*T)/2	(T-S)/2	L-T-A29	A53	R-L-A53
10*L-9*T-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29	27*T+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31+A30+A28+A29+A26+A27+A23+A24+A25+A22-26*L	L-T-A30	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	10*L-11*T	A54	R-L-A54
A38	A19+A15+A16-2*A12+2*A17+8*S-3*M+2*A14-5*T+A23-R-3*A4-2*A10+2*A18+A20+A30+A46-A47+2*A8+2*A9-A1+A38	A39	A40	2*A12-A19-A15-A16-2*A17-8*S+3*M-2*A14+5*T-A23+6*R-5*L+3*A4+2*A10-2*A18-A20-A30-A46+A47-2*A8-2*A9-A44-A45+A1-A43-A42-A41-A40-A39-2*A38	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	(R-L)/2	(11*L-9*R)/2
R-L-A38	2*R-L-A19-A15-A16+2*A12-2*A17-8*S+3*M-2*A14+5*T-A23+3*A4+2*A10-2*A18-A20-A30-A46+A47-2*A8-2*A9+A1-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	A19+A15+A16-2*A12+2*A17+8*S-3*M+2*A14-5*T+A23-5*R+4*L-3*A4-2*A10+2*A18+A20+A30+A46-A47+2*A8+2*A9+A44+A45-A1+A43+A42+A41+A40+A39+2*A38	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	(11*L-9*R)/2	(R-L)/2

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper left corner containing **cornered** magic square of order 8. This **cornered** magic square of order 8 contains magic square of order 4 and 6. This block of order 10 is a **reduced entries semi-magic** square, but the way it is constructed lead us to a magic square of order 12. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 , 2×6 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents magic sums for the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums M, S, T, L and R should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Example 3.23. Let's consider following two examples:

10	mgc												200	10	mgc												241			
		-40	-665	73	75	77	79	81	83	85	312	105	-65	200			-49	-638	73	75	77	79	81	83	85	295	105	-25	241	
		-83	15	51	-15	19	7	33	-17	47	103	107	-67	200			-83	15	51	-15	19	7	33	-17	47	104	107	-27	241	
		59	25	21	23	1	65	-25	-9	39	-39	109	-69	200			59	25	21	23	1	65	-25	-9	39	-38	109	-29	241	
		61	11	9	17	33	5	35	179	-149	-41	111	-71	200			61	11	9	17	33	5	35	179	-149	-40	111	-31	241	
		63	19	-11	45	17	3	37	-19	49	-43	-817	857	200			63	19	-11	45	17	3	37	-19	49	-42	-617	697	241	
		65	11	-95	155	9	20	10	-21	51	-45	113	-73	200			65	11	-95	155	9	20	10	-21	51	-44	113	-33	241	
		67	29	135	-115	31	10	20	-23	53	-47	115	-75	200			67	29	135	-115	31	10	20	-23	53	-46	115	-35	241	
		69	30	170	-71	-11	-13	-15	15	35	-49	117	-77	200			69	30	170	-71	-11	-13	-15	15	35	-48	117	-37	241	
		71	0	-140	101	41	43	45	35	15	-51	119	-79	200			71	0	-140	101	41	43	45	35	15	-50	119	-39	241	
		-172	685	-53	-55	-57	-59	-61	-63	-65	60	121	-81	200			-162	659	-52	-54	-56	-58	-60	-62	-64	70	121	-41	241	
		89	357	91	93	-925	95	97	99	101	103	20	-20	200			89	316	91	93	-684	95	97	99	101	103	40	-199	241	
		-49	-317	-51	-53	965	-55	-57	-59	-61	-63	-20	20	200			-9	-236	-11	-13	764	-15	-17	-19	-21	-23	-199	40	241	
		200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200			241	241	241	241	241	241	241	241	241	241	241	241	241	241

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 70$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 110$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 140$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 160$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 70$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 110$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 140$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 161$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 241$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. To avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums (L, R) are **even** numbers for **first example** and **odd** numbers for **second example**. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 40 \times 80$$

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 30 \times 90$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 40 \times 200$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 40 \times 80$$

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 30 \times 90$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 80 \times 400$$

Result 3.24. *Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:*

$10^*4^*m-9^*L$	$27^*L-28^*4^*m-A27-A26-A25-A23-A22-A21-A19-A20-A17-A18-A14-A15-A16-A13-A24$	a21	a22	a23	a24	a25	a26	a27	$A19+A20+A17+A18+A14+A15+A16+A13+18^*4^*m-17^*L$	A37	R-L-A37
$A13-4^*m$	$A1-A3-A5-A6-A8+A7$	$A6+A8-2^*m+A11+A1-A3-A5$	2^*m	$2^*m+2^*A3+2^*A5-A7-A11-2^*A1$	$A5+2^*A3-A7-A11+A10-A9$	$2^*m-A9-A5-A10$	$A9-2^*A3+A7+A11$	A9	L-A13	A38	R-L-A38
A14	$m+A3+A5+A6+A8-A7-A1$	$3^*m+A3+A5-A6-A8-A11-A1$	(-m)	$A7-m+A11+2^*A1-2^*A3-2^*A5$	$m+A9-A10+A11-A5-2^*A3+A7$	$A9+A5+A10-m$	$m-A9+2^*A3-A7-A11$	m-A9	L-4^*m-A14	A39	R-L-A39
A15	$2^*A3+2^*A5-A7-A11-A1$	A1	$A6+A8+A11-A3-A5$	$2^*m+A7-A3-A5-A6-A8$	$A5+2^*A3-A7-A11$	A5	$2^*m+A7+A11-A10-2^*A3-2^*A5$	A10	L-4^*m-A15	A40	R-L-A40
A16	$A1+m-2^*A3-2^*A5+A7+A11$	m-A1	$m+A3+A5-A6-A8-A11$	$A3+A5+A6+A8-A7-m$	$m+A7+A11-A5-2^*A3$	m-A5	$2^*A3+2^*A5-A7-A11+A10-m$	m-A10	L-4^*m-A16	A41	R-L-A41
A17	$A3+A2-A7-A11+A4$	$2^*m-A3-A2-A4$	$A7+A11-A3$	A3	$2^*m-A6-A8-A11$	$A6+A8-A7$	A7	A11	L-4^*m-A17	A42	R-L-A42
A18	$m+A7+A11-A4-A3-A2$	$A3+A2+A4-m$	$m+A3-A7-A11$	m-A3	$A6+A8+A11-m$	$m+A7-A6-A8$	m-A7	m-A11	L-4^*m-A18	A43	R-L-A43
A19	$A2+2^*A3-A7-A11$	A2	$2^*m+A7+A11-2^*A2-A4-2^*A3$	A4	$A6+A11-A7$	A6	A8	$2^*m+A7-2^*A6-A8-A11$	L-4^*m-A19	A44	R-L-A44
A20	$m+A7+A11-A2-2^*A3$	m-A2	$2^*A3-A7-A11+2^*A2+A4-m$	m-A4	$m+A7-A11-A6$	m-A6	m-A8	$2^*A6+A8+A11-A7-m$	L-4^*m-A20	A45	R-L-A45
$10^*L-9^*4^*m-A13-A14-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19-A20$	$27^*4^*m+A27+A26+A25+A23+A22+A21+A19+A20+A17+A18+A14+A15+A16+A13-26^*L+A24$	L-4^*m-A21	L-4^*m-A22	L-4^*m-A23	L-4^*m-A24	L-4^*m-A25	L-4^*m-A26	L-4^*m-A27	$10^*L-11^*4^*m$	$5^*(R-L)-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45$	$4^*(L-R)+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45$
$2^*A2+2^*A4-3^*m+2^*A6+2^*A8+2^*A5-3^*A7+2^*A10+4^*A3-2^*4^*m-A14+A29-A11+R-A37+A38-A21$	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	$A21-2^*A2-2^*A4+3^*m-2^*A6-2^*A8-2^*A5+3^*A7+A11-2^*A10-4^*A3+2^*4^*m+A14-A34-A35-A36-A31-A32-A33-A30-2^*A29+4^*R-5^*L+A37-A38$	(R-L)/2	$(11^*L-9^*R)/2$
$A21-2^*A2-2^*A4+3^*m-2^*A6-2^*A8-2^*A5+3^*A7-2^*A10-4^*A3+2^*4^*m+A14-A29+A11+A37-A38-L$	R-L-A29	R-L-A30	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	$2^*A2+2^*A4-3^*m+2^*A6+2^*A8+2^*A5-3^*A7-A11+2^*A10+4^*A3-2^*4^*m-A14+A34+A35+A36+A31+A32+A33+A30+2^*A29-3^*R+4^*L-A37+A38-A21$	$(11^*L-9^*R)/2$	(R-L)/2

Details:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper-left corner. Order 10 magic square is embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 formed by equal sum stripes of order 2×4 . The block of order 10 may be a **semi-magic** square but still we can get order 12 as a magic square. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters T, L and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums of the pair (L, R) should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd**. See below two examples.

Example 3.24. Let's consider following two examples:

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											250	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT											275	
-330	765	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	-510	48	32	250	-375	900	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	-595	48	52	275	
-96	-34	-22	60	56	4	6	31	19	146	49	31	250	-96	-34	-22	60	56	4	6	31	19	151	49	51	275	
25	64	52	-30	-26	26	24	-1	11	25	50	30	250	25	64	52	-30	-26	26	24	-1	11	30	50	50	275	
26	7	11	27	15	3	15	22	20	24	51	29	250	26	7	11	27	15	3	15	22	20	29	51	49	275	
27	23	19	3	15	27	15	8	10	23	52	28	250	27	23	19	3	15	27	15	8	10	28	52	48	275	
28	1	21	25	13	5	17	17	21	22	53	27	250	28	1	21	25	13	5	17	17	21	27	53	47	275	
29	29	9	5	17	25	13	13	9	21	54	26	250	29	29	9	5	17	25	13	13	9	26	54	46	275	
30	0	12	34	14	20	16	18	6	20	55	25	250	30	0	12	34	14	20	16	18	6	25	55	45	275	
31	30	18	-4	16	10	14	12	24	19	56	24	250	31	30	18	-4	16	10	14	12	24	24	56	44	275	
400	-715	18	17	16	15	14	13	12	380	-68	148	250	450	-845	23	22	21	20	19	18	17	430	32	68	275	
74	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	-22	40	-190	250	99	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	53	50	-275	275	
6	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	102	-190	40	250	1	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	47	-275	50	275	
23a	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	23b	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275

The magic sums of above two magic squares are as follows:

First Example

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 120$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 170$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 250$$

Second Example

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 120$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 175$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 275$$

The magic rectangles sums are given by

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 80 \times 400$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 100 \times 500.$$

Result 3.25. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

$20^*S+A35-9^*L$	$27^*L-2^*A35-56^*S-A34-A33-A32-A30-A29-A28-A26-A27-A24-A25-A21-A22-A23-A20-A31$	A28	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	$A35+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21+A20+18^*2^*S-17^*L$	A44	R-L-A44
A20-2*S	$2^*S-2^*A4-2^*A7-A12+A3+A6$	$3^*A4+3^*A7-A15-A2+A12-A3-A6-2^*S$	$A2+A14-A16-4^*A4-4^*A7+A3+A6-A1+4^*S+A15$	$A16+3^*A4-3^*S+3^*A7-A3-A6+A1-A14$	A3	$2^*S-A9-A4-A7-A5-A3$	$A5+A8-A16+A3+A6-A1+A9$	$A16+A4+A7-A3-A6+A1-A8-S$	L-A20	A45	R-L-A45
A21	A2	$A4+A7-A15-S$	A1	$2^*S-A4-A7+A15-A1-A2$	A5	$S-A9-A4-A7$	$A16+2^*A4-2^*S+2^*A7+A1-A10$	$A9-A4-A7+2^*S-A16-A1+A10-A5$	L-2*S-A21	A46	R-L-A46
A22	$2^*A4+2^*A7-A13-S-A14+A16-A3-A6+A1-A2$	$4^*S-3^*A4-3^*A7-A12+A3+A6-A13-A1$	$2^*A4+2^*A7+A12-A3-A6+A13+A15-2^*S$	$A2+A13+A14-A16-A4-A7+A3+A6-A15$	$2^*A4-S-A8+A16+A7-A3-A6+A1-A5$	$A3-A4+2^*S-A16-2^*A7-A1+A10$	$A9+A7-A3$	$A8+A3+A6-A10+A5-A9-A4$	L-2*S-A22	A47	R-L-A47
A23	$A12+A13+A14-A16-A1$	$A1-A4-A7+A13+2^*A15+A2$	$2^*A4+2^*A7-A12-A13-A14-S+A16-2^*A15-A2$	$2^*S-A4-A7-A13$	$2^*S-2^*A4+A8-A16-A7+A6-A1$	$A16+3^*A4-4^*S+4^*A7+A1+2^*A9+A5-A10$	$3^*S-A8-3^*A7-A6-2^*A9+A10-A5-2^*A4$	A4	L-2*S-A23	A48	R-L-A48
A24	A6	$A9+S-A11-A6$	$A11-A8-A9$	A8	A12	$A15+S-A17-A12$	$A17-A14-A15$	A14	L-2*S-A24	A49	R-L-A49
A25	A11	A9	A10	$S-A9-A10-A11$	A17	A15	A16	$S-A15-A16-A17$	L-2*S-A25	A50	R-L-A50
A26	$A7+A8-A11$	$A6+A7-A10$	$S-A6-A7-A9$	$A9+A10+A11-A7-A8$	$A13+A14-A17$	$A12+A13-A16$	$S-A12-A13-A15$	$A15+A16+A17-A13-A14$	L-2*S-A26	A51	R-L-A51
A27	$S-A6-A7-A8$	$A10-A7-2^*A9+A11$	$A6+A7+A8+2^*A9-A10-A11$	A7	$S-A12-A13-A14$	$A16-A13-2^*A15+A17$	$A12+A13+A14+2^*A15-A16-A17$	A13	L-2*S-A27	A52	R-L-A52
$10^*L-18^*S-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A35$	$54^*S+2^*A35+A34+A33+A32+A30+A29+A28+A26+A27+A24+A25+A21+A22+A23+A20-26^*L+A31$	L-2*S-A28	L-2*S-A29	L-2*S-A30	L-2*S-A31	L-2*S-A32	L-2*S-A33	L-2*S-A34	$10^*L-11^*2^*S-A35$	$5^*(R-L)-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52$	$4^*(L-R)+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52$
$A36-A28+A15-3^*A7-3^*A4+A6-A21+A3-A44+A45+R-A12$	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	$4^*R-5^*L+A12-2^*A36+A28-A15+3^*A7+3^*A4-A6+A21-A3+A44-A45-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43$	(R-L)/2	$(11^*L-9^*R)/2$
$A12-A36+A28-A15+3^*A7+3^*A4-A6+A21-A3+A44-A45-L$	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	$4^*L-3^*R-A12+2^*A36-A28+A15-3^*A7-3^*A4+A6-A21-A3-A44+A45+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43$	$(11^*L-9^*R)/2$	(R-L)/2

Details:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper-left corner. Order 10 magic square is embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 formed by four equal sum **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. The block of order 10 may be a **semi-magic** square but still we can get order 12 as a magic square. The magic rectangles of order 2×10 are of equal width and length. The letters T, L and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums of the pair (L, R) should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd**. See below two examples.

Example 3.25. Let's consider following two examples:

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												260	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												285
-305	605	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	-437	54	56	260	-710	1820	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	-1202	54	36	285		
-70	45	-51	129	-73	13	22	44	-29	120	55	55	260	-70	45	-51	129	-73	13	22	44	-29	165	55	35	285		
31	12	-44	11	71	15	0	-21	56	19	56	54	260	31	12	-44	11	71	15	0	-21	56	64	56	34	285		
32	-39	80	3	6	-30	48	23	9	18	57	53	260	32	-39	80	3	6	-30	48	23	9	63	57	33	285		
33	32	65	-93	46	52	-20	4	14	17	58	52	260	33	32	65	-93	46	52	-20	4	14	62	58	32	285		
34	16	32	-16	18	22	26	-22	24	16	59	51	260	34	16	32	-16	18	22	26	-22	24	61	59	31	285		
35	21	19	20	-10	27	25	26	-28	15	60	50	260	35	21	19	20	-10	27	25	26	-28	60	60	30	285		
36	14	13	-2	25	20	19	-20	31	14	61	49	260	36	14	13	-2	25	20	19	-20	31	59	61	29	285		
37	-1	-14	48	17	-19	-20	66	23	13	62	48	260	37	-1	-14	48	17	-19	-20	66	23	58	62	28	285		
287	-555	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	355	28	82	260	737	-1725	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	805	-72	162	285		
177	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	-23	55	-345	260	202	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	-148	45	-210	285		
-67	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	133	-345	55	260	-112	44	43	42	41	40	39	38	37	238	-210	45	285		
24a	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	24b	285	285	285	285	285	285	285	285	285	285	285	285		

The magic sums of above two magic squares are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 50$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 100$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 150$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 260$$

Second Example

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 50$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 100$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 195$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 285$$

The magic rectangles sums are given by

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 110 \times 550$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 90 \times 450.$$

Result 3.26. *Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:*

10*T-9*L	27*L-28*T-A49-A48-A47-A45-A44-A43-A41-A42-A39-A40-A36-A37-A38-A35-A46	A43	A44	A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	A41+A42+A39+A40+A36+A37+A38+A35+18*T-17*L	A59	R-L-A59
A35-T	A19+A20+A21+A22+A23-A4-A7-A11-A15	A4	A7	A11	A15	S-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23	T-S-A29	A29	L-A35	A60	R-L-A60
A36	S-A12-A5-A8-A16-A19	A5	A8	A12	A16	A19	T-S-A30	A30	L-T-A36	A61	R-L-A61
A37	A4+A7+A11+A15-A20-A21-A22-A23-A1-A2-A3+A5+A8+A12+A16	S-A4-A5-A12+A21+A22+A23-A17-A7-A8-A15-A16-A13-A9-A11+A1+A2+A3	A9	A13	A17	A20	T-S-A31	A31	L-T-A37	A62	R-L-A62
A38	A1	S+A16+A13+A6-A19+A3-A1-A18-A14-2*A21-A22-A23-A20	A21+A22+A23+A20-A16-A13-A6+A19-A3	A14	A18	A21	T-S-A32	A32	L-T-A38	A63	R-L-A63
A39	A2	S+A16+A13-A9+A6-A19+A3-A10-A21-A22-A23-A20-A7-A8	S+A16+A13-A9+A6-A19+A3-A10-A21-A22-A23-A20-A7-A8	A5+A14+A10+2*A21+A22+3*A23+2*A20-A4+A8-A15-A16-A13+2*A9-2*A6+2*A19-A11-A2-A3-S	S-A19-A20-A21-A22-2*A23+A4+A7+A11+A15-A5-A9-A14	A22	T-S-A33	A33	L-T-A39	A64	R-L-A64
A40	A3	A12+A18+A14+A21+A20+A17+A7+A8+A15+A9-2*A6+A19+A11-A2-2*A3-S	A10	2*S+A4-A8+A15+A16-2*A9+2*A6-2*A19+A2+A3-A12-A5-2*A14-A10-2*A21-A22-3*A23-2*A20	A19+A20+A21+A22+2*A23-A4-A7-A11+A5+A9+A14-2*A15-A16-A17-A18	A23	2*S-2*T+A29+A30+A31+A32+A33	3*T-3*S-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33	L-T-A40	A65	R-L-A65
A41	T-S-A25	A30-A29-2*A9+A13-A25+2*S-2*A21-A22-3*A23-A18-2*A19-3*A20-A14+A15+A16-2*A10+A2+A4+A11-A5+2*A6-A8+A3	T-S-A26	T-S-A27	T-S-A28	2*A25+A28+A27+A26-A30+A29+2*A9-A13-T-S+2*A21+A22+3*A23+A18+2*A19+3*A20+A14-A15-A16+2*A10-A2-A4-A11+A5-2*A6+A8-A3	(T-S)/2	(7*S-5*T)/2	L-T-A41	A66	R-L-A66
A42	A25	A29-A30+2*A9-A13+T+A25-A11-3*S+2*A21+A22+3*A23+A18+2*A19+3*A20+A14-A15-A16+2*A10-A2-A4+A5-2*A6+A8-A3	A26	A27	A28	A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-2*A9+A13+2*T-2*A25-2*A21-A22-3*A23-A18-2*A19-3*A20-A14+A15+A16-2*A10+A2+A4+A11-A5+2*A6-A8+A3	(7*S-5*T)/2	(T-S)/2	L-T-A42	A67	R-L-A67
10*L-9*T-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42	27*T+A49+A48+A47+A45+A44+A43+A41+A42+A39+A40+A36+A37+A38+A35-26*L+A46	L-T-A43	L-T-A44	L-T-A45	L-T-A46	L-T-A47	L-T-A48	L-T-A49	10*L-11*T	5*(R-L)-A59-A60-A61-A62-A63-A64-A65-A66-A67	4*(L-R)+A59+A60+A61+A62+A63+A64+A65+A66+A67
A51-A27+A26-A17-A18+A14-A16+A9+2*A23+A19+A20+A21-2*S+A60+R-A59+2*A22-A4+A5-A7-A11-2*A15-A36-A32+A31-A43	A51	A52	A53	A54	A55	A56	A57	A58	A43-2*A51+A27-A26+A17+A18-A14+A16-A9-2*A23-A19-A20-A21+2*S-A60+4*R+A59-A55-A56-A57-A58-5*L-2*A22+A4-A5+A7+A11+2*A15+A36+A32-A31-A52-A53-A54	(R-L)/2	(11*L-9*R)/2
A43-A51+A27-A26+A17+A18-A14+A16-A9-2*A23-A19-A20-A21+2*S-A60+A59-L-2*A22+A4-A5+A7+A11+2*A15+A36+A32-A31	R-L-A51	R-L-A52	R-L-A53	R-L-A54	R-L-A55	R-L-A56	R-L-A57	R-L-A58	A52+A53+A54-A43+2*A51-A27+A26-A17-A18+A14-A16+A9+2*A23+A19+A20-A21-2*S+A60-3*R-A59+A55+A56+A57+A58+4*L+2*A22-A4+A5-A7-A11-2*A15-A36-A32+A31	(11*L-9*R)/2	(R-L)/2

Details:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper-left corner. Order 10 magic square is embedded with a cornered magic square of order 8 having order 6 magic square at the upper-left corner. The block of order 10 may be a **semi-magic** square but still we can get order 12 as a magic square. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums of the pairs (S, T) and (L, R) should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd**. See below two examples.

Example 3.26. Let's consider following two examples:

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											270	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT											275
-230	170	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	-162	69	31	270	-275	305	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	-247	69	31	275
-85	78	14	17	21	25	-65	1	39	125	70	30	270	-85	78	14	17	21	25	-65	1	39	130	70	30	275
46	-20	15	18	22	26	29	0	40	-6	71	29	270	46	-20	15	18	22	26	29	0	40	-1	71	29	275
47	-4	-5	19	23	27	30	-1	41	-7	72	28	270	47	-4	-5	19	23	27	30	-1	41	-2	72	28	275
48	11	-81	77	24	28	31	-2	42	-8	73	27	270	48	11	-81	77	24	28	31	-2	42	-3	73	27	275
49	12	16	-61	170	-79	32	-3	43	-9	74	26	270	49	12	16	-61	170	-79	32	-3	43	-4	74	26	275
50	13	131	20	-170	63	33	125	-85	-10	75	25	270	50	13	131	20	-170	63	33	125	-85	-5	75	25	275
51	5	-192	4	3	2	298	20	-10	-11	76	24	270	51	5	-192	4	3	2	298	20	-10	-6	76	24	275
52	35	232	36	37	38	-258	-10	20	-12	77	23	270	52	35	232	36	37	38	-258	-10	20	-7	77	23	275
142	-130	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	270	-157	257	270	192	-260	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	320	-157	257	275
146	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	-162	50	-280	270	151	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	-167	50	-275	275
-46	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	32	262	-280	50	270	-51	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	32	267	-275	50	275
25a	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	25b	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275

The magic sums of above two magic squares are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 90$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 130$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 170$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 270$$

Second Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 90$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 130$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 175$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 275$$

The magic rectangles sums are given by

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 40 \times 120$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 100 \times 500$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 40 \times 120$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 100 \times 500.$$

Result 3.27. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

10*T-9*L	27*L-28*T-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A21+A22+A23+A24+A25+A26+A27+A28+18*T-17*L	A45	R-L-A45
A21-T	2*M/3-A6	A6+A7-M/3	2*M/3-A7	2*M/3-A2	A2+A3-M/3	2*M/3-A3	T-2*M-A15	A15	L-A21	A46	R-L-A46
A22	A6+A8-M/3	M+A1-A6-A7-A8	M/3+A7-A1	A2+A4-M/3	5*M/3-A3-A2-A4-A5	A3+A5-M/3	T-2*M-A16	A16	L-T-A22	A47	R-L-A47
A23	2*M/3-A8	M/3+A8-A1	A1	2*M/3-A4	A4+A5-M/3	2*M/3-A5	T-2*M-A17	A17	L-T-A23	A48	R-L-A48
A24	A2	M-A2-A3	A3	A6	M-A6-A7	A7	T-2*M-A18	A18	L-T-A24	A49	R-L-A49
A25	M-A2-A4	A2+A3+A4+A5-M	M-A3-A5	M-A6-A8	A6+A7+A8-A1-M/3	M/3-A7+A1	T-2*M-A19	A19	L-T-A25	A50	R-L-A50
A26	A4	M-A4-A5	A5	A8	M/3-A8+A1	2*M/3-A1	4*M-2*T+A15+A16+A17+A18+A19	3*T-6*M-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19	L-T-A26	A51	R-L-A51
A27	2*T-10*M/3-A10+A15-A16-2*A6-A7-A8	T-2*M-A10	T-2*M-A11	T-2*M-A12	T-2*M-A13	16*M/3-3*T+2*A10-A15+A16+2*A6+A7+A8+A11+A12+A13	(T-2*M)/2	(14*M-5*T)/2	L-T-A27	A52	R-L-A52
A28	A10-A15-T+4*M/3+A16+2*A6+A7+A8	A10	A11	A12	A13	4*T-22*M/3-2*A10+A15-A16-2*A6-A7-A8-A11-A12-A13	(14*M-5*T)/2	(T-2*M)/2	L-T-A28	A53	R-L-A53
10*L-9*T-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28	A21+27*T+A35+A25+A26+A27+A22+A23+A24+A31+A32+A33+A28+A29+A30-26*L+A34	L-T-A29	L-T-A30	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	10*L-11*T	5*(R-L)-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53	4*(L-R)+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52+A53
A11-A8-A7-(10/3)*M+A17+A37-A12-A22-A29-A18+R+2*A1+A46-A45	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	4*R-5*L-A11+A8+A7+(10/3)*M-A17-2*A37+A12+A22+A29+A18-2*A1-A46+A45-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44	(R-L)/2	(11*L-9*R)/2
A8+A7+(10/3)*M-A17-A37+A12+A22+A29+A18-2*A1-A46+A45-L-A11	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	4*L-3*R+A11-A8-A7-(10/3)*M+A17+2*A37-A12-A22-A29-A18+2*A1+A46-A45+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44	(11*L-9*R)/2	(R-L)/2

Details:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper-left corner. Order 10 magic square is embedded again with a **cornered** magic square of order 8 having order 6 magic square at the middle. This order 6 magic square is again composed of four equal sums magic squares of order 3. The block of order 10 may be a **semi-magic** square but still we can get order 12 as a magic square. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and 2×10 are of equal width and length of the same type. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 3, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums of the pair (S, T) and (L, R) should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd**. See below two examples.

Example 3.27. Let's consider following two examples:

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												330	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												321
-230	5	77	79	81	83	85	87	89	-86	109	-49	330	-275	140	77	79	81	83	85	87	89	-171	109	-63	321		
-159	29	34	27	37	18	35	-9	49	209	111	-51	330	-159	29	34	27	37	18	35	-9	49	214	111	-65	321		
63	36	12	42	20	46	24	-11	51	-13	113	-53	330	63	36	12	42	20	46	24	-11	51	-8	113	-67	321		
65	25	44	21	33	26	31	-13	53	-15	115	-55	330	65	25	44	21	33	26	31	-13	53	-10	115	-69	321		
67	23	42	25	31	26	33	-15	55	-17	117	-57	330	67	23	42	25	31	26	33	-15	55	-12	117	-71	321		
69	40	14	36	24	48	18	-17	57	-19	119	-59	330	69	40	14	36	24	48	18	-17	57	-14	119	-73	321		
71	27	34	29	35	16	39	185	-145	-21	121	-61	330	71	27	34	29	35	16	39	185	-145	-16	121	-75	321		
73	-31	1	-1	-3	-5	159	20	80	-23	123	-63	330	73	-31	1	-1	-3	-5	159	20	80	-18	123	-77	321		
75	71	39	41	43	45	-119	80	20	-25	125	-65	330	75	71	39	41	43	45	-119	80	20	-20	125	-79	321		
176	45	-27	-29	-31	-33	-35	-37	-39	280	-753	813	330	226	-85	-22	-24	-26	-28	-30	-32	-34	330	-823	869	321		
-45	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	-455	30	0	330	-54	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	-516	23	68	321		
105	-33	-35	-37	-39	-41	-43	-45	-47	515	0	30	330	100	-47	-49	-51	-53	-55	-57	-59	-61	562	68	23	321		
29a	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	29b	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321		

The magic sums of above two magic squares are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 180$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 220$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 270$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 330$$

Second Example

$$S_{3 \times 3} = 90$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 180$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 220$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 275$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 321$$

The magic rectangles sums are given by

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 40 \times 100$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 60 \times 300$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 90 \times 270$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 46 \times 230.$$

Result 3.28. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

10*T-9*L	27*L-28*T-A37-A36-A35-A33-A32-A31-A29-A30-A27-A28-A24-A25-A26-A23-A34	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	18*T-17*L+A29+A30+A27+A28+A24+A25+A26+A23	A47	R-L-A47
A23-T	4*S-6*M+A11	S+2*A12+2*A13-4*A11-M	2*A11+9*M-6*S-A12-A13	S-A12-M	S-A13-M	A11	T-S-A15	A15	L-A23	A48	R-L-A48
A24	4*M-3*S+A8+A9+A10	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	4*S-A8-A9-A10-5*M	T-8*S-A15-A1-A12-A8-A13+2*A11-3*A4+10*M	A15+A1+A12+A8+A13-2*A11+7*S+3*A4-10*M	L-T-A24	A49	R-L-A49
A25	S-A8-M	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A8	2*A15+A17+A18+A1-2*T+9*S+A12+A8+A13-2*A11+3*A4-10*M+A16	3*T-10*S-A17-A18-2*A15-A1-A12-A8-A13+2*A11-3*A4+10*M-A16	L-T-A25	A50	R-L-A50
A26	S-A9-M	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	A9	T-S-A16	A16	L-T-A26	5*(R-L)-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55	4*(L-R)+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54+A55
A27	S-A10-M	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6	A2	A10	T-S-A17	A17	L-T-A27	A51	R-L-A51
A28	5*M-A11-3*S	4*A11-2*A12-2*A13	7*S+A12+A13-2*A11-10*M	A12	A13	5*M-A11-3*S	T-S-A18	A18	L-T-A28	A52	R-L-A52
A29	T-S+A12+A8+A13-2*A11+2*A1+7*S+6*A4-11*M	8*S+A12+A8+A13-2*A11+2*A1+6*A4-11*M	A20+A19+A21-T-2*A12-2*A8-2*A13+4*A11-4*A1-14*S-12*A4+22*M	T-S-A19	T-S-A20	T-S-A21	(T-S)/2	(7*S-5*T)/2	L-T-A29	A53	R-L-A53
A30	11*M-A12-A8-A13+2*A11-2*A1-7*S-6*A4	T-9*S-A12-A8-A13+2*A11-2*A1-6*A4+11*M	2*T+13*S+2*A12+2*A8+2*A13-4*A11+4*A1+12*A4-22*M-A20-A19-A21	A19	A20	A21	(7*S-5*T)/2	(T-S)/2	L-T-A30	A54	R-L-A54
10*L-9*T-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30	27*T+A37+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31+A29+A30+A27+A28+A24+A25+A26+A23-26*L	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	10*L-11*T	A55	R-L-A55
A39	2*A19+2*A15+A24+2*A16-A12+A17-2*A13+2*A11+12*M-S+A21-9*A4+A31+A18+A20-5*T-R+A47-A48-A8-3*A1-A10+A39	A40	A41	A12-2*A19-2*A15-A24-2*A16-A17+2*A13-2*A11-12*M+S-A21-5*L+9*A4+A10-A31-A18-A20+5*T+6*R-A47+A48+A8-A45-A46+3*A1-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40-2*A39	A42	A43	A44	A45	A46	(R-L)/2	(11*L-9*R)/2
R-L-A39	A12-2*A19-2*A15-A24-2*A16-A17+2*A13-2*A11-12*M+S-A21-L+9*A4+A10-A31-A18-A20+5*T+2*R-A47+A48+A8+3*A1-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	2*A19+2*A15+A24+2*A16-A12+A17-2*A13+2*A11+12*M-S+A21+4*L-9*A4-A10+A31+A18+A20-5*T-5*R+A47-A48-A8+A45+A46-3*A1+A44+A43+A42+A41+A40+2*A39	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	(11*L-9*R)/2	(R-L)/2

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper left corner containing **cornered** magic square of order 8. This **cornered** magic square of order 8 again contains a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 6 with a magic square of order 4. The blocks of orders 6 and 10 are **reduced entries semi-magic** squares, but the way they are constructed lead us to a magic square of order 12. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents magic sums for the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums (S, T) and (L, R) should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Example 3.28. Let's consider following two examples:

11	mgc												200	11	mgc												261			
		-130	-365	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	126	103	-73	200			-139	-338	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	109	103	-13	261	
		-85	-89	32	174	-13	-15	31	-19	39	115	105	-75	200			-85	-89	32	174	-13	-15	31	-19	39	116	105	-15	261	
		57	121	11	85	-11	15	-101	48	-28	-27	107	-77	200			57	121	11	85	-11	15	-101	48	-28	-26	107	-17	261	
		59	-5	21	17	19	43	25	100	-80	-29	109	-79	200			59	-5	21	17	19	43	25	100	-80	-28	109	-19	261	
		61	-7	7	5	59	29	27	-21	41	-31	-849	879	200			61	-7	7	5	59	29	27	-21	41	-30	-549	639	261	
		63	-9	61	-7	33	13	29	-23	43	-33	111	-81	200			63	-9	61	-7	33	13	29	-23	43	-32	111	-21	261	
		65	109	-12	-154	33	35	109	-25	45	-35	113	-83	200			65	109	-12	-154	33	35	109	-25	45	-34	113	-23	261	
		67	-85	15	217	-27	-29	-31	10	70	-37	115	-85	200			67	-85	15	217	-27	-29	-31	10	70	-36	115	-25	261	
		69	105	5	-197	47	49	51	70	10	-39	117	-87	200			69	105	5	-197	47	49	51	70	10	-38	117	-27	261	
		-56	395	-41	-43	-45	-47	-49	-51	-53	160	119	-89	200			-46	369	-40	-42	-44	-46	-48	-50	-52	170	119	-29	261	
		87	554	89	91	-1156	93	95	97	99	101	15	35	200			87	493	89	91	-795	93	95	97	99	101	45	-234	261	
		-57	-524	-59	-61	1186	-63	-65	-67	-69	-71	35	15	200			3	-403	1	-1	885	-3	-5	-7	-9	-11	-234	45	261	
		200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200			261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 100$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 120$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 140$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 170$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 100$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 120$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 140$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 171$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 261$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. To avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums (L, R) are **even** numbers for **first example** and **odd** numbers for **second example**. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 20 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 30 \times 150$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} = 20 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 90 \times 450$$

Result 3.29. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

10*T-9*L	27*L-28*T-A51-A50-A49-A47-A46-A45-A43-A44-A41-A42-A38-A39-A40-A37-A48	A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	A50	A51	A43+A44+A41+A42+A38+A39+A40+A37+18*T-17*L	A61	R-L-A61
A37-T	T-S-A28	2*T+3*S+A30-A25-A31	T-S-A25	A29+2*A28-7*T+2*S+A27+A26+2*A25+A32+A33+A35+2*A31+A34	T-S-A26	T-S-A27	T-S-A29	T-A32-A33-A35-A31-A34-A28-A30	L-A37	A62	R-L-A62
A38	T-S-A31	A19+A20+A21+A22+A23-A4-A7-A11-A15	A4	A7	A11	A15	S-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23	A31	L-T-A38	A63	R-L-A63
A39	T-S-A32	S-A12-A5-A8-A16-A19	A5	A8	A12	A16	A19	A32	L-T-A39	A64	R-L-A64
A40	T-S-A33	A4+A7+A11+A15-A20-A21-A22-A23-A1-A2-A3+A5+A8+A12+A16	S-A4-A5-A12+A21+A22+A23-A17-A7-A8-A15-A16-A13-A9-A11+A1+A2+A3	A9	A13	A17	A20	A33	L-T-A40	A65	R-L-A65
A41	T-S-A34	A1	S+A16+A13+A6-A19+A3-A1-A18-A14-2*A21-A22-A23-A20	A21+A22+A23+A20-A16-A13-A6+A19-A3	A14	A18	A21	A34	L-T-A41	A66	R-L-A66
A42	T-S-A35	A2	S+A16+A13-A9+A6-A19+A3-A10-A21-A22-A23-A20-A7-A8	A5+A14+A10+2*A21+A22+3*A23+2*A20-A4+A8-A15-A16-A13+2*A9-2*A6+2*A19-A11-A2-A3-S	S-A19-A20-A21-A22-2*A23+A4+A7+A11+A15-A5-A9-A14	A22	A35	L-T-A42	A67	R-L-A67	
A43	T-S-A30	A3	A12+A18+A14+A21+A20+A17+A7+A8+A15+A9-2*A6+A19+A11-A2-2*A3-S	A10	2*S+A4-A8+A15+A16-2*A9+2*A6-2*A19+A2+A3-A12-A5-2*A14-A10-2*A21-A22-3*A23-2*A20	A19+A20+A21+A22+2*A23-A4-A7-A11+A5+A9+A14-2*A15-A16-A17-A18	A23	A30	L-T-A43	A68	R-L-A68
A44	A28+A30+7*S+A32+A33+A35+A31+A34-6*T	A25+A31-T-A30-4*S	A25	8*T-A29-2*A28-3*S-A27-A26-2*A25-A32-A33-A35-2*A31-A34	A26	A27	A29	A28	L-T-A44	A69	R-L-A69
10*L-9*T-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44	27*T+A51+A50+A49+A47+A46+A45+A43+A44+A41+A42+A38+A39+A40+A37-26*L+A48	L-T-A45	L-T-A46	L-T-A47	L-T-A48	L-T-A49	L-T-A50	L-T-A51	10*L-11*T	5*(R-L)-A61-A62-A63-A64-A65-A66-A67-A68-A69	4*(L-R)+A61+A62+A63+A64+A65+A66+A67+A68+A69
A32+A5+A25-S-A11+2*A9+A8-A16-A13+3*A23+2*A10+A22+A18+A14+3*A20-A38+A62+R-A61-A2-2*T-A15-A4-2*A6+2*A21-A3+2*A19-A45+A53	A53	A54	A55	A56	A57	A58	A59	A60	S+A11-2*A9-A8+A16+A13-3*A23-2*A10-A22-A18-A14-3*A20-A54-A59-A60-A55-A56-A57-A58+A38-A62+4*R+A61+A2+2*T+A15-5*L+A4+2*A6-2*A21+A3-2*A19+A45-2*A53-A32-A5-A25	(R-L)/2	(11*L-9*R)/2
S+A11-2*A9-A8+A16+A13-3*A23-2*A10-A22-A18-A14-3*A20+A38-A62+A61+A2+2*T+A15-L+A4+2*A6-2*A21+A3-2*A19+A45-A53-A32-A5-A25	R-L-A53	R-L-A54	R-L-A55	R-L-A56	R-L-A57	R-L-A58	R-L-A59	R-L-A60	A32+A5+A25-S-A11+2*A9+A8-A16-A13+3*A23+2*A10+A22+A18+A14+3*A20+A54+A59+A60+A55+A56+A57+A58-A38+A62-3*R-A61-A2-2*T-A15+4*L-A4-2*A6+2*A21-A3+2*A19-A45+2*A53	(11*L-9*R)/2	(R-L)/2

Details:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper-left corner. Order 10 magic square is embedded again with a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 8 having order 6 magic square at the middle. The blocks of orders 8 and 10 may be a **semi-magic** squares but still we can get order 12 as a magic square. The magic rectangles of orders 2×10 are of equal width and length. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums of the pair (L, R) should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd**. See below two examples.

Example 3.29. Let's consider following two examples:

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												280
-190	100	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	-106	71	-1	280	
-123	52	544	55	-516	54	53	51	-123	163	72	-2	280	
48	49	78	14	17	21	25	-75	41	-8	73	-3	280	
49	48	-30	15	18	22	26	29	42	-9	74	-4	280	
50	47	-4	-15	19	23	27	30	43	-10	75	-5	280	
51	46	11	-91	77	24	28	31	44	-11	76	-6	280	
52	45	12	16	-71	180	-89	32	45	-12	77	-7	280	
53	50	13	141	20	-190	63	33	40	-13	78	-8	280	
54	-167	-454	35	606	36	37	39	38	-14	79	-9	280	
166	-60	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	230	-325	395	280	
236	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	-418	35	-105	280	
-166	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	488	-105	35	280	
26a	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												295
-325	505	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	-361	71	-1	295	
-123	52	544	55	-516	54	53	51	-123	178	72	-2	295	
48	49	78	14	17	21	25	-75	41	7	73	-3	295	
49	48	-30	15	18	22	26	29	42	6	74	-4	295	
50	47	-4	-15	19	23	27	30	43	5	75	-5	295	
51	46	11	-91	77	24	28	31	44	4	76	-6	295	
52	45	12	16	-71	180	-89	32	45	3	77	-7	295	
53	50	13	141	20	-190	63	33	40	2	78	-8	295	
54	-167	-454	35	606	36	37	39	38	1	79	-9	295	
316	-450	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	380	-325	395	295	
251	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	-433	35	-90	295	
-181	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	503	-90	35	295	
26a	295	295	295	295	295	295	295	295	295	295	295	295	

The magic sums of above two magic squares are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 80$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 170$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 210$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 280$$

Second Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 80$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 170$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 225$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 295$$

The magic rectangles sums are given by

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 70 \times 350$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 70 \times 350.$$

Result 3.30. *Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:*

10*T-9*L	27*L-28*T-A37-A36-A35-A33-A32-A31-A29-A30-A27-A28-A24-A25-A26-A23-A34	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A29+A30+A27+A28+A24+A25+A26+A23+18*T-17*L	A47	R-L-A47
A23-T	T-2*M-A21	12*M-6*T+A10+A11+A12+A13+A14+A15+A16+A17+A18+A19+A20+2*A21	T-2*M-A16	T-2*M-A17	T-2*M-A18	T-2*M-A19	T-2*M-A20	T-A10-A11-A12-A13-A14-A15-A21	L-A23	A48	R-L-A48
A24	T-2*M-A10	2*M/3-A6	A6+A7-M/3	2*M/3-A7	2*M/3-A2	A2+A3-M/3	2*M/3-A3	A10	L-T-A24	A49	R-L-A49
A25	T-2*M-A11	A6+A8-M/3	M+A1-A6-A7-A8	M/3+A7-A1	A2+A4-M/3	5*M/3-A3-A2-A4-A5	A3+A5-M/3	A11	L-T-A25	A50	R-L-A50
A26	T-2*M-A12	2*M/3-A8	M/3+A8-A1	A1	2*M/3-A4	A4+A5-M/3	2*M/3-A5	A12	L-T-A26	A51	R-L-A51
A27	T-2*M-A13	A2	M-A2-A3	A3	A6	M-A6-A7	A7	A13	L-T-A27	A52	R-L-A52
A28	T-2*M-A14	M-A2-A4	A2+A3+A4+A5-M	M-A3-A5	M-A6-A8	A6+A7+A8-A1-M/3	M/3-A7+A1	A14	L-T-A28	A53	R-L-A53
A29	T-2*M-A15	A4	M-A4-A5	A5	A8	M/3-A8+A1	2*M/3-A1	A15	L-T-A29	A54	R-L-A54
A30	14*M-6*T+A10+A11+A12+A13+A14+A15+A21	7*(T-2*M)-A10-A11-A12-A13-A14-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19-A20-2*A21	A16	A17	A18	A19	A20	A21	L-T-A30	A55	R-L-A55
10*L-9*T-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30	27*T+A37+A36+A35+A33+A32+A31+A29+A30+A27+A28+A24+A25+A26+A23-26*L+A34	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	10*L-11*T	5*R-5*L-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55	4*(L-R)+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54+A55
A11-A8-2*A6-A7+(8/3)*M+R+A39+A16-2*T-A24-A31+A48-A47	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	A46	4*R-5*L-A11+A8+2*A6+A7-(8/3)*M-2*A39-A16+2*T+A24+A31-A48+A47-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46	(R-L)/2	(11*L-9*R)/2
A8+2*A6+A7-(8/3)*M-A39-A16+2*T+A24+A31-A48+A47-L-A11	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	4*L-3*R+A11-A8-2*A6-A7+(8/3)*M+2*A39+A16-2*T-A24-A31+A48-A47+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46	(11*L-9*R)/2	(R-L)/2

Details:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper-left corner. Order 10 magic square is embedded again with a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 8 having order 6 magic square at the middle. This magic square of order 8 is again composed with four equal sums magic squares of order 3. The blocks of orders 8 and 10 may be a **semi-magic** squares but still we can get order 12 as a magic square. The magic rectangles of orders 2×10 are of equal width and length. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 3, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums of the pair (L, R) should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd**. See below two examples.

Example 3.30. Let's consider following two examples:

mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												310	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												343
-250	-320	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	50	149	-89	310	-205	-455	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	135	149	-51	343		
-123	-15	389	0	-3	-6	-9	-12	-144	173	152	-92	310	-123	-15	389	0	-3	-6	-9	-12	-144	168	152	-54	343		
80	18	22	31	19	34	7	31	38	-30	155	-95	310	80	18	22	31	19	34	7	31	38	-35	155	-57	343		
83	15	34	-4	42	10	46	16	41	-33	158	-98	310	83	15	34	-4	42	10	46	16	41	-38	158	-60	343		
86	12	16	45	11	28	19	25	44	-36	161	-101	310	86	12	16	45	11	28	19	25	44	-41	161	-63	343		
89	9	14	41	17	26	17	29	47	-39	164	-104	310	89	9	14	41	17	26	17	29	47	-44	164	-66	343		
92	6	38	2	32	14	52	6	50	-42	167	-107	310	92	6	38	2	32	14	52	6	50	-47	167	-69	343		
95	3	20	29	23	32	3	37	53	-45	170	-110	310	95	3	20	29	23	32	3	37	53	-50	170	-72	343		
98	152	-333	56	59	62	65	68	71	-48	173	-113	310	98	152	-333	56	59	62	65	68	71	-53	173	-75	343		
0	370	-51	-54	-57	-60	-63	-66	-69	300	-1149	1209	310	-50	500	-56	-59	-62	-65	-68	-71	-74	250	-959	1057	343		
33	125	128	131	134	137	140	143	146	-817	30	-20	310	66	125	128	131	134	137	140	143	146	-660	49	-196	343		
27	-65	-68	-71	-74	-77	-80	-83	-86	877	-20	30	310	32	-27	-30	-33	-36	-39	-42	-45	-48	758	-196	49	343		
30a	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	30b	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	

The magic sums of above two magic squares are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{3 \times 3} = 72$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 144$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 200$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 250$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 310$$

Second Example

$$S_{3 \times 3} = 72$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 144$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 200$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 245$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 343$$

The magic rectangles sums are given by

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 60 \times 300$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 98 \times 490.$$

Result 3.31. *Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:*

10*T-9*L	27*L-28*T-A40-A39-A38-A36-A35-A34-A32-A33-A30-A31-A27-A28-A29-A26-A37	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A32+A33+A30+A31+A27+A28+A29+A26+18*T-17*L	A50	R-L-A50
A26-T	T-S-A23	2*T+3*S+A14-A20-A15	T-S-A20	A24+2*A23-7*T+2*S+A22+A21+2*A20+A16+A17+A19+2*A15+A18	T-S-A21	T-S-A22	T-S-A24	T-A16-A17-A19-A15-A18-A23-A14	L-A26	A51	R-L-A51
A27	T-S-A15	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	S-M-A10	A10	A15	L-T-A27	A52	R-L-A52
A28	T-S-A16	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A10+A11+A12-S+M	2*S-2*M-A10-A11-A12	A16	L-T-A28	A53	R-L-A53
A29	T-S-A17	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	S-M-A11	A11	A17	L-T-A29	5*(R-L)-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57-A58	4*(L-R)+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54+A55+A56+A57+A58
A30	T-S-A18	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6	A2	S-M-A12	A12	A18	L-T-A30	A54	R-L-A54
A31	T-S-A19	S-M-A8	2*S-A8-A1-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-M	2*A8+A1+A9+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12+M-2*S	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	(5*M-3*S)/2	A19	L-T-A31	A55	R-L-A55
A32	T-S-A14	A8	A8+A1+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12-S	3*S-2*A8-A1-A9-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-2*M	A9	(5*M-3*S)/2	(S-M)/2	A14	L-T-A32	A56	R-L-A56
A33	A23+A14+7*S+A16+A17+A19+A15+A18-6*T	A20+A15-T-A14-4*S	A20	8*T-A24-2*A23-3*S-A22-A21-2*A20-A16-A17-A19-2*A15-A18	A21	A22	A24	A23	L-T-A33	A57	R-L-A57
10*L-9*T-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33	27*T+A40+A39+A38+A36+A35+A34+A32+A33+A30+A31+A27+A28+A29+A26-26*L+A37	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	10*L-11*T	A58	R-L-A58
A20-A34+A51+A16-2*A9-2*T-A1+A42+R-A50-2*A8+5*S-4*M-3*A4-2*A12-2*A10-A27	A42	A43	A44	A34-A20-A51-A16+2*A9+2*T-A46-A47-A48-A43-A44-A45-2*A42+4*R-A49+A50+2*A8-5*L+A1-5*S+4*M+3*A4+2*A12+2*A10+A27	A45	A46	A47	A48	0	(R-L)/2	(11*L-9*R)/2
A34-L-A20-A51-A16+2*A9+2*T+A1-A42+A50+2*A8-5*S+4*M+3*A4+2*A12+2*A10+A27	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	A20-A34+A51+A16-2*A9-2*T+A46+A47+A48+A43+A44+A45+2*A42-3*R+A49-A50-2*A8+4*L-A1+5*S-4*M-3*A4-2*A12-2*A10-A27	R-L-A45	R-L-A46	R-L-A47	R-L-A48	R-L-A49	(11*L-9*R)/2	(R-L)/2

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper left corner containing **cornered** magic square of order 6 with a magic square of order 4. The blocks of orders 8 and 10 are **reduced entries semi-magic** squares, but the way they are constructed lead us to a magic square of order 12. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums (S, T) and (L, R) should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Example 3.31. Let's consider following two examples:

12	mgc												200	12	mgc												281			
		-150	45	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	-74	60	-10	200			-339	612	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	-431	60	50	281	
		-84	-13	509	-10	-257	-11	-12	-14	-72	114	61	-11	200			-84	-13	509	-10	-257	-11	-12	-14	-72	135	61	49	281	
		37	-5	11	57	-11	13	10	20	25	-7	62	-12	200			37	-5	11	57	-11	13	10	20	25	14	62	48	281	
		38	-6	16	14	15	25	33	-3	26	-8	63	-13	200			38	-6	16	14	15	25	33	-3	26	13	63	47	281	
		39	-7	9	8	33	20	9	21	27	-9	-326	376	200			39	-7	9	8	33	20	9	21	27	12	-26	136	281	
		40	-8	34	-9	33	12	8	22	28	-10	64	-14	200			40	-8	34	-9	33	12	8	22	28	11	64	46	281	
		41	-9	12	-24	61	11	15	25	29	-11	65	-15	200			41	-9	12	-24	61	11	15	25	29	10	65	45	281	
		42	-4	18	54	-31	19	25	15	24	-12	66	-16	200			42	-4	18	54	-31	19	25	15	24	9	66	44	281	
		43	172	-489	30	277	31	32	34	33	-13	67	-17	200			43	172	-489	30	277	31	32	34	33	8	67	43	281	
		104	-15	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	180	68	-18	200			314	-561	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	390	68	42	281	
		-3	52	53	54	-191	55	56	57	58	59	25	-75	200			78	52	53	54	28	55	56	57	58	59	55	-324	281	
		53	-2	-3	-4	241	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-75	25	200			32	58	57	56	82	55	54	53	52	51	-324	55	281	
		200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200			281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 70$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 100$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 120$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 150$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 70$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 100$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 120$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 171$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 281$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. To avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums (L, R) are **even** numbers for **first example** and **odd** numbers for **second example**. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 50 \times 250$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} = 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 110 \times 550$$

Result 3.32. Let's consider following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:

10*T+A46-9*L	27*L-2*A46-28*T-A45-A44-A43-A41-A40-A39-A37-A38-A35-A36-A32-A33-A34-A31-A42	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	A46+A38+A37+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31+18*T-17*L	A55	R-L-A55
A31-T	T-S-A27	2*T+3*S+A17-2*A14-A24-2*A13-2*A8-5*M-3*A4-A18-2*A15	T-S-A24	A28+2*A27+2*A14-7*T+2*S+A26+A25+2*A24+2*A13+2*A8+5*M+3*A4+A19+A20+A22+2*A18+2*A15+A21	T-S-A25	T-S-A26	T-S-A28	T-A19-A20-A22-A18-A21-A27-A17	L-A31	A56	R-L-A56
A32	T-S-A18	S-M-A15	S-A13-M	2*A11-3*A4-A13-A8+A9+M	3*A4-3*S+2*A13+A14+2*A8+A9-A10+2*A15+2*M	S-A14-M	S-A8-A9-A10-A11-A15	A18	L-T-A32	A57	R-L-A57
A33	T-S-A19	S-M-A9	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	A9	A19	L-T-A33	A58	R-L-A58
A34	T-S-A20	S-M-A10	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A10	A20	L-T-A34	5*(R-L)-A55-A56-A57-A58-A59-A60-A61-A62-A63	4*(L-R)+A55+A56+A57+A58+A59+A60+A61+A62+A63
A35	T-S-A21	S-M-A11	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	A11	A21	L-T-A35	A59	R-L-A59
A36	T-S-A22	S-M-A8	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6	A2	A8	A22	L-T-A36	A60	R-L-A60
A37	T-S-A17	A8-4*S+A9+A10+A11+A15+5*M	A13	S-2*A11+3*A4+A13+A8-A9-2*M	4*S+A11-3*A4-2*A13-A14-2*A8-A10-2*A15-3*M	A14	A15	A17	L-T-A37	A61	R-L-A61
A38	A27+A17+7*S+A19+A20+A22+A18+A21-6*T	A24+2*A13+2*A8+5*M+3*A4+A18+2*A15-T-A17+2*A14-4*S	A24	8*T-A28-2*A27-2*A14-3*S-A26-A25-2*A24-2*A13-2*A8-5*M-3*A4-A19-A20-A22-2*A18-2*A15-A21	A25	A26	A28	A27	L-T-A38	A62	R-L-A62
10*L-9*T-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A46	27*T+2*A46+A45+A44+A43+A41+A40+A39+A37+A38+A35+A36+A32+A33+A34+A31-26*L+A42	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	L-T-A41	L-T-A42	L-T-A43	L-T-A44	L-T-A45	10*L-11*T-A46	A63	R-L-A63
A47	A32-A19-A24-S-A13+2*A11+2*M+A39-6*A4-A10-R-A56+2*T-A8+A9+A55-A1+A47	A48	A49	A19+A24+S-A32+A13-2*A11-2*M-A39+6*A4+A10+6*R+A56-5*L-2*T+A8-A9-A53-A54-A55+A1-A52-A51-A50-A49-A48-2*A47	A50	A51	A52	A53	A54	(R-L)/2	(11*L-9*R)/2
R-L-A47	2*R-L+A19+A24+S-A32+A13-2*A11-2*M-A39+6*A4+A10+A56-2*T+A8-A9-A55+A1-A47	R-L-A48	R-L-A49	A32-A19-A24-S-A13+2*A11+2*M+A39-6*A4-A10-5*R-A56+4*L+2*T-A8+A9+A53+A54+A55-A1+A52+A51+A50+A49+A48+2*A47	R-L-A50	R-L-A51	R-L-A52	R-L-A53	R-L-A54	(11*L-9*R)/2	(R-L)/2

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 12 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 at the upper left corner containing magic square of order 4. The blocks of orders 6, 8 and 10 are **reduced entries semi-magic** squares, but the way they are constructed lead us to a magic square of order 12. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×10 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic sums for the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums L and R should be of same type, i.e., either even or odd.

Example 3.32. Let's consider following two examples:

13	mgc												200	13	mgc												301		
		-194	138	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	-158	65	-15	200			-473	975	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	-685	65	55	301
		-69	-7	-97	-4	341	-5	-6	-8	-104	109	66	-16	200			-69	-7	-97	-4	341	-5	-6	-8	-104	140	66	54	301
		42	2	-5	-3	38	77	-4	-23	28	-2	67	-17	200			42	2	-5	-3	38	77	-4	-23	28	29	67	53	301
		43	1	1	11	47	-11	13	19	29	-3	68	-18	200			43	1	1	11	47	-11	13	19	29	28	68	52	301
		44	0	0	16	14	15	15	20	30	-4	-371	421	200			44	0	0	16	14	15	15	20	30	27	-21	141	301
		45	-1	-1	9	8	23	20	21	31	-5	69	-19	200			45	-1	-1	9	8	23	20	21	31	26	69	51	301
		46	-2	2	24	-9	33	12	18	32	-6	70	-20	200			46	-2	2	24	-9	33	12	18	32	25	70	50	301
		47	3	83	23	-18	-57	24	25	27	-7	71	-21	200			47	3	83	23	-18	-57	24	25	27	24	71	49	301
		48	114	127	34	-311	35	36	38	37	-8	72	-22	200			48	114	127	34	-311	35	36	38	37	23	72	48	301
		98	-98	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	234	73	-23	200			408	-904	22	21	20	19	18	17	16	544	73	47	301
		57	49	58	59	-283	60	61	62	63	64	25	-75	200			57	-52	58	59	168	60	61	62	63	64	60	-359	301
		-7	1	-8	-9	333	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-75	25	200			63	172	62	61	-48	60	59	58	57	56	-359	60	301
		200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200			301	301	301	301	301	301	301	301	301	301	301	301	301

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 60$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 80$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 110$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 150$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} = 60$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 80$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} = 110$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} = 181$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} = 301$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. To avoid decimal entries, the pair of magic sums (L, R) are **even** numbers for **first example** and **odd** numbers for **second example**. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 50 \times 250$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 10} = 120 \times 600$$

4 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** lease see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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